

A landscape study on open access and monographs

Policies, funding and publishing in eight European countries

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Executive summary

Overall observations

Some overall observations and context for our study:

- ▶ We are cautiously optimistic about the prospects for a significant amount of European long-form scholarship to be published as OA, despite well-known obstacles
- ▶ There is substantial funding that could be re-routed in various ways to pay for the publishing of books more efficiently, although we recognise that this involves complex operational changes
- ▶ Countries in the study are similar in many ways, however, there are huge differences in population size, book markets, OA policies, funding streams and publishers' approaches to OA
- ▶ No single model will fit all and there is no scenario for a perfect transition. Indeed, we do not expect all monographs to go OA, but we see a number of ways in which OA for books can be encouraged further
- ▶ Monograph sales are steadily declining, destabilising academic book publishers, raising barriers for early career authors, undermining the monograph as a valuable form of scholarly output and thereby reducing scholars' choice of output
- ▶ Academic book publishers in many continental countries continue to rely on "print" subsidies from public and private funds that could in theory be rechanneled to pay for OA publishing
- ▶ Successful pure OA monograph publishing initiatives in various countries are demonstrating clear benefits, though scaling will require further support
- ▶ OA for monographs is becoming an accepted publication model, offered by leading book publishers. Authors are increasingly becoming aware of the benefits of increased exposure

- ▶ Stakeholders are working towards greater OA in the countries in this study at varying speeds

The report looks at OA and monographs in eight countries and presents information on the following key issues:

- ▶ Inclusion of OA monographs in OA policies
- ▶ Funding streams to support OA monographs
- ▶ Business models for publishing OA monographs

Our conclusions are summarised here and followed by our main recommendations for Knowledge Exchange.

Inclusion of OA monographs in OA policies

National policies on OA for books are not consistent across the eight countries despite encouragement in policy statements from a number of EU and European level agencies.

Austria is the only country that has a coordinated, more or less country wide, approach to OA with an OA mandate that includes monographs.

Some research funders have begun mandating that books and book chapters are available in OA and are providing funding. An example at the European level is the ERC and the independent foundation in the UK, The Wellcome Trust, operates its policy on a global level. At the national level we have FWF in Austria and NWO in the Netherlands.

The transition to OA books will benefit from the connection to research assessment programmes (in particular the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and the REF in the mid 2020s).

Although the benefits of OA are similar for all countries, the context of the transition in the case of books varies from one country to the next. Countries with small,

domestically oriented academic book industries have different needs to those that have a very large book publishing industry.

Funding streams to support OA monographs

The extent of state support for scholarly publishing is an important factor in how OA for monographs is perceived, as well as funded.

There are many different book publishing models that co-exist, ranging from commercial publishers and non-subsidised university presses to subsidised (and in some cases fully funded) publishing operations within institutions. There are different divides in different countries. For instance, in the UK there are commercial and highly profitable university presses alongside library-based, fully funded new university presses, and in Germany there are commercial publishers requiring print subsidies also alongside library-based university presses. The way these publishers can develop OA publishing models is influenced by national economic structures and traditions.

Libraries in many countries support OA monographs either directly or indirectly, through activities as varied as supplying information on funding opportunities to managing publication funds. New library initiatives in some countries are establishing pure OA publishers.

Ad hoc funding for BPCs is a less recognised, but significant funding source in some university departments and research institutions.

Libraries also support OA monographs through crowd-funding initiatives like Knowledge Unlatched (KU sources funding from over 400 libraries in 25 countries).

Despite varying levels of support for OA monographs, the chief obstacle in moving forward is funding, and the re-routing of existing funds is especially challenging. A key to moving forward will be support from university administrators, including top-level librarians.

Business models for publishing OA monographs

From the publisher perspective, obstacles to moving to OA for monographs include the changes that will be required in publishing business models and workflows, as well as authorial understanding and acceptance of the benefits.

Publishers of all kinds in all countries are experiencing issues around covering the costs of monographs – whether through subsidies or sales. Therefore, publishers are becoming increasingly interested in OA options – if sufficiently funded.

It is unlikely that any single, overarching business model will gather much traction as the solutions will be multifaceted and different within different types of publishing operations and within each country – though learning from each others' experiences would be very helpful going forward.

There are some experiments in university and academic-led publishing that are dotting the landscape - providing some interesting alternative business models, though scaling will be a challenge. These tend to rely on mixed funding sources, such as grants, memberships, free labour, in kind support and print and e-book sales.

Recommendations for Knowledge Exchange

Adoption of OA policies and mandates for monographs was never going to have a smooth ride, however, it is very possible to avoid some of the mistakes and polarising of positions that have taken place in the journals world. This is largely because the money at stake is relatively small and publishing monographs is less concentrated in the hands of a few large multinationals. Therefore, we would encourage both research and awareness-raising on a number of fronts.

Below are a number of areas where Knowledge Exchange might make a positive contribution, either on its own or in partnership with others.

Recommendations in the area of policies and funding:

- ▶ Facilitate exchange of ideas and foster awareness for policy makers across countries on the issues around encouragement and mandating of OA for monographs
- ▶ Facilitate the streamlining of OA requirements and compliance in the way BPCs are being administered. Support campaigns for compliance
- ▶ Convene with other stakeholders to pave the way towards OA monographs, to explore coordinated approaches by funders and libraries, following the OA2020 initiative for articles
- ▶ Establish a permanent Open Access Book Watch (OABW), to monitor progress, to identify good practices, examples, and business cases, to provide a tool for funders and policy makers

Recommendations in the area of publishing:

- ▶ Provide a forum for publishers to exchange ideas and experiences on how to accomplish successful OA monograph publishing
- ▶ Address misconceptions around OA books by supporting and showcasing success stories
- ▶ Look beyond OA to related aspects of monograph publishing: service levels, quality assurance, transparency, pricing and incentive structures for authors
- ▶ Contribute to modelling lower cost base monographs without sacrificing quality
- ▶ Support research projects to improve dissemination and discovery of OA monographs as well as to improve understanding of the barriers that exist in today's supply chain
- ▶ Support the development of a toolkit on OA books (this could be partly based on existing work, looking at various aspects of OA book publishing: metadata; information that publishers should make available; licensing; self-archiving; funder requirements; peer-review; metrics; dissemination and discovery)
- ▶ Identify key infrastructures for a transition to OA, looking at what is already available and what is still needed, in line with earlier KE work

Guide to the report

The structure of the report is such that the reader can dip into particular areas of interest, or read the whole. Here we indicate some signposts.

Part one (Chapters 1-4):

We begin with a very short introduction that is then followed by Chapter 2, “The brief and methodology”. Chapter 3 offers an overview called “The open access monograph publishing landscape”. This is where we introduce the general themes of the report. We answer the brief looking at policies, funding streams and publishing business models. We contextualise our findings from our individual country studies and draw out similarities and differences between countries. It is where we consolidate most of the data we collected and analyse and incorporate our comparative observations on the eight countries. We’ve placed the recommendations for further work that Knowledge Exchange might consider in Chapter 4.

Part two (Chapters 5-6):

After a brief introduction to the country studies in Chapter 5 we present the country studies themselves and include a short comparison of the Nordic countries in Chapter 6. While this part has only two chapters, it is Chapter 6, covering the eight countries, that makes up nearly half the report.

Part three (Chapters 7-8):

We were concerned that notable initiatives might get lost in the country studies, so we decided to create Chapter 7, which has as its objective highlighting the large and encouraging variety of initiatives that are underway. Information gaps and recommendations to stakeholders are covered in Chapter 8. We hope that some of the information gaps will be addressed by further projects, either by Knowledge Exchange or other bodies.

Part four – Appendices (Chapters 9-16):

Part four consists of eight appendices. The first one is a literature review. It is striking how difficult it is to segregate policy on books from articles in policy documents, and this is borne out through the literature review itself. The second appendix, “Why BPC costs vary so much” was authored by Frances Pinter and draws on her experience as a British publisher for many decades. It aims to shed light on the vexed question of its title with relevance for all the countries. This is followed by “Assessing the Impact of OA Books”, specially commissioned from Ronald Snijder of OAPEN. We follow with a short version of the recommendations for the transition to open access in Austria, because we felt it to be a useful indication of the factors that need to be taken into account elsewhere. Next, we list the stakeholder organisations and companies we interviewed, but not the individuals for purposes of anonymity. A list of acronyms is included. Then follow acknowledgements to the many helpful people we met along the way while working on this study. Finally, we present the questionnaires used both for the online survey and for our interviews.

Part one

1

1. Introduction to Part one

In this part we introduce the reader to the brief set by Knowledge Exchange and the methodology that was employed to conduct the study.

In the brief for this landscape study on open access (OA) monographs two main objectives were presented:

- ▶ Analyse existing information about:
 - › The inclusion of OA monographs in OA policies
 - › Funding streams to support OA monographs
 - › Business models for publishing OA monographs
- ▶ Establish any information gaps or areas where Knowledge Exchange (KE) could contribute to the development of OA monographs

In the chapter on the “Brief and methodology” we discuss how we enlarged not only the number of countries in the study beyond the original five, but also drew parameters around what additional information we felt needed to be in scope and what would be out of scope. We had set out to find clear indicators of progress in the area of OA for monographs, but found that a number of areas that we’d wished to explore and develop as benchmarks fell out of the scope of this modest study with data either hard to come by or non-existent.

Chapter three, “The open access monograph publishing landscape”, is the main chapter that analyses and incorporates our comparative observations on the eight countries in this study. We began by following the three headings as per the brief above but quickly incorporated other factors that we felt needed to be taken into account. Country size, language(s) of publication, presence of multinational corporations and socio-economic cultures of countries varied widely and we wanted to place our findings into context in this chapter.

The construction of this chapter led to long discussions about what types of approaches, models and attitudes are prevalent in each country – only to agree that polarisations along the lines of commercial/non-commercial, for profit/university press, Anglo-Saxon/continental were not especially helpful. Each country has people within each stakeholder group holding a range of views on the need or otherwise to make monographs open access (and to encourage/mandate or not). Every country has access to a range of funding opportunities for OA monographs. While it has to be said that the money across all eight countries appears to be far from adequate, reconfiguring how support for monographs is spent could help to reduce the shortfall. Finally, there are a number of reasons as to why we agree that there is a need for a number of business models to serve the needs of OA monographs. Several other studies have contributed thoughts on this and we refer the reader to them through the literature review in the appendix (Chapter 9).

“There is a need for a number of business models to serve the needs of OA monographs.”

In our study we have focused on developing a typology of publishers that is introduced in Chapter 3. To provide some further context we have followed the typology with a section called “Other aspects of making the transition to OA” where we cover issues that need addressing to make any of the OA business models work effectively. We touch on quality control, discoverability and visibility, technical formats and platforms, supply chain hurdles, new marketing methods, standards, library and institutional engagement with OA, author attitudes to OA monographs, and especially infrastructure, much of which needs global scale transformation along with usage data and other metrics.

In constructing Chapter 3 we also felt the need to address the question of “Why book processing charge (BPC) costs vary so much”. The reader can find our attempt to address this in the appendix (Chapter 10). A much fuller examination and agreement of the range of services provided by the whole range of monograph publishers would be helpful. This would certainly bring down the heat in the discussions when comparing costs.

Finally, in Chapter 4 we list our recommendations to Knowledge Exchange for additional work that KE might undertake or encourage others to do.

2. Brief and methodology

2.1 The brief

In the brief for this landscape study on OA monographs two main objectives were presented:

- ▶ Analyse existing information about
 - › The inclusion of OA monographs in OA policies
 - › Funding streams to support OA monographs
 - › Business models for publishing OA monographs

- ▶ Establish any information gaps or areas where Knowledge Exchange (KE) could contribute to the development of OA monographs

The brief further stipulated some key areas of investigation including: the costs of OA books; the fees being charged for OA books; the range of non-BPC models, and the adoption of OA policies for books by funders (both public and private), universities, and publishers. The investigation should be undertaken in the KE countries, ie Denmark, Finland, Germany, Netherlands and United Kingdom (at the time France was intended to be part of KE but the brief didn't mention this). Furthermore the investigation was asked to cover traditional publishers (including commercial publishers), established university presses, learned society presses, pure OA publishers, and library-driven presses.

Considering these different actors our primary goal for the landscape study was to come up with comparable data and analysis of the KE countries as requested under key areas of investigation. To do so we developed a methodology that in effect is a cascade with three main components – metrics collection, web-based questionnaires and interviews.

We enlarged the landscape study to include Norway and Austria because we thought this would enrich the study bringing in perspectives, issues and cases from two countries that in different ways have been active in this area. The two organisations, CRISTin in Norway and FWF in Austria, kindly offered to support the study

financially. We also approached Couperin to include France in the study as they were not formally part of Knowledge Exchange at the time we began. Couperin also kindly offered financial support.

2.2 Scope

2.2.1 Definition of the monograph

What is a monograph? This is very hard to define in a narrow sense and between countries we have noticed significant differences. However, while working with our questionnaires and interview questions we realised that we had to come up with a working definition of the **monograph** and that this definition had to be not too rigid. We therefore came up with this definition:

A long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, and extended to also include peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.

Although this definition has been helpful we still have to acknowledge that the boundaries between e.g. a monograph and a trade book for primarily an academic audience can be rather blurred. Wherever possible we have addressed potential confusions of what a monograph is and overall instigated a pragmatic approach to the concept. Throughout the report we use the terms “monograph” and “book” synonymously.

2.2.2 Definition of open access

Since the early 1990s, when the concept of open access became more widely used and accepted, the number of definitions has been vast. Most people refer to the BOAI¹ or Berlin Declaration² definitions which Peter Suber summarises in his book **Open Access** like this:

*Open access (OA) literature is digital, online, free of charge, and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions.*³

We use this general definition for our understanding of OA. We also use the terms gold and green OA in the way they are commonly used. Gold OA refers to manuscripts that are turned into monographs (or articles) and published OA by publishers whereas green OA refers to manuscripts that are being published non-OA by publishers but where the final and peer-reviewed manuscript version is deposited OA in an open repository.

2.2.3 Out of scope

The above definition of the monograph means that a lot of books intended for the academic community fall out of scope for this study. For instance, we leave out textbooks that generally have a significant commercial potential and we also do not include popularised monographs that are edited as trade books with the lay reader as target audience. At the other end of the spectrum we also leave out PhD dissertations (that have not been edited) and books that are compilations of articles. Nor did we include scholarly editions. Furthermore, report-type books (typically published by organisations) are also not part of our focus. As a consequence institutional publishers (international organisations, government bodies, NGOs etc) are not included in the study.

2.2.4 Stakeholders

As outlined in the brief and as proposed in our response to the call for tender we focused on three central stakeholder groups with regards to OA monographs: publishers, funders and libraries. The surveys and interviews were specifically targeted towards these groups. We did acknowledge that authors, obviously, play a crucial role in the field and we did promise to provide some indication of the challenges facing authors, many of whom have been reluctant to see their books made available free of charge. The importance of author attitudes, scholarly reward and incentive systems was raised throughout the study by numerous interviewees. We did not cover these in depth as other studies have already done so, such as the **Academic Book of the Future Report** and the OAPEN-UK study. However, we suggest that author attitudes might change over time and may vary in different disciplines, so regular studies should be conducted.

Footnotes

- 1 budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read
 - 2 <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>
 - 3 Page 4 in Peter Suber: *Open Access*. MIT Press, 2012 (<https://mitpress.mit.edu/books/open-access>)
-

“The methodology employed was a mix of desk work (involving metrics gathering and literature review), a web-based questionnaire, and interviews.”

2.3 Methodology

The methodology employed was a mix of desk work (involving metrics gathering and literature review), a web-based questionnaire, and interviews. From the different elements of the methodology we will identify information gaps and other issues in the transition to OA monographs, as well as good practices.

2.3.1 Metrics gathering and literature review

We hired a research assistant who undertook the tasks of gathering metrics, and conducting the literature search and review. All of this was undertaken under the direction of the principal investigators. Data sources included, for example: OpenAIRE; PMC Bookshelf; DOAB (information about OA book publishers and OA books); OAPEN (information on usage of OA books); ROARMAP (information on policies of funders and institutions); Knowledge Unlatched (information on libraries and OA title fees); OAPEN pilot projects (information on costs of monographs from the OAPEN-NL and OAPEN-CH pilots and information on sales and downloads from these projects and OAPEN-UK). Commercial sources such as Proquest and EBSCO and non-commercial ones such as OCLC are referred to.

The literature review has proved very valuable as input to the other parts of the study and as a structured presentation of existing observation and studies in the field. Furthermore, it provides a comprehensive bibliography of the relevant published literature on OA monographs.

2.3.2 Web-based questionnaires

As the second part of our methodology three separate but relationally linked questionnaires were developed and administered to a representative selection of three stakeholder communities: publishers, libraries and their host institutions and research funders. The processing of the questionnaires was undertaken by the researcher, while being designed by the principal investigators. Wherever possible we were looking to establish metrics and comparative ratios for benchmarking.

We used SurveyMonkey as our software tool to develop and send the questionnaires. The library questionnaire was sent to 370 libraries (via LIBER and directly), the publisher questionnaire to 164 publishers and the funder questionnaire to 57 funders. Return rates were, despite sending chasers, very poor; 15% for libraries, 25% for publishers and 16% for funders. The response rates were too low to consider aggregated measures statistically valid. However, there are a few countries where a sufficient number replied to be able to extract meaningful quantitative data. Nonetheless, these web-based questionnaires have produced a treasure trove of commentary where open fields for text were provided. Additionally, Couperin sent out an adapted version in French to libraries and this provided a higher response rate. In the Nordic countries personalised chaser emails were sent and in some instances (where appropriate) short adaptations of the questionnaires (for instance to funders) were sent. These efforts, however, did not significantly increase the response rates although it did give more responses and did add some valuable perspectives to the study.

Although we spent a significant amount of resources on the survey (relative to the size of the landscape study) our post-survey reflection has been that it would require significantly more resources to complete successfully. We were probably too ambitious when developing the questionnaires (too many questions) and we realised that the differences between the eight countries in terms of OA monograph development were at such a level that country specific questionnaires would have been better, although this would make data comparison very difficult. It is likely that the field of OA monographs needs more streamlining across nations and to be more developed before surveys of this kind can become an efficient method of comparative investigation.

2.3.3 Interviews

The purpose of the interviews was to complement the questionnaires and provide in-depth perspectives to the material gathered through desk research. These were conducted as 45-60 min. interviews either in person or by Skype/telephone. The principal investigators conducted all interviews (in-depth interviews with people from 73 institutions). A careful selection of interviewees was undertaken for each country ensuring a balanced representation among the key stakeholders. For each stakeholder group (publishers, funders and libraries) a set of thoroughly worked out questions was developed (20-25 questions).

Conducting this vast amount of interviews was very time-consuming but proved hugely successful. The field of OA monographs is still in its early evolution and therefore in-depth conversations were needed to understand the different developments among the different stakeholders. In this way the puzzle came together for each of the countries paving the way for further analysis at an aggregated level.

2.3.4 Design and implementation of indicators

Finally we have been gathering data throughout the project in order to add content to our proposed indicators. Transparency in the methodology and the data used will support the development of robust benchmarks that can be used by the community in order to gauge changes over time. Data has not been available for all indicators. However, these information gaps give valuable input to the overall gap analysis.

3. The open access monograph publishing landscape – an overview

3.1 Structure of this chapter

This chapter aims to provide an overview of the open access publishing landscape in eight European countries. It forms the core of our study.

In the first section of this chapter – 3.2 Introduction and background – we will look at the eight countries and some of the main differences between them, the role language plays in book publishing, and what we know (or don't know) about monograph output.

We then provide information and observations in three parts, as per the initial brief from KE: Inclusion of OA monographs in OA policies (3.3), Funding streams to support OA monographs (3.4), and Business models for publishing OA monographs (3.5). In the latter section we also present our typology of publishers.

Finally in section 3.6 – Other aspects of making the transition to OA – we discuss a range of other issues such as quality assurance, formats, discoverability, underlying infrastructure, supply chain hurdles, the role of libraries, author attitudes and more.

Wherever possible we draw comparisons across the eight countries. The perspectives are informed by the individual country studies presented in Part two of this report. Some of the gaps in information – many of which will be evident in this chapter are summarised in Part three.

3.2 Introduction and background

Each of our eight countries has approached OA differently and had different experiences with it. We attempt in this chapter to draw contrasts and similarities and to tease out reasons as to why things are as they are at present and what forces may prevail in any transition to OA in the future.

Our eight countries range in population from just over five million to over eighty million. This in itself is significant, along with the language(s) of publication. Choices on whether to publish in English or in one's national

language are made based on readership, impact and requirements for career promotion.

Table 1: Statistical indicators for the eight countries in our study

Country	*Population (2015)	**GDP US dollars/capital (2016)	***Tertiary education spending (% of GDP) (2013)
Austria	8,638,370	50,141	1.7
Denmark	5,683,480	49,972	1.7
Finland	5,479,530	43,105	1.8
France	66,538,390	41,945	1.5
Germany	81,679,770	49,055	1.2
Netherlands	16,939,920	51,136	1.7
Norway	5,190,240	63,220	1.6
UK	65,128,860	42,898	1.8

Sources:

* World Bank (2015)

<http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL>

** OECD (2017), Gross domestic product (GDP) (indicator).
doi: [10.1787/dc2f7aec-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/dc2f7aec-en) (Accessed on 20 May 2017)

*** OECD (2017), Education spending (indicator).
doi: [10.1787/ca274bac-en](https://doi.org/10.1787/ca274bac-en) (Accessed on 20 May 2017).

“Each of our eight countries has approached OA differently and had different experiences with it.”

In our study we looked at similarities and differences between the eight countries. In language terms we found the more natural link between Austria and Germany. The Nordic countries have certain similarities in size, but differing OA policies. The Netherlands has little in common with any of the countries largely because the Netherlands serves as the home country of a number of large and medium-sized multinationals and because of the lead it

“Funding is not, in itself, the prime obstacle; the main constraints are the willingness (or lack of it) to reconsider how monographs are published and lack of understanding of the benefits.”

has taken on promoting OA generally. France’s unique system of funding university presses is in sharp contrast with the way traditional university presses in the UK have covered their costs by generating income through sales. At the same time, there are numerous new university and academic-led presses cropping up in the UK that are born digital and OA. These are largely supported through institutional, and especially library, budgets and are more akin to the continental model for university presses.

We believe that the direction of travel for enabling monographs to be published on an open access basis is clear, though each country is approaching the issue differently. They are at varying stages of a transition towards enabling monographs to go OA and which is arguably only just beginning. We do not say that OA will be ubiquitous any time soon, but that the barriers are not insurmountable. Funding is not, in itself, the prime obstacle; the main constraints are the willingness (or lack of it) to reconsider how monographs are published and lack of understanding of the benefits.

Discussions about the “oversupply” of HSS monographs in and around the **Academic Book of the Future Report** (<https://academicbookfuture.org>) suggest that a two-track approach whereby more specialist monographs are produced at lower costs may contribute to alleviating pressures on funding publishing through sales and/or OA.

We also believe the forces that drive the evolution of OA monographs will not be the same as those that drove development of OA journal articles, despite certain similarities.

We look at each country study in detail in Chapter 6, but here we draw together our main observations. Once national policies, cultural traditions, publishing industry structures etc have been taken into account, we have found one more very forceful driver in the move to OA. That is the role of a few key individuals, either one or a very small handful in each country, that have pushed for change. We’ve also

seen progress at EU level. We agree with the recent report from Simba Information that OA books have the potential to grow substantially over the next few years, though we did not have the resources to undertake such a detailed evaluation ourselves. Nevertheless we hope this study will contribute to a greater understanding of roadblocks and what can be done to overcome them.

Throughout this report we talk about “policy” and “mandates”. The word mandate is used in the English language very broadly and can be a directive, an instruction from an authoritative body or even a law. In other languages “mandate” can sometimes take on a more restrictive meaning. To help our discussion we note the different forms of “encouragement” within stated policies, which may or may not lead to mandates.

Strong encouragements for OA books do not always translate into mandates. In addition, mandates do not always translate into efficient funding. Funded mandates are still a long way away for monographs in most of our countries, and the debates between green and gold continue in all the countries. However, monograph mandates are likely to follow where mandates for journal articles have paved the way. While the catch-up is slow, there are suggestions that this slower paced change can benefit from avoiding the pitfalls associated with journal articles. The various types of OA policies and mandates are discussed in more detail in the Literature Review, chapter 9.3.2 (Funders: OA policies and mandates).

3.2.1 The English language

Each European country has a distinct tradition of monograph publishing. Small countries publish primarily in the national language, have few monographs and where possible and appropriate encourage their researchers to publish in English with internationally known publishers. Most of the Nordic publishers produce some scholarly monographs in English although domestic language publishing dominates the market. Those publishing in English generally have distribution arrangements with

“We also believe the forces that drive the evolution of OA monographs will not be the same as those that drove development of OA journal articles, despite certain similarities.”

international distributors and or publishers to ensure access to the global market.

German publishers publish predominantly in the German language, although English is growing, especially from the larger book publishers and in certain disciplines. The Netherlands has a very high proportion of monographs published in English due to its international publishing history rooted in the Dutch Golden Age, and ultimately leading to a very large multinational publishing industry.

France has a relatively low proportion of books published in English by French publishers although there appear to be signs that this may be changing. The UK, of course, benefits not only from English being its mother tongue, but also from a well-established global sales infrastructure and from being home to the headquarters of a number of the major academic publishers.

3.2.2 Monograph output and open access

Although figures are hard to come by, we believe that the monograph output of the UK leads the world - publishing more monographs than even the United States although, of course, authors are sourced from all over the globe.

Estimates of annual monograph outputs vary significantly and figures are in no way comparable. They range from 20,000 to 40,000 per annum, but may or may not include edited volumes, proper peer review etc.

The number of OA monographs available globally in English at the time of issuing this report is estimated by Simba Information to be in the region of 10,000 titles.⁴ This is in the context of tens of thousands of conventionally published monographs that are considered “in print” (in English) and available for purchase. It is possible that the Simba figure may be on the low side, as DOAB currently lists 7,500 titles and we do not think DOAB has yet reached 75% of all OA output (many publishers are not yet listed, and some of the listed publishers are not up to date with uploading their OA titles – especially backlist books that were only recently turned into OA). The numbers in DOAB have been growing by over 50% in the last three years.

Footnotes

4 simbainformation.com/about/release.asp?id=4026

Figure 1: Number of OA books in countries of our study

Figure 2: OA books per continent

“According to ROARMAP, there are 245 OA policies worldwide that explicitly include books or book sections, from funders and research organisations.”

3.3 Inclusion of OA monographs in OA policies

According to ROARMAP, there are 245 OA policies worldwide that explicitly include books or book sections, from funders and research organisations.⁵ 85 of these policies are mandates, with the requirement to deposit and make publications open access.

Figure 3: Policies adopted by quarter

Source: ROARMAP

Footnotes

⁵ <http://roarmap.eprints.org>

Table 2: OA policies including books and book section

	OA policies, including books	Mandated OA
Funder (http://bit.ly/2woVFej)	18	8
Funder and research organisation (http://bit.ly/2vIAPzC)	3	1
Research organisation	219	76
Multiple research organisations (http://bit.ly/2woVeRm)	5	0
Total	245	85

Source: ROARMAP

Table 3: OA policies by region and organisation type

	Funders	Research organisations	Total OA policies	OA mandates
Worldwide	18	219	245	85
Europe	14	177	198	73
UK	1 (WT)	26	27	14
Germany	-	8	9	
France	1 (ANR)	7	8	4
Netherlands	1 (NWO)	4	5	1
Austria	1 (FWF)	4	5	2
Norway	-	3	3	
Denmark	-	2	2	2
Finland	-	1	1	1

Source: ROARMAP

An indicative list of funders, and funder and research organisations, worldwide (*indicates that the funders have mandates in place for OA books)

- ▶ Agence National de la recherche (ANR) Humanities & Social Sciences Branch
- ▶ Austrian Science Fund (FWF)*
- ▶ CGIAR
- ▶ Estonian Research Council
- ▶ European Research Council (ERC)*
- ▶ Fondazione Cariplo
- ▶ Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (Portugal)*
- ▶ Hungarian Scientific Research Fund (OTKA)
- ▶ Indian Council of Agricultural Research
- ▶ International Development Research Centre
- ▶ Irish Research Council for Science, Engineering & Technology (IRCSET)*
- ▶ Lietuvos mokslo taryba (Research Council of Lithuania)
- ▶ Lithuanian University of Health Sciences
- ▶ Ministry of Education and Research
- ▶ National Research Council Canada (NRC)
- ▶ Science Europe*
- ▶ Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)
- ▶ Spanish General State Administration*
- ▶ Wellcome *

The list is not completely accurate, as we know that both NWO (Netherlands) and SNSF (Switzerland) have OA mandates that include books. In addition, Science Europe does not actually fund research, but represents its members who are funding organisations.

In the table on the following page, we give an overview of OA mandates that include books from Wellcome, the European Research Council, the Austrian Science Fund, and the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research.

Table 4: OA mandates for books: policy characteristics of four main funders – Wellcome, ERC, FWF, and NWO – for illustrative purposes

	Wellcome	ERC	FWF	NWO
Scope of policy (content)	All original scholarly monographs and book chapters authored or co-authored by Wellcome grant holders	All monographs, book chapters and other long-text publications related to results from ERC funded research (for H2020: only peer reviewed publications are covered)	All peer reviewed research results of FWF funded research	All publications resulting from NWO grants after 1 Dec 2015
Maximum embargo	six months	6 months (12 months for outputs in the humanities and social sciences in H2020)	12 months (No embargo for FWF funded publications)	Immediate (no embargo)
Funding availability	Yes	Yes, within grant period	Yes: FWF has a separate funding programme for stand-alone publications (such as monographs and edited collections), which is available for FWF grant holders and researchers who conduct their research activities mainly in Austria or under the auspices of an Austrian research institution abroad	Yes, up to 6000 EUR for gold OA. However, Incentive Fund for gold OA will be terminated on 1 January 2018
Licence (gold)	CC BY preferred, other CC licences permitted	Not specified	Not specified (CC BY for FWF funded publications)	Not specified
Self-archiving of author manuscript	Allowed. Any licence	Allowed. Any licence	Allowed. Any licence	Allowed. Any licence
Repository	Deposit in a repository is required Wellcome mandates PMC Bookshelf, from which works will be mirrored to Europe PMC and OAPEN	Deposit in a repository is required The ERC recommends OAPEN	Deposit in a repository is required. (For FWF funded stand-alone publications: FWF mandates FWF-E-Book-Library, from which works are harvested by OAPEN)	Deposit in a repository is required in case of green OA Any trusted repository (OpenDOAR)
Deposit timing and process	If an open access fee is paid publishers must deposit the work on behalf of the author immediately upon publication Authors may self-archive the author manuscript	Works must be deposited immediately upon publication. Authors may self-archive the author manuscript	Authors or publishers must deposit the author manuscript or the electronic copy of the stand-alone publication (For FWF funded stand-alone publications: FWF deposits the work on behalf of the author immediately upon publication)	Works must be deposited immediately upon publication, in case the work is not published in gold OA A post review version is recommended, a pre-review version accepted
Policy URL	https://wellcome.ac.uk/funding/managing-grant/complying-our-open-access-policy	https://erc.europa.eu/managing-your-project/open-access	fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/	nwo.nl/beleid/open+science

“ Science Europe (SE) members unanimously adopted a set of “Common Principles on the Transition to Open Access to Research Publications” in April 2013. ”

3.3.1 European OA policy

Science Europe

Science Europe (SE) members unanimously adopted a set of “Common Principles on the Transition to Open Access to Research Publications”⁶ in April 2013. It was the first time that the major European public research funding and performing organisations had collectively endorsed and committed to actionable principles that will contribute to a swift transition to open access.

Although these principles did not refer to monographs, SE does include books in its definition of open access in the SE Roadmap as “unrestricted, online access to scholarly research publications (including books, monographs and non-traditional research materials) for reading and productive reuse, not impeded by any financial, organisational, legal or technical barriers”. An overview of OA policies of member organisations is provided in a survey report about OA policies from member organisations.⁷

Horizon2020 OA mandate

As an example of an OA policy that applies to books as well as articles, and that includes green and gold, we can look at the EU’s OA policy in its current funding programme, Horizon 2020 (H2020). (While articles are mandated, monographs are not.)

The H2020 OA requirements are based on “a balanced support to both green and gold”⁸:

- ▶ All beneficiaries of H2020 grants are required to deposit and ensure OA (note that this means that beneficiaries must deposit their publication, even if it will be made gold OA)
- ▶ **What:** A machine-readable copy of the published version, or a final peer-reviewed paper accepted for publication (post-print version)

- ▶ **Where:** In a repository for scientific publications of their choice
- ▶ **When:** As soon as possible and at the latest on publication
- ▶ **When OA:** Immediately for gold OA, or within six months (twelve months for publications in HSS) for green OA

The H2020 OA policy does not specify under what licence a publication should be made available, but encourages authors to retain their copyright and grant open licences to publishers, such as Creative Commons licences.

Under the H2020 programme, beneficiaries can pay APC’s for gold OA (in both OA and hybrid journals) out of the H2020 grant (which limits APC payments to the grant agreement period).

The H2020 OA policy does not specify monographs, although the policy could be interpreted to include monographs. However, the guidelines explain that “grant beneficiaries are also strongly encouraged to provide open access to other types of scientific publications” and includes monographs in the list of examples⁹.

Footnotes

- 6 http://scienceeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/SE_POA_Pos_Statement_WEB_FINAL_20150617.pdf
- 7 http://scienceeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/SE_OpenAccess_SurveyReport.pdf
- 8 <https://openaire.eu/open-access-in-horizon-2020>
- 9 http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

This has enabled the ERC, which funds its research programmes through H2020 and is therefore bound by the H2020 OA requirements, to explicitly include monographs in its guidelines.¹⁰ ERC also recommends the OAPEN Library as the repository for monographs, book chapters and other long-text publications.

3.3.2 Country OA policies

Formal mandating of open access has only been adopted in a few of the countries, though there are some incentives already appearing to do so in others. For example, although not mandated yet, HEFCE has said that it will give extra points to OA books as early as the 2020/21 REF.

In comparing OA policies we found significant variations due to the differing political structures of the eight countries. In contrast to the centralised political system of France, Germany has a decentralised governance structure, through 16 states with their own state governments and ministries of science and culture. Although there are many programmes to promote OA, most policies are based on recommendations rather than mandates, and apart from the national OA strategy, monographs aren't included in OA policies.

The general explanation for monographs not being included in policies is the global focus on journal publishing and the perception that monographs are more complex to deal with than journals. Some also point to a lack of demand from authors.

Our study shows that although the main OA policies do not include monographs, conversations about OA and monographs are surfacing and are expected to be accelerating over the next few years. The ongoing OA monograph publishing experiments show a desire to test different models in order to harvest necessary experience and empirical evidence about the viability of different funding models.

The Netherlands, strong advocates of OA, were perhaps the first to negotiate national offsetting agreements, to allow Dutch researchers to publish their articles OA as part of new big deals with the main scientific publishers. The government used its EU Presidency in the first half of 2016 to raise the issue of open science and push it up on the political agenda. This was followed early in 2017 by a National Plan for Open Science, which contains the ambition to achieve 100% OA for all scientific publications by 2020. The plan involves the Dutch universities, their libraries, the Royal Academy of Arts and Sciences, and the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), among other academic institutions. NWO already mandates OA for publications resulting from research grants, and this mandate includes books. NWO was also one of the founders of OAPEN Foundation, after the close of the EU project in 2011, and supported OAPEN-NL, the first national pilot exploring OA book publishing.

Within Austria, the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) has perhaps played an even stronger role in leading the transition to OA. FWF was an early signatory of the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities and the first public research funding agency to mandate OA to scholarly publications, in 2008. The mandate includes monographs, requiring deposit in a repository, but FWF also funds gold OA monographs through its Stand alone Publication Programme since 2009.

“ Our study shows that although the main OA policies do not include monographs, conversations about OA and monographs are surfacing and are expected to be accelerating over the next few years. ”

FWF also has an active role in promoting OA in Austria and elsewhere, by adopting the Principles on the Transition to Open Access to Research Publication initiated by Science Europe, establishing the Open Access Network Austria (OANA), becoming a member of Europe PubMedCentral, joining OAPEN, etc. In addition, OANA published 16 recommendations for the transition towards open access in Austria with the goal of converting Austria's entire scholarly publication output to open access by 2025.

The UK approach is thought to be more in line with the Anglo-Saxon tradition of both politics and business cultures. The commercial sector responded relatively quickly to the mandates for OA journal articles that followed on from the Finch Report published in 2012¹¹ although even then RCUK and HEFCE took slightly different positions on their preferences for implementation (one gold, the other green). HEFCE and other public funding bodies have been more cautious with monographs subsequent to the findings of the Crossick Report (published January 2015). However, a committee under the auspices of Universities UK (UUK) has been established to work through all outstanding issues with stakeholders, with a view to mandating OA within the next few years and in time for the REF after next (i.e. 2026/17).

In contrast to the cautious approach adopted by HEFCE, Wellcome was one of the first research funders to mandate OA for monographs.

They have since produced a guide for OA monograph publishers¹² and work with OAPEN to increase the reach of these monographs and edited volumes in inter-disciplinary areas around medical research.

All three Nordic countries in our study have set OA as a firm goal although the push for OA varies among the countries. For the past few years in Finland and recently also in Denmark we have seen initiatives that embrace the larger notion of open science as an umbrella that

includes OA. So far, these initiatives have given little or no attention to monographs, albeit there are examples of OA monograph publishing experiments. Denmark has explicitly left monographs out of the national OA strategy and in the policies of the public research funding bodies. This is also the case in Norway although the new Norwegian OA guidelines (currently in the making) recommend that monographs should be considered part of new policies. In Finland the national and research organisation's OA mandates – which almost all universities in Finland now have – are explicit about OA for journal articles but not for monographs. However, the Ministry of Education and Culture has emphasised that open science should be all inclusive and thus encompass monographs. This suggests that the landscape may very well soon change in Finland.

“ Wellcome was one of the first research funders to mandate OA for monographs. ”

Footnotes

10 https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_Open_Access_Guidelines-revised_feb_2016.pdf

11 psa.ac.uk/sites/default/files/page-files/Finch%20Working%20Group%20Report%2C%20Oct%202013.pdf

12 https://wellcome.ac.uk/sites/default/files/Guide-to-open-access-monograph-publishing-for-researchers-final_0.pdf

The table below summarises our findings on mandates for monographs:

Table 5: Our findings on mandates for monographs

Country	Mandates and encouragement
Austria	FWF has a mandate and a specific programme to fund stand-alone publications
Denmark	No mandate, no encouragement
Finland	No mandate, but general encouragement to include all scholarly outputs, including monographs
France	No mandate, encouragement from some quarters
Germany	No mandate, no encouragement
Netherlands	NWO has a mandate
Norway	No mandate, no encouragement but new guidelines that are in the making recommend considering the inclusion of monographs in future policies
UK	Encourages OA and considering mandates for the next but one REF (expected mid 2020s)

As summarised in the study **Towards a Competitive and Sustainable Open Access Publishing Market in Europe**, the European Council's call for immediate open access as the default by 2020 represents a "step change in the policy environment. EC policy on open access has evolved steadily in recent years, with an open access pilot under the Framework Programme 7 (the EC's Research & Innovation programme for the period 2007-2013), and the inclusion of open access as a general principle of the successor programme, Horizon 2020". Despite the EC's clear recommendation in 2012 that member states define clear open access policies countries have not moved forward at a uniform pace. Monographs were rarely included in policy statements, encouragements, or mandates, though this is beginning to change.

3.3.3 How publishers are adapting to OA policies

Despite initial caution, most UK publishers of monographs are now enabling OA where possible. Publishers are happy to comply with funders if the policy is made known to them.

Self-archiving

In general, OA book publishers will comply with gold OA policies from funders and institutions. This is not the case for green OA. It appears self archiving policies from publishers for books are largely restricted to book chapters. We did find a few examples of publishers with self archiving policies for entire monographs in the Netherlands: Amsterdam University Press (outlined below), and Boom Publishers. The example of Boom is interesting because they operate at a crossroads of professional and academic subjects (law, criminology, administrative science), and apparently they don't think allowing self archiving will harm sales.

Some publishers make books OA after a certain period, which is a form of green OA (for example, Leiden University Press makes its books OA after one year). Some publishers offer delayed OA at lower charges (for example, Amsterdam University Press will make a book OA after one year for 50% of the original BPC). And Goldsmiths Press announced it will "combine green open access with a fair and varied pricing model in order to avoid the exploitation of authors as well as readers, creators as well as users". A few examples of self archiving policies (not including specific conditions):

“ In general, OA book publishers will comply with gold OA policies from funders and institutions. This is not the case for green OA. ”

“ Almost all the major international publishers have an OA book offering, and the number of OA books is growing rapidly ”

- ▶ **Amsterdam University Press:** allows authors to share their accepted manuscript (after peer review, before final layout) in institutional repositories, on their personal website and in other outlets, without any embargo
- ▶ **Brill:** allows immediate self-archiving of monographs in a closed repository, only accessible for students and staff
- ▶ **Cambridge University Press:** authors may self-archive one chapter of the published book, and contributors of edited collections may self-archive their own chapter, in both cases six months after publication
- ▶ **De Gruyter:** allows self-archiving of articles published in multi-authored works (journals, anthologies, edited volumes and databases) 12 months after publication, in the published version of their article in the publisher’s layout, (but only on their personal website or in the repository of their institution)
- ▶ **Oxford University Press:** allows authors to post one chapter (or 10%) of their book (or co-authored book or edited volume) after 12 months (for science and medical), or 24 months (for academic, trade and reference)
- ▶ **Palgrave MacMillan:** allows self-archiving of one chapter per work, in the author’s own, pre-copy-edited version, 36 months after publication
- ▶ **Springer:** no public self-archiving policy at present

Embargo periods

As can be seen in the examples above, embargo periods for book chapters tend to vary considerably.

The principle behind the position is that the publisher should be able to recover its investment before the content goes OA. In a fluid market with dwindling sales of monographs, whether closed or open, judging when this might be is difficult since, although most monograph sales occur within the first twelve months, many have continued longer-term sales. Indeed well established presses rely on backlist sales to a considerable degree. In addition, embargo periods for articles in the humanities tend to be longer than for articles in the physical sciences, which have a very short life cycle.

In the case of monographs one should also look at sales and usage patterns. A monograph in the humanities may not be deemed significant until many years after its appearance – so arriving at a standard average “half-life” of either sales or usage is fraught with difficulties.

DOAB

The Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) lists 200 publishers. These publishers have all published peer reviewed books under an open licence. This is not an exhaustive list as DOAB doesn’t list institutional publishers, textbook publishers, and non-academic publishers (publishers that don’t conduct peer review). But it is clear that OA book publishers are still a small minority among all academic book publishers. However, almost all the major international publishers have an OA book offering, and the number of OA books is growing rapidly (listed books in DOAB have shown a growth rate of over 50% in the past three years). Most large publishers offer an OA option if BPCs are found.

3.4 Funding streams to support OA monographs

Funding schemes for books are lagging behind schemes for articles and their availability to fund the publishing process is somewhat ad hoc across the countries we've surveyed.

A page maintained by Nature lists 54 organisations worldwide that fund BPCs, of which 16 are research funders.¹³ Most of these organisations are from Europe (34, including 13 funders).

In the table below, we list the funding bodies and institutions that support BPCs from the eight countries of our study (in total 19, including nine research funders):

Table 6: Funding bodies and institutions that support BPCs

Country	Funders	Institutions
Austria	Austrian Science Fund	Academy of Fine Arts, Vienna
	Commission for Development Research at the OeAD-GmbH	University of Salzburg
Denmark		University of Southern Denmark
Finland	Academy of Finland Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	University of Helsinki Aalto University University of Turku University of Tampere University of Lapland
Germany	DFG	University of Konstanz
Netherlands	Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research. (Incentive fund for OA to end on 1 January 2018)	Utrecht University Delft University of Technology
Norway		Oslo and Akershus University College of Applied Sciences University of Agder University of Bergen University of Oslo University of Tromsø / Arctic University of Norway
France		OA for books generally part of subsidy to institution and emanates from departmental budgets
UK	Department for International Development Research Councils UK, including AHRC, BBSRC, ESRC, EPSRC, MRC, NERC, STFC Wellcome Wellcome Library	UCL Press and smaller institutional OA publishing initiatives of which at time of writing there were around a dozen and more planned ¹⁴

Funding of BPCs or some equivalent is easier to find where there has been a tradition of state support for monograph publishing (though tightening of budgets is a feature everywhere). Nevertheless, there is a recognition everywhere that extra funds for a transition period will be necessary and there is concern over how BPCs will be determined, where the money will come from and how this new model might impact on quality; there are issues around funding the “supply side” and what impact this has on university budgets if not adjusted for higher output institutions. Nevertheless we believe that the task is one of rechanneling existing funds rather than finding new money.

Another open question is whether OA funded publishing will alter the prestige rankings of publishers. Can library and academic-led publishing make enough of an impact to break the habits of old? Or is this an issue that is intractably embedded in the promotion system as is most clearly evident in America? Our research suggests that this varies from country to country and between subjects, and that it will also be dependent on the outlook of key individuals.

Very few publishers can survive financially only on monograph publishing. To date few monographs are supported through research grants because many monographs, especially in the humanities, do not arise out of funded research projects. In the social sciences the picture is somewhat different. Large-scale quantitatively based projects are usually funded either through one of the national research bodies or from EU projects such as Horizon 2020. And funding for monograph OA publishing has been made retrospectively available for the EU’s Framework 7 programme.

“Very few publishers can survive financially only on monograph publishing.”

Footnotes

- 13 <http://nature.com/openresearch/funding/funding-for-open-access-books>
 - 14 The Jisc report *Changing Publishing Ecologies: A Landscape Study of New University Presses and Academic-led Publishing* by Graham Stone and Janneke Adema provides more detail. <http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6666>
-

Below are the main bodies that fund OA and/or funding approaches that fund OA books in each country:

Table 7: The main bodies that fund OA and/or funding approaches that fund OA books

Country	Main funding bodies
Austria	FWF OA mandate includes monographs and FWF funds gold OA through its stand-alone publications programme. The funding scheme is modular, based on publisher services. It requires CC BY.
Denmark	Green national strategy and policy that does not include funding for OA publishing. One university library (University of Southern Denmark) has set up a publication fund that is also open for monograph applications. Some of the private funds that generally support book publishing also support OA
Finland	The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies is beginning to fund more OA. A group of university libraries (the Aleksandria consortium) has funded an OA publishing experiment. The Aleksandria Consortium is a library consortium initiated by the Finnish Literature Society and the Helsinki University Library. Its goal is to provide a funding mechanism for books written in Finnish
France	Generally university departments
Germany	DFG recommends OA for all types of publications, and there are funding opportunities for monographs that allow OA publication. DFG also funded two infrastructure projects resulting in new OA presses (Heidelberg University Publishing and Language Science Press) MPG has agreements to fund OA monographs with some publishers (De Gruyter, Nomos)
Netherlands	NWO OA mandate includes monographs. NWO funds up to 6000 euro for gold OA for publications resulting from funded research. (Incentive fund for OA to end on 1 January 2018). The university libraries of Utrecht and Delft have publication funds that can be used for BPCs
Norway	Publication funds dedicated to support OA are widespread across the country (almost 20 funds exist). Other funds can be applied for to subsidise OA publishing
UK	HEFCE is preparing to fund OA monographs; AHRC has funding opportunities for monographs that can be used for OA, Wellcome funds BPC's for books and chapter resulting from funded research

3.4.1 Crowd-funding and membership schemes

Crowd-funding and membership schemes cut across national borders. Support for these have been primarily from libraries though consolidating funding from a greater variety of sources, such as research institutes, is just beginning with Language Science Press (LSP). LSP, based in Germany, has just commissioned Knowledge Unlatched (KU) to raise funds from three sources, libraries, research institutions and individual scholars.

Knowledge Unlatched is the largest crowd-funding initiative devoted to books. To date 449 books have been supported by 414 libraries from 25 countries – of which the eight countries in the study account for 32%. With the last round KU has become the largest single source of funding for OA monographs. KU will be expanding its sales efforts to other countries and so the proportion from countries in this study is expected to decrease, though, of course, KU hopes to gather more support from the smaller countries and France. KU invites applications from any qualifying publisher based on quality (through peer review) whether commercial, non-commercial, new or old. A review committee made up of 40 librarians from 12 countries (selected by the larger network of KU libraries) then selects which titles to put forward for library support. KU is also a source of support for OA/digital first publishers such as UCL Press, Ubiquity, Ottawa and others, all of which need to find outside sources of funding. KU aims to raise the full BPC costs for several hundreds of books each year, charging a small administration fee to cover its own costs.

“ Crowd-funding and membership schemes cut across national borders. ”

Membership is a variation of the crowd-sourcing type of model. Open Book Publishers has established a library membership scheme although it relies on a mixed funding model whereby the library membership plays only a small role in its programme support. This is similar, though not identical, to the University of California Press Luminos project.

3.5 Business models for publishing OA monographs

We begin this section with a discussion on how to build a typology that represents the spectrum of publishing models available for OA monographs.

3.5.1 Typology of publishers

The typology used for this study is partly derived from a report by London Economics' Economic analysis of business models for open-access monographs, which was undertaken as part of the monographs and open access report for HEFCE (the Crossick Report). This typology is presented in the literature review in 9.2.1 (publisher typology).

We build our publishing typology on the basis of where the funding for publishing costs comes from and this is discussed below.

Our typology makes a distinction between for profit and non-profit publishers, and between traditional university presses, new university presses, and academic led presses:

- ▶ Traditional publishers (for profit publishers)
- ▶ University presses, institutional publishers and learned society publishers (non-profit often, but not always, connected to university or research institution)
- ▶ New university presses (mostly OA, including library-driven presses and funded mostly by the parent institution)
- ▶ Academic-led presses (independent presses, either for profit or non-profit)

“ We build our publishing typology on the basis of where the funding for publishing costs comes from ”

“ Publishers can adopt a number of OA business models simultaneously for different books. ”

Table 8: Examples of publishers by type in each of the countries

Country	Traditional publishers	University presses	New university presses	Academic-led presses
Austria	Böhlau Holzberger	Austrian Academy of Sciences Press		
Denmark	Multivers Academic	Aalborg UP		
Finland	Gaudeamus	Finnish Literature Society	Lapland UP, Tampere UP	
France	PUF	University of Rennes Press		
Germany	Springer De Gruyter		German UP's	Language Science Press
Netherlands	Brill	Amsterdam UP Leiden UP		
Norway	Scandinavian UP, Cappelen Damm Academic			BOAP
UK	Bloomsbury Academic	OUP, CUP, Manchester UP	UCL Press University of Westminster Press University of Huddersfield Press	OBP, OHP

3.5.2 Publisher approaches to OA business models

OA business models can be adopted by any publisher and make up anything from a very tiny percentage of their output to all of their monograph programme. Publishers can adopt a number of OA business models simultaneously for different books. We show in our country studies how variations on the business models are determined by the context of the traditional monograph businesses from which they are emerging. However, at the operating level there are real challenges around workflows in all parts of the publishing company everywhere.

With the exception of some publishers in Norway and Finland, almost all publishers will publish a printed edition alongside the OA edition. The printed edition can be a higher priced hardback for the institutional market, intended to help recover the total costs of the publication, or provided as a service to readers as a low cost paperback print on demand (PoD) edition that also provides a margin. The distinction between short print runs and PoD carries implications for the supply chain

although end users hardly notice the difference.

OpenEdition has pioneered the freemium model whereby readers can have access to an OA version (usually HTML, but sometimes EPUB or PDF) and from the same platform arrange purchases of other formats. For publishers this provides additional revenue as well as income for OpenEdition for reinvestment in its development.

Some publishers will publish both hardback and paperback editions, and some will also sell other format e-books next to the OA edition. Providing a range of versions for sale in print and/or e-book editions next to a free online edition is often part of a freemium model and these sales contribute to covering the costs of the overall monograph project.

Traditional publishers usually charge a BPC, which can be paid by the author generally from a research grant, or an institutional publication fund. BPCs

can also be paid through an arrangement with a research department or institution, or by libraries in a collaborative funding model (such as Knowledge Unlatched or the Luminos model of the University of California Press).

Publishers employ different methods to calculate the level of BPCs. Commercial publishers who engage in OA book publishing tend to cover the total costs of publication through the BPC. This is, for instance, the case at Scandinavian University Press and Cappelen Damm Academic in Norway. Brill will calculate anticipated revenue from sales and only charge a higher BPC when a book is published under a CC BY licence – where it is assumed that there will be no further sales of other formats. Many university presses will calculate the BPC based on the costs to produce the digital file. At present there is not enough understanding of how costs of an OA books might differ to closed books and how that might influence the pricing of a BPC. (See the appendix (Chapter 10) for more on how BPCs are calculated).

With the exception of the UK, university presses are in some way supported through their institution, but this arrangement predates open access models. This is what separates traditional university presses from new university presses (NUP), in that the NUPs begin their lives with open access as part of their remit. We include the German university presses in this category of NUP, even though most of them were established around the turn of the century. Some NUPs don't charge authors belonging to their institution for the publication of OA books, while others make use of institutional publication funds from elsewhere.

Independent academic-led presses tend to be mission-oriented OA publishers. These publishers may not receive direct institutional support and will seek out grant support, and some (like Open Book Publishers) will only charge BPCs if there are funds available to

the author, or waive them under certain conditions. For a discussion on the available literature, see 9.1.1 (OA business models).

Our approach has been to focus on where the money is coming from to pay for OA publishing. But first we describe what we include in the OA costs.

Publishing monographs costs money and this varies tremendously. The study by Nancy Maron et al, **The Costs of Publishing Monographs**¹⁵ shows the huge variation amongst US university presses, but does not cover costs from the large commercial presses who either do not spend as much time on monograph crafting and/or can avail themselves to economies of scale to bring costs down. Nor does it reflect on the profit requirements of public companies – a factor that can then bring costs up, negating economy of scale savings.

Arriving at the cost of getting to first digital copy of a monograph is only one part of the BPC calculation. Many publishers are now experiencing (or expecting to experience) reduced print and other digital format sales independently of the impact of OA and so are looking for income substitution, including potential revenue and possibly subsidies from their BPCs.

“ Arriving at the cost of getting to first digital copy of a monograph is only one part of the BPC calculation. ”

Footnotes

15 <http://sr.ithaka.org/publications/the-costs-of-publishing-monographs/>

The obvious extension of this process is that there will be negligible income from anything other than BPCs to not only cover fixed costs but those contributions that were expected from sales of other formats minus the print and bind costs (See Chapter 10 on publishing costs).

Below we look at some of the sources of payment for getting to first digital file, or fixed costs of a monograph, or BPC that may or may not include partial or full overhead recovery. As we said above, the source of funding is the backbone of our typology. We then provide examples of some of the companies employing these business models in each of the countries later in the study.

1. BPC paid for by research funder

In this case it is generally up to the author to arrange for the money to be found and transferred – often through the offices of the author’s institutional department or library, who will be responsible for the payment. The price is generally set by the publisher.

2. BPC paid for by author’s institution

This is similar to the above, but the source of funds will come from the institution’s budget to support publication. Administration of the funds can be carried out centrally by the library or by one or more departments.

3. Crowd-funding

Crowd-funding is an increasingly popular way of raising funds for all sorts of projects. KU employs this model by crowd-funding from the academic library community to cover BPCs. The Berlin based, but internationally active, KU crowd-funds from over 400 libraries in 25 countries.

4. Membership funding

A few publishers such as Open Book Publishers in the UK and the University of California Press Luminos project in America are experimenting with library membership models that account for financing parts of BPCs (see related model 5 below). These are usually applied in conjunction with raising funds from other sources. Lever Press is adopting a “platinum OA model” with members of over 40 US liberal arts college libraries paying a membership fee to cover all publishing costs.

5. Mixed model funding

In fact many BPCs are assembled by funds from multiple sources. UC Press/Luminos <http://luminosoa.org> has set up parameters around this, but in most cases authors and publishers look wherever they can for opportunities to cover BPC costs. Language Science Press is employing Knowledge Unlatched to launch its mixed model funding approach whereby support is being sought from specialist research institutions, libraries and individuals. knowledgeunlatched.org/2017/03/ku-launches-language-science-press/.

6. Embedded institutional support

This can be seen as a special case of mixed model funding. Most library-based presses make use of in kind contribution of resources and staff, which is then combined with low BPCs to cover out of pocket production costs. Tampere University Press recently shifted from a non-OA publishing model to an OA-only publishing model and it is an example of this business model. Their BPC is very low (around 1800 euros) because the BPC does not cover salaries and overheads, which are part of the library budget. Other examples are to be found in German university presses, Leiden University Press and Stockholm University Press.

7. Institutional funding

This applies to some of the newer, pure OA publishers that are set up as an integral part of the institution, to disseminate knowledge as part of their core mission. In this model, OA publishing is seen as a cost centre and any revenue coming in from sales is part of the overall budget. One of the earliest examples is Athabasca University Press. Some German university presses are funded through this model, as is Perspectiva.net, the publishing arm of the Max Weber Stiftung. In some ways French

university presses are moving towards this direction as they gradually move not only backlist but also frontlist titles onto OpenEdition and are expected, as before, to return any surplus income to the parent institution. Newer library-based presses in the UK, such as UCL Press, also follow this model.

In the table below we provide some examples in each country of publishers that employ the various sources of payment:

Table 9: Examples of payment sources used by publishers in various countries

Country	Model 1: BPC paid for by research funder	Model 2: BPC paid for by author's institution	Model 3: Crowd funding	Model 4: Membership funding	Model 5: Mixed model funding	Model 6: Embedded institutional support	Model 7: Institutional funding
AUT	Böhlau Holzhausen	Vienna UP Ac. of Sciences Press					
DEN	Multivers Academic					Aalborg UP	
FIN	Gaudeamus	Lapland UP	Finnish Literature Society			Tampere UP	
FR							PU de Rennes
DE	De Gruyter, Springer		De Gruyter, transcript Verlag			LSP	Perspectiva
NL	Brill, Amsterdam UP	Amsterdam UP, Brill, Leiden UP			Leiden UP		
NOR	Scandinavian UP, Cappelen Damm Academic	Scandinavian UP, Cappelen Damm Academic					BOAP
UK	CUP, OUP, SpringerNature, Routledge		13 UK presses participate in KU	OBP	OBP	University of Huddersfield Press	UCL Press

“ One determinant of BPCs is, in some instances, the company’s expectation of future sales and the element they will need to cover in full lost contributions to overheads. ”

3.5.3 Book processing charges (BPCs)

There is no source of information that provides definitive data on BPC charges. Averages by publisher are hard to come by unless they are advertised on their websites. The level varies with publisher expectations of additional sales of other formats, especially print.

However, we know that the range is significant - from as little as €500 at KIT for simple posting - to Brill €8,500, deGruyter €10,000, Bloomsbury up to £8,500, Routledge £10,000. These options tend to be on CC BY-NC licences with various pre-press services included. Examples of BPCs with a CC BY licence are: Brill €18,500 and Palgrave £11,000. Variations are likely to reflect different levels of input and services and also take into account staff cost structure and local wage levels. This is also dealt with in the Ithaka report.

There is scant evidence to say that OA has definitively harmed all print sales, and there is little understanding of what kinds of works actually see increased sales from OA exposure. Brill has monitored OA impact on print sales over a period of six years and found that in 2016 59% had no impact, 13% had a positive impact and 28% had a negative impact. While there were widely fluctuating results over the six years with no impact being as high as 70% in 2014, positive impact of 27% in 2011 and 20% negative impact in 2014, there is no reliable way of predicting the future.

One determinant of BPCs is, in some instances, the company’s expectation of future sales and the element they will need to cover in full lost contributions to overheads. These may be included in BPC charges – though there is no hard and fast rule on the exact figure.

There is a general belief that, as discoverability and accessibility increase, print sales will fall and therefore BPC charges will rise as they move from covering not only “getting to first digital file” but also serve as income substitutes – recompensing publishers completely for lost sales. On the other hand in some cases extra

visibility has increased sales of print versions bought by individuals beyond expectations. We look at why BPC costs vary in greater detail in Chapter 10, and the available literature is discussed in 9.2 (Costs of OA publications and the question of pricing).

3.5.4 Licensing

Licensing of monographs poses different challenges than articles. While the underlying principle of the benefits of CC BY holds true for all content, many monograph publishers choose at least a CC BY-NC licence so as to be able to commercialise other formats such as print. However, there is no clear pattern in the choices publishers make. Palgrave MacMillan was the first commercial publisher to introduce CC BY in 2013, in combination with a PoD service that was presented as a service to readers rather than a means to recoup investment, while the non-profit publisher Open Book Publishers (OBP) also provides CC BY, although OBP aims to sell various other editions to reduce the need for author side payments.

Brill on the other hand makes a sharp distinction between the BPC for publications with a CC BY-NC licence, for which it charges a flat fee of €8,500, and the BPC for publications with the less restrictive CC BY, for which the charge is €18,500. And publishers in Norway recommend CC BY as they don’t expect revenues from sales of print copies or other digital formats. So, although there is a relation between the business model applied by the publisher and the restrictions that are placed on the content through licensing, there are many different approaches to licensing of OA books.

Looking at the OA books in DOAB, the various licences with NC add up to almost 60% of titles, but when we look at books added in 2016, the NC licences are declining in favour of CC BY, which was the largest single category in 2016.

Cumulatively, CC BY-NC-ND is still the largest category in DOAB (34%). ND is usually at the request of the author, who generally retains the copyright of the content, entering into an exclusive arrangement with a publisher by way of contract (and governed by contract law and not intellectual property law). Authors of monographs tend to be more protective of their work than authors of articles, which is understandable considering the time it takes to write a monograph, but also for practical reasons: books may be translated, and ND licences allow authors to control the translation of their work.

“Cumulatively, CC BY-NC-ND is still the largest category in DOAB (34%).”

Figure 4: Distribution of licences per country (from DOAB)

“ Ensuring the high quality of OA monographs is key to all stakeholders. ”

Funders are on the whole in favour of CC BY licences for books, but most funders understand the specific considerations for book publishers and for authors in the humanities and don't require CC BY as they do for articles. For instance, Wellcome requires monographs to be “licensed in ways which support their reuse. Although the Creative Commons Attribution licence (CC BY) is strongly preferred, we will accept non-commercial and/or no-derivatives licences (i.e. CC BY NC, or CC BY NC ND)”.¹⁶ The only funder requiring CC BY for the books it funds is FWF.¹⁷

However, whatever the policy of the funder, publishers are generally willing to comply with funder requirements regarding the type of licence. For a discussion on the available literature, see 9.2.2 (Publishers: OA policies and licences).

3.6 Other aspects of making the transition to OA

The incorporation of OA into the publishing practices of a large number of very varied publishers is no doubt one of the biggest challenges for OA monographs. Some issues are identical to those arising out of the expansion of scholarly communications globally, while others have to do with the migration to digital publishing. Here we discuss a few of these issues as they pertain to OA monographs.

3.6.1 Quality assurance

Ensuring the high quality of OA monographs is key to all stakeholders. Quality is generally being linked to peer review. Maintaining rigorous peer review seems to be the single most important issue in the debate. However, there are other aspects to quality assurance that are just as important. Below we discuss peer review, editorial process and their impact on BPC charges and the significance for transparency. The available literature is reviewed in chapter 9.3.1 (Quality assurance and peer review).

Peer review

The primary motive to pay special attention to peer review in the transition to the new OA publishing model is that the model is often based on author side payment, or pay to publish, which is often considered to be synonymous with “vanity publishing”. Peer review is to ensure that the decision to publish is made independent of any payments. A secondary motive is to counter the perception of free e-books as being of lesser quality. This is why platforms like OAPEN and DOAB make peer review a requirement of membership, and publish the description of peer review processes by publishers on their platform. DOAB is developing a more formal certification service for publishers, which includes a classification of the type of peer review that a publisher uses.

Another approach to promote trust in publishing operations is to introduce peer review or quality labels by a group of publishers, or a national institution. Examples of these labels are Kriterium in Sweden¹⁸, and the label for peer-reviewed scholarly publications in Finland.¹⁹ Another motive for this approach is to promote professional academic standards, and this is typically important in countries where academic book publishing is very small or under pressure. Avoiding vanity publishing accusations and ensuring standards of peer review both played a key role in establishing the certification service introduced by FWF.²⁰

Editorial process

Peer review is a key element of quality assurance, but other elements are just as important. **The long argument**, which is how the monograph is often described in the humanities and social sciences, is typically developed in close collaboration between the author and the publisher/editor including lengthy deliberations, corrections and questions from referees. This profound development of manuscripts is at the core of a scholarly publisher's operations. However, editorial development is not something all publishers

do in the same way, and it is not undertaken for all types of books.

It is no secret that some book publishers ask for a “camera ready” copy (these days actually a print ready digital file), which effectively means they will not do anything with the final manuscript and authors are supposed to do this work themselves. This is common for the treatment of theses in some publishing houses. Some publishers will do a light form of copy-editing and rounds of proof reading, and some will concern themselves solely with typesetting the final manuscript. It is clear that the way manuscripts are handled is another key element in the level of quality assurance, defining for the quality of the publisher, and also much asked for by authors.

BPC levels

Editorial quality is intimately connected to the total cost of publishing as we have seen in the Nancy Maron et al. Ithaka study. This begins with the work of the acquisitions (or commissioning) editor. Acquisition costs are rarely fully reflected in the BPC levels thus making comparisons between publishers really difficult. We see large differences in the ways in which the publishers treat manuscripts and accordingly we also see large differences in the costs associated with OA monograph publishing. National differences in the general wage level adds to the complexity when comparing BPC levels since most of the costs associated with publishing are staff hours. In the UK, for instance, the average wage level is only two thirds of what it is in Denmark²¹ – and in Norway it is even higher. (See appendices, Part 4, Chapter 10 for more on why BPC costs vary).

Transparency

Quality assurance requires transparency at all levels: in the way peer review is carried out, in the services that are being offered, and in how these are then reflected in the costs of OA publications. Transparency in both the service levels and cost structures of publishers is pivotal

for funders to evaluate BPC levels, but no less important for authors who are looking to understand the publishing process when searching for an appropriate publisher.

“Quality assurance requires transparency at all levels: in the way peer review is carried out, in the services that are being offered, and in how these are then reflected in the costs of OA publications.”

Footnotes

- 16 <https://wellcome.ac.uk/funding/managing-grant/complying-our-open-access-policy>
 - 17 https://fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/files/Dokumente/Antragstellung/Selbstaendige_Publikationen/pub_application-guidelines.pdf
 - 18 <http://kriterium.se/site/en-welcome/>
 - 19 <https://tsv.fi/en/services/label-for-peer-reviewed-scholarly-publications>
 - 20 https://fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/files/Dokumente/Antragstellung/Selbstaendige_Publikationen/pub_certified-publisher-checklist.pdf
 - 21 http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=lc_lci_lev&lang=en
-

3.6.2 Infrastructure for OA book publishing

OA book publishing can only develop in conjunction with infrastructure that supports the publishing process. OA book publishing relies on three types of infrastructure:

- ▶ The existing and evolving digital infrastructure for e-publishing, such as digital identifiers (DOI, ORCID) and standardised usage data (COUNTER)
- ▶ Infrastructure developed to support open access in general, such as institutional repositories and the SHERPA services (SHERPA/RoMEO)
- ▶ Infrastructure that is developed specifically to support OA book publishing, such as publishing software (Open Monograph Press) and discovery services (DOAB)

Below we look specifically at the latter category, and list examples of infrastructures that operate on an international level. A review of the available literature is presented in 9.3.3 (OA infrastructure).

Publishing software for OA books

The one example of a software solution is Open Monograph Press (OMP), managed by the Public Knowledge Project (which is also responsible for Open Journal System). OMP is an open source solution, which is being used and adapted by publishers such as Heidelberg University Publishing and Language Science Press. University repositories also sometimes offer publishing software solutions. A new entrant in the commercial space is Glasstree, owned by Lulu.

Publishing platforms

There are many examples of publishing platforms, but within the countries of this study we can mention Ubiquity Press and OpenEdition Books, both operating internationally with various publishers. Ubiquity Press

is UK based and works mostly with new university presses. They provide a range of modular services to their partners. OpenEdition Books is part of OpenEdition, based in France, and works with most of the French university presses and some publishers in other countries. OpenEdition provides a range of services, including a freemium business model.

Intermediaries

Intermediaries can have different functions, such as hosting and dissemination, aggregation, deposit, preservation, discovery, crowd funding, and sales representation.

OpenEdition should also be mentioned in this category. OpenEdition works with publishers and libraries to provide its freemium service.

OAPEN Library is a dedicated platform for OA books, based in the Netherlands, acting as aggregator and providing services in the area of hosting and dissemination, preservation, and deposit. OAPEN works with publishers and libraries, and provides a deposit service to funders that mandate OA books, such as Wellcome, FWF and ERC. OAPEN also works with Ubiquity Press and Knowledge Unlatched.

DOAB is a discovery service for OA books, listing peer reviewed books that are published under an open licence, and making the metadata freely available to libraries and their service providers. DOAB is a service of OAPEN Foundation.

Knowledge Unlatched is now a German-based broker or crowd funding organisation, working with publishers and libraries to fund OA monographs.

In addition, both Ingenta and JSTOR have started to provide services for OA books. Project MUSE is developing its platform to include OA books.

“ There is much work to be done to improve the discoverability and visibility of OA monographs. ”

Looking at the current infrastructure for OA book publishing, there are a few points to consider:

- ▶ The infrastructure is partly developed and partly still under construction. The separate pieces of infrastructure need to link together to make the system as a whole work effectively. We will address specific issues in the sections about discoverability and visibility and about supply chain hurdles, below.
- ▶ The infrastructure needs to be developed and maintained in a sustainable manner. This implies that there should be coordination at some level, and that the system needs business and governance models to ensure continued operation. Knowledge Exchange has explored the issues in this area²², and further work is being done.
- ▶ The infrastructure is the result of the collective endeavour of many different players, both public and private, in different countries, who are also working together to develop a new, overarching, distributed infrastructure in an initiative called OPERAS, which we will describe below.

OPERAS

An innovative pan-European project aiming to connect and build on existing infrastructure is Open Access in the European Research Area through Scholarly communication (OPERAS). OPERAS is a distributed research infrastructure (RI) project for open scholarly communication. The main goal is to introduce the principle of open science and ensure effective dissemination and global access to research results in the humanities and social sciences.²³ OPERAS currently consists of 24 partners in ten European countries, among them the infrastructure providers mentioned above: OpenEdition, Ubiquity Press, OAPEN, Knowledge Unlatched. Other partners include the Greek National Documentation Centre (EKT), Max Weber Foundation (MWS), and UCL Press.

OPERAS is currently conducting an H2020 project, HIRMEOS, dedicated to OA books.²⁴ HIRMEOS is a project to develop a layer of added services on top of existing platforms for OA books. The platforms are OpenEdition Books, Ubiquity Press, OAPEN, EKT and Göttingen University Press. Other partners in the project are KU Research and Open Book Publishers. The services to be implemented are:

- ▶ Identifiers: DOI (Crossref), ORCID, named entities (NERD)
- ▶ Entity recognition, with NERD
- ▶ Certification of publications, with DOAB
- ▶ Open annotation, with Hypothesis
- ▶ Usage metrics

3.6.3 Discoverability and visibility

There is much work to be done to improve the discoverability and visibility of OA monographs. For this to be achieved there needs to be cooperation between all parties in the supply chain: publishers, libraries and intermediaries.

One level of work has to do with ensuring that OA monographs have the right metadata. This includes conventional metadata (bibliographic information, ISBNs, classification codes, keywords, abstracts), metadata for digital content (DOI, ORCID, and increasingly chapter level metadata), and specific metadata for OA content (licence information, funder information, links to OA editions, and, in the case of green OA, embargo information, version information and link to the version of record).

Footnotes

²² <http://knowledge-exchange.info/event/oa-dependencies>

²³ <http://operas.hypotheses.org>

²⁴ <http://operas.hypotheses.org/hirmeo>

“A thorn in the side of the supply chain has been the lack of transparency of both paid for and OA editions of books.”

Good practice guidelines for OA book metadata have been developed by Editeur for ONIX²⁵, by Crossref²⁶, and by OAPEN/Jisc.²⁷

The purpose of metadata is to support dissemination, and this is the next level of work. Metadata needs to be converted into specific formats to be made available for intermediaries. ONIX is the preferred format for the book industry, and MARC21 is the preferred format for the library community. Metadata feeds need to be made available for various intermediary channels, such as library discovery systems (OCLC WorldCat, ExLibris Primo, EBSCO Discovery), OA channels (BASE, OAI-PMH harvesting), and web resources (Europeana, DPLA).

Finally, the OA books need to be made available on hosting and dissemination platforms (OAPEN, JSTOR, Ingenta Open). Most publishers are also contributing the metadata of their OA titles to DOAB. DOAB has the largest collection of OA monographs, currently over 8,800 books from 220 publishers, but doesn't host OA books, only metadata. The metadata of books is uploaded by the publishers that are listed in DOAB, and made available to libraries for their catalogues and to intermediaries for their discovery services. DOAB has the potential to help solve the issues around discovery. A recent study concluded that "...aggregation of OA metadata by a trusted entity such as DOAB plays a significant role in facilitating OA book discoverability in library catalogues"²⁸, provided publishers upload the metadata to DOAB and libraries opt to display OA monograph records. See chapter 9.3.2 for a discussion of available literature.

3.6.4 Supply chain hurdles

A thorn in the side of the supply chain has been the lack of transparency of both paid for and OA editions of books. The GOBI Library Solutions service (formerly YBP and now a part of EBSCO <https://gobi.ebsco.com/>) provides a good price comparison service and is

widely used around the world. However, it does not, as yet, show OA availability. But in late 2016 Ingenta Connect launched Ingenta Open followed swiftly by JSTOR with JSTOR Open. Both have agreed not to charge for any e-books that may be listed behind its paywall in subject collections and available as OA. Instead, they will signpost users to the OA version. MUSE is working on developing a similar option that will have more functionality (funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation) by the time it launches (scheduled for 2019). DOAB is an invaluable service but still takes up too much library staff time in checking what is OA.

In general, the sales and distribution of e-books is still relatively undeveloped with general terms of trade not yet settled. In the meantime libraries are rightly concerned that they may inadvertently be paying for monographs that appear in paid for collections even though they are available in OA editions. Indeed there are still issues over duplication of closed books in the various large collections of the main aggregators as publishers make the books available through multiple sales channels and automated de-duping is not yet fully effective.

There are a very few wealthy libraries that are willing to support both open and closed editions - for instance a combination of participating in Knowledge Unlatched, while at the same time buying everything that is on offer through, for example, MUSE - even with the knowledge that there is some duplication. This is because of the extra functionality on the current MUSE platform. Such competitive advantages change over time as platforms routinely upgrade their features. Nevertheless, this sort of duplication is expected to decline once discoverability, interoperability and standardisation of platforms develop further.

Another issue is that authors expect their books to be distributed through both traditional and new channels. Rupert Gatti of Open Book Publishers compared

both retail and library distribution channels, and then compared book sales to downloads. Total sales are dwarfed by downloads which are 300 times as many on average per book. Servicing the retail channels requires maintaining relationships with half a dozen different vendors – all with different requirements, and resulting in a very small number of sales. For the library market OBP has contractual relationships to supply books with 14 vendors all of which have different sales models and service requirements.

Gatti's experience mirrors those of other OA publishers that find servicing the traditional channels hugely cumbersome and expensive given the legacy discount structures.

These issues need resolving quickly and streamlining before there can be greater stability in how publishers approach OA and how their business models will evolve.

3.6.5 Technical formats and platforms

The current debate focuses on which e-format best serves the reader. PDF is preferred because of its familiarity, however, EPUB and HTML both have their advocates because of additional functionality possibilities.

From our survey and further examination of publisher websites, we found the following formats employed for OA monographs. We also know from the OAPEN Library that the vast majority of the books hosted there are in the currently popular PDF format, though a growing number of publishers are now producing EPUB, or considering doing so in the future.

There is an increasing demand for chapter level discoverability for both paid for and OA content. Some publishers have already implemented this into their workflow, and have allocated DOIs to chapters; others have not. Platform service providers such as

JSTOR assign their own DOIs to books and chapters even though the original idea behind DOIs was that there should be only one DOI for each piece of content (whether article, book or chapter).

As we discussed in the section on discoverability, there is an urgent need to use common and globally applied standards to avoid confusion in the metadata.

Other desired improvements include annotation functionalities for books, and OA monographs are also expected to provide such facilities.

“ Another issue is that authors expect their books to be distributed through both traditional and new channels. ”

Footnotes

- 25 Open Access monographs in ONIX for Books <http://editeur.org/files/ONIX%203/20140722%20Open%20Access%20e-books%20in%20ONIX%20FAQ.pdf>
 - 26 crossref.org/06members/best_practices_for_books.html
 - 27 <https://oapen.org/content/sites/default/files/u6/WP3%20Metadata%20for%20OA%20monographs%20-%2020160607.pdf>
 - 28 Aaron McCollough, 'Does It Make a Sound: Are Open Access Monographs Discoverable in Library Catalogs?' in: *Libraries and the Academy*, Vol. 17, No.1 (2017)
-

“ Now much more emphasis is put on social media marketing. ”

3.6.6 New marketing methods

In the past publishers had a marketing budget that was expressed as a percentage of sales and/or other income. This was spent on tried and tested methods of printing and mailing out catalogues and leaflets, attending conferences and sending out review copies. Now much more emphasis is put on social media marketing. This requires people with different skills, and traditional presses are having to duplicate efforts while they still provide legacy services and set up work processes for the new. This can be seen in all countries.

At the same time, in the case of larger presses, acquisitions editors are still expected to attend academic conferences where they compete for authors, attend sessions to sharpen up their knowledge of new trends in their subject areas and generally engage in friendly industrial espionage.

Monograph publishers must thus find resources to support efforts to market the press, both to the communities of authors that presses rely on to provide high quality content and to global communities of readers, both within and beyond academia. Effective marketing of OA services to authors, and OA content to communities of readers, is demanding investments of time, skill and capital.

3.6.7 Library and institutional engagement with OA

Libraries have a crucial role to play in supporting open access and monographs. They are in some countries the “front of house” face that deals with authors who are looking to understand what is required of them and where to look for the OA funding. While some libraries allocate a small amount of their own funds to support OA, more act as conduits and administrators of other funders. (Section 9.2.4 of the literature review provides further sources of information).

The various roles played by libraries are summarised below:

- ▶ **Managing funds for third parties**
In much the same way as managing APCs libraries can (and already do) support authors and funders by being the conduit for funds, whether from other departments, central institutional funds or elsewhere
- ▶ **Re-allocating acquisitions funds**
In adopting the principles behind the OA2020 initiative launched by the Max Planck Society 2015, libraries can re-allocate their acquisition funds to support OA initiatives. These can be through a number of crowd sourcing and membership initiatives that are providing cost-effective alternatives.
- ▶ **Establishing new publishing operations**
In many countries new publishing operations have been springing up under the umbrella of the library. We discuss elsewhere the energy these new library led initiatives have brought to the publishing landscape and encourage a better understanding of their costs and their potential
- ▶ **Promoting awareness and information about open access**
Many libraries already play a crucial role in promoting awareness of open access opportunities to their scholars. This is through both online tools and face-to-face interactions with authors. They are also potential champions for OA within the university administration
- ▶ **Playing a role in ensuring compliance with funder requirements**
Libraries are often tasked with ensuring that both authors and their publishers are aware of the funder requirements. This is a labour intensive undertaking, especially as funder requirements differ substantially (see compliance section below)

In each of the countries we surveyed the university system is ostensibly primarily public, though the level of public support for research and tuition varies. Nevertheless, most are considered to be a cost centre of the institution. This is in contrast with the US where the private university system constitutes a larger market share and libraries are often funded by a mixture of sources including endowments and philanthropic contributions.

The extent to which individual librarians take an interest in OA is influenced by the policy positions of organisations such as LIBER at the European level and national bodies such as Couperin, SCONUL, SURF, DEFF, DFG, Jisc and CSC.

Librarians have given thought to how they might contribute to supporting their institution's goal of attracting more research funding and one way has been to support OA as a way of increasing potential impact of those authors from the parent institution. Libraries play an important role in facilitating discoverability of OA monographs through identifying and cataloguing OA content. Much depends on how they use aggregation services. As Ronald Snijder concluded in his study, "Open libraries pave the way for intermediaries to offer new discovery and aggregation services. These services play an important role by amplifying the impact of open access licensing in the case of scholarly books".²⁹

“ Libraries play an important role in facilitating discoverability of OA monographs through identifying and cataloguing OA content. ”

Library services to OA vary from institution to institution but we can summarise the range of services provided by the larger libraries, and to some extent the smaller ones as well, though perhaps more selectively due to resource constraints:

- ▶ Administering APCs and where available BPCs
- ▶ Ensuring that offset deals with publishers are fair
- ▶ Working with university administrators to find ways of supporting otherwise unfunded APCs and, in a few instances, unfunded BPCs
- ▶ Providing information and support to scholars around open access
- ▶ Starting up and running new publishing services
- ▶ Working internally and with intermediaries to improve visibility of open access content

Libraries are undertaking new roles and we have seen the establishment of OA teams carrying out entirely new functions. The way in which they become embedded and related to other departments is still work in progress but it is generally acknowledged as necessary to handle the new roles that libraries are embarking on as part of the transition to OA.

Footnotes

29 JLSC Vov3m Issue 1 2015 – ep. 1187

3.6.8 Compliance – funder requirements and publisher/author compliance

We sought to look at the extent to which all in the OA chain comply with the requirements of the funders. Compliance is, however, in its infancy. Funders are still developing their requirements for books and the relevant guidelines are then passed through to authors, publishers and intermediary administrators (such as libraries).

Specific funders such as Wellcome monitor compliance of their grantees and publication of articles; the compliance rate has increased since 2012 when Wellcome announced that failure to comply with its policy could result in final grant payments being withheld and non-compliant publications being discounted when applying for further funding. Wellcome has a policy and fund for OA books and publishes guidelines and requirements on its website.³⁰

Given the time lag between research and publishing a book there is not yet enough information on whether authors with Wellcome research grants have complied with OA policies.

Libraries, authors and publishers would like to see more streamlining and standardisation of requirements. One large library told us that they posted 39 different sets of funder requirements on their website and these had to be monitored regularly as they often changed.

3.6.9 Author attitudes to OA monographs

While the study brief did not explicitly explore author attitudes to OA monographs it is clear that attitudes vary greatly both between countries, between disciplines and even among researchers within a discipline, depending on their career stage and other factors.

We have seen examples of available funds for OA monographs that have found very little uptake from authors which points to a lack of awareness or understanding among researchers. On the other hand there appears to be an increasing appetite amongst both younger and older academics for OA, the former because they see no logic behind scholarship being closed and the latter because they have already attained their career goals and looking for broader dissemination. For the increasingly mobile academic increased usage figures are a definite plus. However, some studies (such as the Book of the Future report from the UK) provide evidence that in some subjects there is still limited understanding of the benefits or appetite for OA. Other studies, in particular OAPEN-UK, are discussed in the literature review, chapter 9.2.5 (authors and readers).

OA brings benefits of impact that short runs of closed editions cannot. Libraries often encourage academics to publish where there are OA options, to use their institutional repositories and provide training and advocacy for OA, thus raising awareness of OA. Case studies can be found on the Knowledge Unlatched website of individual authors and the journey their books took after publishing in OA.

The most vocal voices against OA have been those who see the challenges such as third party rights permissions as insurmountable obstacles. As we see from this and other studies a more nuanced approach to OA can alleviate some of the concerns.

“ OA brings benefits of impact that short runs of closed editions cannot. ”

In many countries it is the library that provides information about OA options, benefits and risks to authors. However, there is no comparative information about the extent to which this is provided in any of the countries studied here and it would lend itself to further investigation.

We agree with what most other studies of OA have concluded that the incentive structures for authors need to change before there is widespread conviction that the OA model benefits them.

Nonetheless, the benefits of OA are now beginning to be seen. Palgrave Macmillan (now part of SpringerNature) claims that its OA publications are downloaded 12 times more than closed ones.³¹

Knowledge Unlatched provides individual institutional download statistics by both IP addresses and geo-locational statistics and this is especially helpful where local communities do not go into the library via its IP address for access.

3.6.10 Usage data and other metrics

Tracking and consolidating usage data for monographs is still in its infancy. Some of the larger companies have systems in place for doing so (such as Springer). OAPEN provides COUNTER compliant usage data and Knowledge Unlatched provides usage data to publishers for books in the programme as well as supporting libraries.

Tracking use of OA material is challenging. Most usage does not go through university library IP addresses. Nevertheless we've seen (above) that Palgrave claims its OA books are downloaded 12 times more than the average closed monographs and KU's geo-locational statistics around the universities that support it are finding that usage in the university town can be several times higher than reported via the IP addresses. More information on mobile usage will come from a new partnership between KU and Biblioboard.

Traditional citation metrics are being challenged with new ones that measure downloads, blog citations and much more. Altmetrics (www.altmetric.com) is one of the first in this area. Institutions and funders are asking for more information with Kudos (www.growkudos.com) as an example of a company bringing data about authors and their publications together - all of which is changing the workflow for everyone, whether open or closed.

For a further discussion on assessing the impact of open access books, Ronald Snijder has prepared a more thorough review and this is included as Chapter 11 (the literature review also presents available literature in chapter 9.3.4).

“Tracking and consolidating usage data for monographs is still in its infancy.”

Footnotes

30 wellcome.ac.uk/funding/managing-grant/complying-our-open-access-policy

31 <http://ingenta.com/blog-article/yes-open-earth/> (cited 23 January 2017)

4. Recommendations to Knowledge Exchange

Below are a number of areas where Knowledge Exchange might make a positive contribution, either on its own, or in partnership with others. We believe that there are several areas that will benefit from KE involvement.

Recommendations in the area of policies and funding:

- ▶ Facilitate exchange of ideas and encourage awareness for policy makers across countries on the issues around encouragement and mandating of OA for monographs
- ▶ Facilitate the streamlining of OA requirements and compliance in the way BPCs are being administered. Support campaigns for compliance
- ▶ Convene with other stakeholders to pave the way towards OA monographs, to explore coordinated approaches by funders and libraries, following the OA2020 initiative for articles
- ▶ Establish a permanent Open Access Book Watch (OABW), to monitor progress, to identify good practice, examples, and business cases, to provide a tool for funders and policy makers
- ▶ Address misconceptions around OA books by supporting and showcasing success stories
- ▶ Look beyond OA to related aspects of monograph publishing: service levels, quality assurance, transparency, pricing, the incentive structure for authors
- ▶ Contribute to modelling lower cost base monographs without sacrificing quality
- ▶ Support research projects to improve dissemination and discovery of OA monographs as well as understanding better the barriers that exist in today's supply chain
- ▶ Support the development of a toolkit on OA books (this could be partly based on existing work, looking at various aspects of OA book publishing: metadata; information that publishers should make available; licensing; self-archiving; funder requirements; peer review; metrics; dissemination and discovery)
- ▶ Identify key infrastructures looking at what is still needed and already available for any transition to OA in line with earlier KE work

Recommendations in the area of publishing:

- ▶ Provide a forum for publishers to exchange ideas and experiences on how to accomplish successful OA monograph publishing

Part two

2

5. Introduction to country studies

Part two is the backbone of our report as input to the analyses presented in Part one. It is the result of careful examination of the eight countries that we have researched for this report: Austria, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and United Kingdom.

In autumn 2016 when we were assigned the task of composing a landscape study for OA monographs France was not yet part of the Knowledge Exchange (KE). However, we decided that it would indeed make sense to include France, as it was to become part of KE. Couperin kindly agreed to contribute to our study. Looking at the European landscape we also thought that when it comes to OA and monographs Austria in particular stands out with FWF as a driving force in Europe. We therefore also invited Austria to be included. FWF kindly accepted our invitation and has also contributed directly to the study. Finally, we also wanted to include Norway and CRIStin of Norway kindly agreed to contribute to the study. Although we would have liked to include all of Europe this was clearly way beyond the scope of the KE call. However, we still think that among the eight countries that we researched we find most – if not all – the issues to be found in the rest of Europe. We would, though, recommend widening the scope and including more countries should the wish or need for further studies arise.

As described in Chapter 2: Brief and methodology, we investigated the countries partly through a web based questionnaire, partly through interviews. We administered three web-based questionnaires, one for each of the stakeholder groups that we focused on: publishers, funders and libraries. The questionnaires and organisations we spoke to can all be found in the appendices section.

5.1 Input from questionnaires

The response rate was unfortunately quite low for our web-based questionnaires. We sent the questionnaire to 167 publishers. 42 responded which is a response rate of 25%. The funder questionnaire was sent to 58 funders of which 15 responded making the response rate 26%. Finally the library questionnaire was sent to 95 libraries directly from us and to the 424 member libraries of LIBER by LIBER on our behalf. With a total of 59 responses the response rate was only 11%. However, we decided to have our questionnaire translated into French and Couperin then kindly re-sent it to the French libraries. This gave another 49 responses, which in effect made the actual response rate for libraries rise to 21%. In any case, the response rates for all three stakeholder groups were very low despite sending chasers and even personal letters to certain institutions. We think there are several reasons for this under the heading “one size doesn’t fit all” and hence many felt the questionnaire was not relevant to them. This is true at country level where we see big country-specific differences but also at stakeholder level. Publishers, for example, are not a homogeneous group. As we described in our publisher typology section there are very explicit differences within this stakeholder group. This is reflected in the responses we have received where some have answered in great detail while others have only answered very few questions. This pattern is also true for the funders’ and libraries’ questionnaires. Combined with the low response rates the use of the questionnaires did not warrant the effort of producing and distributing them.

In contrast, performing in-depth interviews with a number of key actors (73) proved very fruitful. A careful selection of interviewees was undertaken for each country ensuring a balanced representation among the key stakeholders. For each stakeholder group (publishers, funders and libraries) a set of thoroughly worked out questions was developed (20-25 questions).

5.2 Input from interviews

The interviews were conducted by the principal investigators as 45-60 min interviews either in person or by Skype/telephone.

Unlike the questionnaires the set of questions for the interviews could be adjusted fitting the concrete context and type of publisher/funder/library. Performing interviews in this way and with such a large number of people was very time consuming but proved hugely successful. The field of OA monographs is still in its early evolution and therefore in-depth conversations were needed to understand the different developments among the different stakeholders. In this way the puzzle came together for each of the countries, paving the way for further analysis at an aggregated level.

The eight country studies are all structured identically. First we present a few key observations in short form followed by an introduction to the country and the current publishing landscape. The central part of the country studies are the parts “OA policy landscape” and “OA publishing landscape”. Each country study then concludes with a look into the future of OA monograph publishing in the particular country.

As one can imagine, the differing levels of activity within the eight countries means that some countries demand more space than others. It simply takes more words to describe ongoing activities in a big country like the United Kingdom than in a small country like Denmark where far less is happening when it comes to OA monographs, both politically and within publishing.

Each country has its own anecdotes and notable initiatives. We have extracted these from the country studies and compiled them in Chapter 7 (Part three): Notable initiatives. Finally, as a special case, the three Nordic countries have been attached with a common introduction looking at the whole Nordic region.

We are dutifully aware that our country studies most certainly are incomplete. OA monograph publishing is in a transitional phase and developing fast and new initiatives pop up at high speed. We have looked at the landscape at a certain moment but time has already moved far ahead adding new initiatives to this landscape. Also, we could not possibly claim to have turned each and every stone in any country. However, we feel that we have encountered the most important aspects of OA monographs in each country fueling us sufficiently to making our landscape analysis, our gap analysis and our recommendations.

6. Country studies

6.1 Country study: Austria

Key observations:

- ▶ FWF has a leading role in OA policy development, coordinating a national approach and collaboration with stakeholders in Austria
- ▶ FWF offers a good example of an OA mandate including monographs, combined with a book-specific funding scheme that looks beyond OA, to promote transparency and quality of OA services
- ▶ The publishing industry is not strong, with mostly smaller, regional presses, mostly German language output, dependent on subsidies, mostly unable to establish peer review practices

6.1.1 Introduction

Within Austria, the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) plays a leading role in the transition to OA. FWF was an early signatory of the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities and the first public research-funding agency to mandate OA for scholarly publications, in 2008. The mandate includes monographs, requiring deposit in a repository, but FWF also funds gold OA monographs through its Stand-alone Publication Programme since 2009. In addition, FWF has an active role in promoting OA in Austria and elsewhere, by adopting the Principles on the Transition to Open Access to Research Publication initiated by Science Europe, establishing the Open Access Network Austria (OANA), becoming a member of Europe PubMedCentral, OAPEN, and supporting DOAJ. FWF expects to achieve open access to a large part of funded publications by 2020. In addition, OANA published 16 recommendations for the transition towards open access in Austria with the goal of converting Austria's entire scholarly publication output to open access by 2025.

6.1.2 Monograph publishing landscape in Austria

In many ways, the Austrian monograph publishing landscape is comparable to the German landscape. As in Germany, book publishers tend to be dependent on print subsidies. Publishers feel the pressure of decreasing sales and the need for investing in digital workflows. Monograph output is predominantly in the German language. There is a tendency to publish more in English, but it is hard for book publishers to develop the capacity for English editing, translation, international distribution, etc. Austrian scientific publishers also struggle to maintain a high level of quality, and few publishers have a peer review process for their monograph output.

6.1.3 OA policy landscape in Austria

The OA landscape in Austria has developed considerably since 2012, when the Open Access Network Austria (OANA) was established, initiated by FWF and Universities Austria (uniko).

OANA consists of around 50 research institutions from Austria (including universities). They meet once a year, but can act outside meetings and there are various working groups resulting in new initiatives and policy statements.

The OANA initiative that comes closest to a national OA policy is **Recommendations for the Transition to Open Access in Austria**.³² It was supported by the Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy (BMWFV) and contains 16 coordinated measures, with the aim to achieve open access to Austria's publicly funded scholarly publication output by 2025. The set of measures favours gold OA. We include a selection of the recommendations here, but a complete list of the recommendations is provided as an appendix (Chapter 12):

- ▶ The commitment to establish OA policies at OANA member level
- ▶ Measures to create cost transparency
- ▶ The effort to reorganise publishing contracts in order to achieve OA for Austrian authors
- ▶ A commitment to establish OA publication funds
- ▶ The transformation of publicly funded publication venues to OA
- ▶ The participation in international initiatives that promote non-commercial publication models and infrastructures

Another OANA working group is a group of young researchers and science administrators who, in 2016, published a vision for scholarly communication in the 21st century, called **The Vienna Principles**.³³ The twelve principles include open access, reusability and reproducibility of research results. Other principles are discoverability, transparency, quality assurance and innovation.

However the push for open access started with FWF, as one of the early signatories of the Berlin Declaration in October 2003, followed by an open access recommendation in 2004, and by an open access mandate in 2008. Since 2015 the following rule for final reports of FWF funded projects is in place: “In accordance with the guidelines of the FWF concerning open access, with the submission of the final report, all peer reviewed publications that resulted from the project have to be made openly accessible.³⁴ Exceptions to this rule, e.g. if a publication organ explicitly does not permit open access, must be proven. For projects funded after 1 January 2016, no exceptions are possible”.

FWF transformed its programme “Stand-Alone Publications” to OA in 2009. The programme is separate from the OA mandate for FWF-funded projects, which includes funding of APC’s. The programme for stand-alone publications can be used to comply with the OA mandate for FWF-funded projects, but it is actually wider, aimed at all Austrian researchers, in order to make these publications available to a broader public. The programme includes conventional publication forms (e.g. monographs, edited collections), but is also available for support of new formats such as apps, wiki-based publications, annotated scientific databases, web-based publications enriched with various media (e.g. audio, video, animation), etc. The programme is described in detail in the next section.

Academic libraries in Austria are actively engaged in the transition to OA. Most of the universities now have institutional repositories, and many have publication funds, in line with the **Recommendations for the Transition to Open Access in Austria**. The Austrian Academic Library Consortium (KEMö cooperation) has established OA agreements with a number of publishers: Royal Society of Chemistry; Emerald; Sage; SCOAP3; Springer Compact. Apart from offsetting agreements, there are also agreements with some pure gold OA publishers, such as BMC/Springer Open. In addition, there are collaborative agreements of smaller groups of stakeholders to support other OA initiatives, such as DOAJ, Knowledge Unlatched, and OAPEN.

Footnotes

32 https://zenodo.org/record/51799/files/OANA_OA-Recommendations_23-05-2016_ENG.pdf

33 <http://viennaprinciples.org/>

34 <http://fwf.ac.at/en/researchfunding/open-access-policy>

FWF coordinated a countrywide consortium agreement with OAPEN, for Austrian researchers to deposit their OA books in the OAPEN library. The consortium partners are Holzhausen, Böhlau, the University of Vienna and FWF.

6.1.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in Austria

It is fair to say open access monograph publishing in Austria started with FWF in 2009. Commercial publishers developed their OA offering in response to FWF, and most of their publications are funded through FWF. As FWF was already paying for book publications, the transition to BPCs was relatively straightforward from a financial point of view.

FWF was the first funder to mandate OA for books, and among funders, FWF has without doubt the most elaborate and specific funding programme for books. All the books it funds are OA, all books are subject to a strict quality assurance system and all are made accessible centrally, through the FWF e-book library, hosted by the University of Vienna, and through OAPEN. Since 2015, books are required to be made available under a CC BY licence.

The approach of FWF has been to look beyond open access to the needs of scholarly communication in Austria. The programme is not restricted to publications resulting from FWF funded research, but open to all Austrian researchers. And the aim of FWF is to improve not only access to, and reach of, monographs but also the quality and transparency of Austrian academic book publishing. This is why FWF pays for a range of services from publishers rather than just for OA, and it explains the modular approach of the book programme. The programme “Stand-Alone Publication” makes a distinction between “innovative publication formats” and “conventional publication formats” (such as monographs and anthologies).

The programme for conventional publications has four modules:

Module 1: Basis

A lump sum grant of up to €10,000 for production costs, for simultaneous open access publication and for editing in the mother tongue of the author.

Module 2: Foreign-language editing or translation

Instead of editing in the mother tongue FWF provides a lump sum grant of up to €4,000 for foreign language editing or translation.

Module 3: Surcharges

A lump sum grant of up to €4,000 for additional costs due to, e.g. a higher number of pages or an increase in expenses for layout and image rights. Surcharges have to be proven by a cost calculation.

Module 4: Discretionary funding

FWF provides a lump sum grant of up to €8,000 in cases where the peer review process reveals that an English language version would increase the visibility of the publication significantly. This amount is approved as an additional grant by the FWF, and the entire funding amount is subject to the requirement that the publication is then translated into English and at least a digital version of the English language version is made available for open access archiving. This module cannot be applied for but may be granted by the FWF board.

The programme for innovative publication formats consists of a lump sum grant of up to €50,000 as a subsidy for production costs including foreign language editing or translation and open access publication.

Comparing the level of subsidies that FWF paid for books before OA was mandated with the overall level of subsidies through the modular programme, shows that subsidies at book level have remained more or less the

same. In 2004, FWF paid on average €13,000 per book, and in the last two years the average was €14,362. The difference is that before the current programme was introduced the subsidy was for printing costs, whereas the new programme subsidises gold OA, copy editing, and/or translations.

FWF is trying to get publishers to professionalise and adopt international standards. To this end it has set up a system to certify publishers. Certification is based on a range of requirements which the publisher must fulfil and document on its website, such as:

- ▶ All scholarly books should be subjected to an international peer review process, ensuring independent and external peer review prior to publication
- ▶ Books must be copy edited by established experts (including foreign language editing)
- ▶ Costs of book publishing must be completely transparent

In addition, there are criteria for each publication, including DOIs, metadata standards, digital preservation and CC BY licensing.

The certification system has a number of benefits:

- ▶ The system raises awareness of the quality of the Austrian book publishers and promotes professional and international standards
- ▶ The application process for OA funding is simpler and faster when monographs are to be published by certified publishers

- ▶ FWF does not need to organise a separate review of the publication and, instead, the publisher submits two non-anonymised reviews with the application
- ▶ The production process of the OA monograph isn't held up by an external review process

However, it should be mentioned that currently, the only Austrian publishers to be certified are Holzhausen and the Austrian Academy of Sciences Press. Böhlau, which publishes most of the FWF funded monographs, tried to organise its own review process for a few years, but decided to discontinue this service. International publishers certified by FWF are Palgrave Macmillan, Springer, and De Gruyter. FWF organises peer review of all the other books it funds through the application system for stand-alone publications. This is possible because FWF funds a relatively small number of books: around 60-65 annually.

FWF's OA funding programme has resulted in almost 350 OA monographs to date. Most, around 60%, concern the humanities and 90% are in German. Almost 50 books are in English, or English and German. The majority of the books, almost 60%, were published by Böhlau. Other prominent publishers are the Austrian Academy of Sciences Press (with 37 books), Studien Verlag (14) and Holzhausen (12).

Böhlau Verlag

Böhlau operates in Germany and Austria, with offices in Vienna, Cologne, and Weimar. The Vienna office is the largest academic book publisher in Austria, with an estimated output of around 150 books annually. Böhlau was acquired by Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht in January 2017. Böhlau has published the majority of FWF funded OA books (approx. 200), but also publishes OA monographs supported by funding sources in Germany and Switzerland.

Holzhausen

Holzhausen publishes 20 to 30 monographs annually (next to cultural and educational lists). Around 20% of these books are OA, and funded by FWF. The OA offering is developed around the FWF programme for stand-alone publications. Holzhausen is an FWF certified publisher and manages a peer review system.

Austrian Academy of Sciences Press

The Austrian Academy of Sciences Press is the institutional press of the academy and follows the institution's OA policy. However, the press is self-sustaining and cannot publish its books in open access without additional funding. But researchers can choose how to make their publication publicly available and the academy recommends that researchers self-archive their publication as soon as possible, through the institution's repository (EPUB.OEAW) or a subject repository of their choice. The press publishes around 50 books annually, 70%-80% of them in the German language. About 10%-15% of titles are published in OA, but the press also makes about 25% of backlist titles available in OA. There are currently around 170 OA books in total, of which 37 were funded by FWF.

Vienna University Press

VU Press is outsourced as an imprint to Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht (since 2007). They have published approx. 100 books; only about five are OA to date. Their OA offering has a relatively low BPC (under €10,000, which is considered to be well below the fees of commercial publishers, although BPCs remain high compared to charges in most other countries). A special committee with representatives of the University of Vienna decides about publication.

6.1.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in Austria

FWF has set up a thoughtful funding programme, to enable the transition to open access for books and to promote Austrian scholarship even beyond its own research funding programmes. This approach is successful and has ensured a steady output of high quality OA monographs. But Austrian academic book publishers seem to face increasing economic pressures and very few are able to achieve and maintain a high quality level of book publishing. So far, as elsewhere, a relatively small part of monograph output is made OA. We may assume that more money will become available through institutional OA publication funds, but a significant transition to OA is complicated in a situation where book publishers are already struggling to survive.

FWF would like to see the implementation of international standards for quality control and services (e.g. peer review, copy editing, technical OA standards) for monographs, including an authoritative database like DOAJ for all book publishers that comply with these standards. DOAB may provide a solution, as it is developing a certification system within the H2020 HIRMEOS project.³⁵

6.2 Country study: Germany

Key observations:

- ▶ OA policy landscape is varied due to decentralised governance structure. Strong OA policies in certain research institutes, but on the whole, monographs are not included in OA policies
- ▶ Publishing industry is quite large in terms of number of book publishers and output, but there are huge differences in size, quality, and service levels. Publishers generally depend on author side payments and on publishing paid-for PhD dissertations

- ▶ Germany has quite a few active OA book publishers, including university presses, large commercial publishers and new entrants

6.2.1 Introduction

The German scientific landscape is quite varied, due to its decentralised governance structure, through 16 states with their own state governments and ministries of science and culture, along with several state-funded research organisations for top-level research (Max Planck Society, Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft, Leibniz-Gemeinschaft, etc) and local/regional academies. This has led to a wide variety of OA policies. Although there are many programmes to promote OA, most policies are based on recommendations rather than mandates, and on the whole monographs are not included in OA policies. However, this doesn't mean that there is nothing going on around OA books. The German university presses can be seen as the first wave of new university presses, library driven and dedicated to OA. Springer and De Gruyter were among the first commercial publishers to start publishing OA monographs, and in fact De Gruyter is the largest publisher of OA books in the humanities. In addition, there are a number of interesting new initiatives, such as the academic-led Language Science Press, which was set up with support from the German Research Foundation (DFG).

6.2.2 Monograph publishing landscape in Germany

The first thing to note about the German academic book publishing landscape is its size. Despite ongoing concentration, with larger publishers (such as De Gruyter, C.H. Beck and recently Dutch publisher Brill) acquiring smaller ones, there are a large number of small and medium sized, independent book publishers. The German trade association (Boersenverein) lists 600 academic publishers. The vast majority are small (92% have less than 12 FTE staff). This means there are around 50 medium to large publishers.

A factor to consider when looking at the German academic book publishing market is the requirement to publish a PhD thesis. There are around 30,000 PhD students each year finishing their theses successfully³⁶, and although an increasing number of dissertations are published in electronic form or as a collection of journal articles, a significant part of the academic book output published in Germany is original PhD theses published as monographs.

Some of the main book publishers are Springer, De Gruyter, Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, Campus Verlag, and C.H.Beck.

Springer, now SpringerNature, is a true multinational company, one of the four largest scientific publishers in the world, and with the acquisition of BioMed Central also the largest open access publisher. They are by far the largest academic book publisher in Germany, although De Gruyter is the largest book publisher in the humanities. Springer is unique in the way it has transitioned completely to e-publishing, with books being offered primarily as e-books through the SpringerLink platform, and with print as an option through the MyCopy service.

De Gruyter has acquired many publishers, particularly in recent years, among them Birkhäuser, Mouton, Oldenburg, Saur, and Versita. De Gruyter is now one of the largest humanities book publishers in the world, with around 1300 monographs annually, 400 FTE and branches in Vienna, Warsaw, Boston, Beijing.

Footnotes

35 <http://hirmeos.eu>

36 <https://destatis.de/DE/ZahlenFakten/GesellschaftStaat/BildungForschungKultur/Hochschulen/Tabellen/PromotionenBundeslaender.html>

The dominant model of academic book publishing continues to be conventional and print based, although vendors, libraries and publishers are increasingly moving into the direction of e-books, often through PDA platforms. However, several publishers have not managed the transition to e-publishing, let alone OA publishing. Many are highly specialised and publish exclusively or mainly in the German language.

The segment of English language books seems to be slowly growing, but mostly in data-driven disciplines, less in disciplines that have a tradition of sustained argumentation. For instance Language Science Press, a pure OA publisher in linguistics, publishes in English. And large publishers with an international list publish more in English. But until recently, even De Gruyter published more books in German than English.

German remains the preferred language for monographs in the humanities for many reasons. It is hard for publishers to develop a strong list of English language monographs and to set up an international distribution network, it requires years of training for authors to be able to write monographs in a foreign language and translation is very expensive. And finally, the German language area with approximately 90 million inhabitants and a highly developed academic system is a significant market, and in addition, German monographs do sell abroad, for instance in specific areas of history and philosophy, and of course German studies.

Although the German language area is quite large, including Austria, part of Switzerland and Northern Italy, publishing in German clearly limits the sales potential of books and sales have declined in Germany. Publishers cannot sustain their business through sales alone, and the practice of charging authors a fee (“druckkostenzuschuss”) for publishing their manuscript is widespread in many humanities disciplines, even

among the large presses. A typical fee will be between €2,000 and €4,000 for a monograph in the humanities, but there are examples of much higher charges.

Authors need to look for funds to cover these charges, and there are many, mostly private funders that can provide support to publish monographs. These funders come in all sizes, and some, like VW-Stiftung, are very large.

Even so, dwindling sales threaten the sustainability of smaller, specialised monograph publishers. The CEO of a small publishing house in humanities and social sciences says: “Monographs are subsidised. These are commissioned productions. We are not looking for these books, but the scientists come and say we want to have that printed. And we do that when it is economically viable. Sales have now fallen dramatically. We produce monographs of which we do not sell a hundred copies.” Many of these smaller publishers have shied away from investing in new technologies or workflows to make the transition to e-publishing. This has contributed to a concentration phase in the book publishing landscape, leading to a more dominant position of the larger book publishers such as De Gruyter.

Digitisation has been a driver for new initiatives at universities. Many of the university presses were established around the turn of the century, usually by university libraries, and motivated by the new opportunities for digital information and online distribution on the one hand, and economic challenges such as increasing subscription costs on the other. There are 28 university presses in Germany (and 5 German language university presses in other countries).³⁷ Twenty-five of these presses are members of the German Working Group of University Presses (AG Universitätsverlage).³⁸ The largest is KIT Scientific Publishing, followed by TU Berlin and Göttingen University Press.

A typical characteristic of the German academic book publishing market is the tradition of publishers to work with “Herausgeber”, usually distinguished scholars acting as series editors on behalf of publishers. These scholars lend their prestige to the book series, which in turn attracts authors to submit their work. The herausgeber then has a role as gatekeeper, with the responsibility for selection and peer review. This system leads to a different dynamic around quality assurance and prestige than in the UK and USA. There is an on going discussion about the disadvantages that this system may have for innovative research and for younger scholars and first time authors to find a publisher for their book. Some argue that this system of herausgeber should be replaced by the internationally more accepted system of peer review.

6.2.3 OA policy landscape in Germany

The German research landscape is characterised by its decentralised structure: apart from the federal government, there are 16 states and each have their own ministry and research funding. Universities (and their libraries) are funded through the states, and partly through the funding programmes of the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft - DFG) as well as through other funders at national and European levels.

The decentralised nature of research funding leads to a large variety in policies, including OA policies. An OA strategy was introduced last year at federal level, but there are also policies at state level, for instance for Berlin, Baden-Württemberg and Schleswig-Holstein.

Another uniquely German feature is the strong presence of extra-universitarian and in some cases very large research performing organisations (RPO's), such as Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft, Leibniz-Gemeinschaft, and Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, along with one national and eight regional Academies of Sciences. These are all (partly) federally funded, autonomous organisations.

The German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) launched its strategy in 2016, aiming to make open access standard practice. The BMBF requires that scientific articles stemming from projects that it funded have to be open access by default, either through the gold or green routes to OA. In Germany, the green open access model has already gained support through a change in copyright law in 2014. Authors of mainly publicly funded research publications have the right to re-publish their manuscripts for non-commercial purposes after an embargo period of 12 months.

The German Research Foundation (DFG) is the single largest research funder in Germany, with an annual budget of around 2 billion euros.

DFG is governed by two bodies: a senate, representing the scientific community, and a main committee, consisting of scientists and representatives from the federal and state governments. DFG funds research conducted at the majority of universities and extra-universitarian institutes.

DFG stimulates OA through various programmes, but the common feature is that OA is recommended, not mandated. Another important feature is that OA policies focus on articles, not books.

Footnotes

37 <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/leap.1053/full>

38 http://blog.bibliothek.kit.edu/ag_univerlage/?page_id=535

The general policy regarding DFG funded research is that project results should be made publicly available either through self-archiving (green) or direct OA publication (gold). There is no licence specification.

DFG has a number of funding programmes directed at infrastructures:

- ▶ For electronic publications, for instance funding of OA journals or transforming toll access journals
- ▶ For national licensing agreements; and temporary (six year) co-funding of OA publication funds at universities to cover APCs (this programme has been implemented for 35 universities so far)

The Max-Planck-Gesellschaft has been a leading institution in the development of OA policies in Germany and internationally, dating back to the **Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities**³⁹ in 2003.

Some other RPOs have also developed OA policies: The Helmholtz Association aims for 60% OA by 2020, and 100% in 2025; Fraunhofer aims for 50% OA in 2020, of which 60% should be published via the gold road; the Leibniz Association recently introduced its OA publication fund.

What sets MPG apart from the other RPOs is the way it has centralised budget control over all publisher related expenditure - for content acquisition and licensing, and also for open access expenditure - within the Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL).

MPG launched the Open Access 2020 initiative⁴⁰ at the 12th Berlin Open Access Conference hosted by the Max Planck Society in December 2015. OA 2020 is an international initiative that aims to induce the swift, smooth and scholarly-oriented transformation of today's scholarly journals from subscription to open access publishing.

OA2020 aims "to transform a majority of today's scholarly journals from subscription to OA publishing in accordance with community-specific publication preferences. At the same time, we continue to support new and improved forms of OA publishing".⁴¹

This transformation is to be achieved by "converting resources currently spent on journal subscriptions into funds to support sustainable OA business models".

OA2020 invites stakeholders to sign the Expression of Interest. Close to one hundred research organisations have already signed. The practical implementation of the OA2020 initiative is coordinated through a roadmap, which is prepared by MPDL and updated regularly.

There are very few OA policies that include monographs or are directed at OA monograph publishing. It seems that none of the many private funders have shifted to OA, or made it possible to apply for BPCs.

DFG is the single exception; it has funded one call for proposals intended to support OA monographs, in 2012. This call resulted in two new OA initiatives: Language Science Press in Berlin, and Heidelberg University Publishing (further details below).

However DFG also has some programmes that support book publications (in print or digital), which can be utilised for OA:

- ▶ Successful DFG funded research projects can include up to €5000 in their project budget (for articles the price cap is €750 per year)
- ▶ A separate fund to support book publications, open for applications regardless of DFG funding, and without a limit

DFG is generally considering expanding its OA policy, and may include books in the future. However, given the strong position of scientists within the governance structure of DFG, any new policies will need to be based on clear evidence of a demand for OA, particularly among researchers.

MPG has some experience with supporting OA books. The first initiative was with De Gruyter, set up as a framework for a contractual relationship for OA books. However, this arrangement was not successful. But recently a new collaboration was agreed with Nomos (part of C.H.Beck). This agreement involves existing publishing projects with MPG, which makes it more promising. The agreement is based on initial BPCs, combined with transparency of costs and sales revenue, which is intended to lead to an evidence-based system to adjust the level of BPCs over time.⁴²

One of the MPG institutes, Max Planck Research Library for the History and Development of Knowledge, has an in-house open access book series: Edition Open Access. The series, which doesn't involve MPDL, aims to disseminate peer reviewed results of scholarly work to a broad audience rapidly and at low cost.⁴³

Attitude of scientists

In Germany, the discussion about open access has become entangled with the wider issues around digitisation (e.g. through the Heidelberger Appell which was launched in March 2009)⁴⁴. In the humanities at least, there is a small but very vocal group of researchers that present open access as a threat to academic freedom and this view has been strengthened by the perception of open access with lack of quality.

An example of this attitude is the discussion at the University of Konstanz. The university law of the state Baden-Württemberg (§ 44 (6) LHG) says that universities are supposed to oblige scientists to exercise

the right to make non-commercial use of their publications after they have been published in a commercial journal.⁴⁵ The University of Konstanz has implemented such a statute, resulting in some scientists filing a suit against their university by stating an infringement of Article 5 of the German Constitution which states: "Art and science, research and teaching are free".⁴⁶

However, there is also a large group of scholars supporting open access in the humanities, see the Siggenthesen.⁴⁷

Footnotes

39 <http://oa.mpg.de/berlin-prozess/berliner-erklarung/>

40 <https://oa2020.org/>

41 <https://oa2020.org/mission/>

42 http://nomos.de/aktuelle-meldungen/?tx_ttnews%5Btt_news%5D=44863&cHash=7c6f6bd3795a4f2c0d2ac5f7ab10e051

43 <http://edition-open-access.de/index.html>

44 http://textkritik.de/urheberrecht/index_engl.htm

45 "Die Hochschulen sollen die Angehörigen ihres wissenschaftlichen Personals durch Satzung verpflichten, das Recht auf nichtkommerzielle Zweitveröffentlichung nach einer Frist von einem Jahr nach Erstveröffentlichung für wissenschaftliche Beiträge wahrzunehmen, die im Rahmen der Dienstaufgaben entstanden und in einer periodisch mindestens zweimal jährlich erscheinenden Sammlung erschienen sind."

46 "Grundgesetz", Art. 5, Abs. 3

47 <https://merkur-zeitschrift.de/2016/10/24siggenthesen/#comment-939>

More generally, authors tend to choose publishers based on perceived prestige, which is usually connected to their brands, their size, or certain book series. Most researchers have very little understanding of publisher services and service levels and, as one publisher put it, “zero cost awareness”. Taken together, this leads to what this publisher called “the reputation economy”, and it creates an entry barrier for new publishers (especially if they offer innovative publishing models such as OA).

However, there are signs that the perception of researchers is slowly changing, at least in some disciplines. Researchers are also increasingly aware of lower service levels of established publishers and increasing author subsidies and retail prices.

6.2.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in Germany

Although Germany lacks OA mandates for books, there are several publishers actively involved in OA monograph publishing and there are several promising initiatives.

University presses

Although German university presses do not constitute a large segment of the monograph market, they represent the majority of the OA books output. It is interesting to note that the German university presses were, in fact, first movers towards OA, and already publishing OA monographs well before anyone else was doing this.

The university presses in the Working Group of University Presses share a common approach: The presses are non-profit and mostly embedded within the university library, as a service unit or as a publishing unit, in some cases as a separate legal entity.⁴⁸

As they are part of a larger organisation, they have few dedicated personnel: the average is 1.8 FTE. The average number of books published is 44.

This relatively high output indicates that in general, these presses do not perform all the tasks of conventional publishers. They are all committed to OA, and over half of the presses mandate OA.

The largest of these presses is KIT Scientific Publishing. They are not typical of the university presses, as they are part of the Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (belonging to the Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft) and not a humanities publisher. KIT Scientific Publishing was founded in 2004 in order to promote OA publishing. They have five FTE and publish around 160 books yearly, and over 1,700 to date. All books are OA, 70% of the books are PhD theses and about 35% of the books are in English. This large output is possible through the system of around 70 series editors, who are responsible for acquisition and quality assurance. The press has a highly standardised workflow based on stylesheets. Books are published with CC BY-SA as default licence, and are available in print through a PoD service. KIT Scientific Publishing charges between €500 and €600 for its services.

Another relatively large press is Göttingen University Press, with fewer than three FTE and around 50 OA books annually, and over 550 OA books to date (since 2003).

In terms of OA monograph output, both these presses are larger than any other publisher in our study.

Commercial publishers

Springer

Springer is one of the largest open access publishers internationally, but has a modest list of OA books (around 320 OA books for Springer and Palgrave together). Springer was one of the first publishers to offer OA for books, with the launch of Springer Open books in 2011. The books are made available at SpringerLink and accessible to anyone, using a CC BY licence as default option.

OA books aren't offered in separate, for sale e-book formats, but the printed book is available through the MyCopy service (for library customers).

Springer is in the process of integrating the Springer and Palgrave offerings. A challenge for the large legacy publishers is that their workflow is highly standardised and automated, and OA monographs require work arounds. Similarly, for the business side, OA is a challenge as it isn't part of the site-licence model.

De Gruyter

De Gruyter is one of the largest independent publishers of OA books and has a leading role in the transition to OA in the humanities in Germany. De Gruyter started its OA book publishing programme at an early date and accelerated the OA programme with the acquisition of Versita, a Polish OA publisher, in 2012.

De Gruyter's model for OA books is straightforward: gold OA is offered at a fixed fee of €10,000, all e-versions are OA (no e-book sales), and print is offered as a PoD service. The model is similar to Springer, in the way that the books are made available through their platform, on degruyter.com, with print offered as a PoD service.

De Gruyter recently launched its Open Access Book Library, intended to draw attention to the growing number of open access books on degruyter.com. The library already contains around 900 OA titles, approximately half of these are from DeGruyter, the other half from publishing partners. The largest partner for OA books is transcript Verlag.

Institutional publishers

[Perspectivia \(MWS\)](#)

Perspectivia.net is the central open access publication platform of the Max Weber Stiftung (MWS). MWS is one of the leading agencies supporting German research in the humanities abroad, with ten institutes providing a

bridge function between the host nations and Germany. Perspectivia launched in 2008 as a two-year project to develop a publication platform. As an institutional press, Perspectivia works with a budget and doesn't charge BPCs to authors. An important part of output comes from a retrodigitisation project (300-400 OA books), and a small part is "born digital" edited collections (around 30-40 in the last three years). Although Perspectivia set out to publish e-only, they found that authors prefer print, and so they provide PoD or small print runs next to the OA edition. They have around six FTE.

New entrants

[Language Science Press⁴⁹](#)

Language Science Press (LSP) is an interesting example of a new entrant that was developed with support from DFG. LSP is a pure OA, academic-led publisher. LSP has a discipline specific approach and was set up as a community enterprise, with currently 800 supporters from around the world (including the likes of Noam Chomsky).

LSP is developing a collaborative, library based funding model somewhat similar to Luminos, but set-up with Knowledge Unlatched as broker. The goal is to raise enough financial support to publish 30 OA titles yearly for three years (based on an annual fee from libraries of €1,000). Another innovative feature is open review as an option for authors, both pre-submission and pre-publication, and a feature for comments post-publication. However, this has not seen much take-up so far.

Footnotes

48 <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/leap.1053/full>

49 The Jisc report on New University Publishers and Academic led Publishers by Graham Stone and Janneke Adema provides more detail on LSP and meson press

LSP seems to be successful in overcoming one of the main barriers that new entrants have to face: to gain credibility among the community and attract authors. The discipline specific approach is one of the factors contributing to the early success of LSC. Another factor is the international and advanced nature of linguistics, when compared to other humanities disciplines (LingOA is another example in this area). Illustrative is the fact that LSP publishes predominantly in English, and that CC BY has been accepted as default.

Heidelberg University Publishing

Heidelberg University Publishing (heiUP) was set up by the university and with support from DFG, aiming to develop a business model and an xml-based publication platform.

HeiUP launched in 2015, as a pure OA publisher, based in the library. HeiUP has around four FTE and is funded by the library. The library has other publishing services and imprints, but these aren't peer reviewed.

HeiUP charges a low BPC, all books are peer reviewed and published OA, default CC BY, in various formats (PDF, html, EPUB), with optional print on demand. They are aiming to publish between eight and ten OA monographs in 2017.

Meson press⁵⁰

Meson press grew out of the project Hybrid Publishing Lab, based at Leuphana University of Lüneburg. It is a pure OA, academic-led press, founded by Mercedes Bunz, Marcus Burkhardt and Andreas Kirchner. Meson publishes experimental, multi-format books on digital cultures and networked media, and is committed to publishing under CC BY-SA. It has a mixed business model, based on book sales, BPCs and institutional support.

Modern Academic Publishing

Modern Academic Publishing (MAP) is a publisher of humanities monographs and journals drawn from the best work at the universities of Cologne and Munich. They focus on supporting young authors by publishing selected PhD theses as OA monographs. MAP is a partner of Ubiquity Press.

Books on Demand

Another potentially interesting development in the transition to OA monographs is the emergence of "white label" service providers. An example is Books on Demand (BoD), a multinational company providing e-book services to consumers and publishers. BoD is launching an open access publishing service specifically for research institutions.

6.2.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in Germany

It is likely that the German transition to OA will gain momentum through the OA2020 initiative. Apart from Max Planck Society, German signatories include the German Research Foundation, Göttingen State and University Library, the German Rectors' Conference, and other RPO' such as Fraunhofer, the Helmholtz Association, and the Leibniz Association. Obviously, OA2020 doesn't include OA for monographs. But it is interesting to note that, in principle, there is no reason why the process that is driving the transition for articles would not work for books. A number of people have argued that the way forward for OA monographs is for libraries to reserve an increasing percentage of their acquisitions budget for OA books, through collaborative funding models (such as Knowledge Unlatched).⁵¹ One could argue that OA2020 is based on the same principle, to achieve a transition through collaborative agreements with publishers.

Apart from OA policies for books, it is likely that the transition will continue due to market pressures. The conventional model for monograph publishing

is clearly losing its sustainability, and OA has the added advantage of making it easier to disseminate works beyond traditional academic channels, and is better suited to deal with the increasing importance of English.

Market pressures can support advocacy work to make book authors and editors aware of the benefits of OA, of the importance of disseminating scholarly books to the widest possible audience, and of retaining the rights to their work.

6.3 Country study: Netherlands

Key observations:

- ▶ The Netherlands is very active in terms of OA policy development: strong national policy, active library community, national action plan for open science, national offsetting agreements
- ▶ Most OA policies include monographs, but mandates aren't enforced and there is little uptake for gold OA books by authors
- ▶ The Netherlands has a relatively strong book publishing industry, very international, most providing OA services and ready for further transition

6.3.1 Introduction

The Netherlands, a strong advocate of OA, was perhaps the first country to negotiate national offsetting agreements, to allow Dutch researchers to publish their articles OA as part of new big deals with the main scientific publishers. The government used its EU Presidency in the first half of 2016 to raise the issue of open science and push it up the political agenda. This was followed early in 2017 by a National Plan for Open Science, which contains the ambition to achieve 100% OA for all scientific publications by 2020. The plan involves the Dutch universities, their libraries, the Royal Academy of Arts and Sciences, and the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), among

other academic institutions. NWO already mandates OA for publications resulting from research grants, and this mandate includes books. NWO was also one of the founders of OAPEN Foundation (after the EU project closed in 2011), and supported OAPEN-NL, the first national pilot exploring OA book publishing.

6.3.2 Monograph publishing landscape in the Netherlands

The Netherlands has a unique position in scientific publishing, which can be traced back to the 17th century. The relatively liberal atmosphere during the Dutch Golden Age brought religious refugees from all over Europe to the Netherlands, which contributed to a flourishing publishing industry. Some of the publishers today were established in the 17th century, when the Netherlands became the publishing centre of Europe.

Brill was founded in 1683, and Elsevier takes its name from the original House of Elzevir, a Dutch family publishing house founded in 1580 (although the modern publishing business Elsevier was founded in 1880).

Considering the size of the national market, the Dutch publishing industry is still very large and has a strong international focus. Elsevier became Reed Elsevier in 1992, and Kluwer, at one time the second largest scientific publisher in the world, merged Kluwer Academic Publishers with BertelsmannSpringer to form Springer science+business media in 2003.

Footnotes

50 See also the Jisc report on New University Publishers and Academic led Publishers by Graham Stone and Janneke Adema

51 See for instance Martin Eve: <http://blog.hefce.ac.uk/2017/02/28/its-time-to-heed-the-drive-towards-open-books/>

Outside of these huge publishing companies, the book publishing industry is not especially large, but very international. The majority of academic books are published in English and intended for international markets. The largest book publisher in the humanities is Brill, with an expected output of around 1200 books this year. Other academic book publishers are considerably smaller, such as John Benjamins (founded in the 1960's), Amsterdam University Press (established in 1992), Wageningen Academic Publishers (founded in 2002 as successor of Wageningen Pers), and Leiden University Press (re-established in 2010). Boom publishers is an exception among the academic book publishers, as its books are mostly in Dutch, and they have a mixed list (non-fiction, professional and academic).

6.3.3 OA policy landscape in the Netherlands

The Netherlands has been among the forerunners in the open access movement. The former president of the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), Jos Engelen, was a strong advocate for open access and NWO introduced an OA incentive fund in 2011. The NWO policy became a mandate in December 2015, requiring all publications resulting from NWO grants to become available to the public immediately at the time of publication. In addition, NWO will no longer pay for APCs in hybrid journals. However in June 2017, NWO announced it will terminate the OA incentive fund on 1 January 2018, arguing that the academic world is now sufficiently aware of open access publishing and its importance.

It is interesting to note that, notwithstanding the considerable commercial interests of the Dutch publishing industry, the Dutch government is also a clear supporter of OA. In 2013, state secretary Sander Dekker announced the government's support for open access and his preference for the gold route to OA. The aim was to have 60% of Dutch academic publications available through open access in five years (2019), and achieve 100% by 2024.

It became the task of the Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU) to manage the transition to OA. The VSNU started negotiations with the large publishers to achieve open access for publications from Dutch researchers within the framework of the big deals that were being renewed (usually referred to as offsetting agreements, but more accurately called pre-paid OA agreements). The VSNU has since reached agreements with Springer, Wiley, the American Chemical Society, Taylor & Francis, Elsevier, Sage, De Gruyter, Cambridge University Press and Brill. There was one renewal without securing OA, with Wolters Kluwer, with regard to law scholars, and just recently VSNU and Oxford University Press broke off negotiations as they were unable to reach an agreement to advance OA as part of renewing access to OUP journals.

Recently, due to a Freedom of Information (FOI) request, the VSNU published the major contract points including cost details for eight out of ten of their open access agreements (the agreements with Elsevier and Springer have not yet been made public).⁵²

From the start, the Netherlands tried to coordinate its activities with other countries, in particular Germany and the UK. The Netherlands used its Presidency of the EU in the first half of 2016 to push the open science agenda. The Dutch EU Presidency organised an open science conference in April, resulting in the Amsterdam Call for Action on Open Science.⁵³

Within the Netherlands, a broad coalition of stakeholders, among them the NWO, the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW), VSNU, the coalition of 13 Dutch university libraries and the National Library of the Netherlands (UKB) and SURF, was formed to develop the National Plan for Open Science.

The National Plan for Open Science was presented earlier this year.⁵⁴ It prioritises three issues:

- ▶ Aim to publish 100% open access in 2020
- ▶ Make possible the optimal reuse of research data
- ▶ Develop matching evaluation and reward systems

The aim to achieve 100% OA by 2020 is explicitly directed at all disciplines, and includes all types of publications (articles, books or parts of books, reports) resulting from publicly funded research.

The Dutch university libraries have also been very active in the transition to OA. In 2005, the Netherlands became the first country in which all university libraries had established an institutional repository. A number of universities (Erasmus University in Rotterdam, Eindhoven, TU Delft, Groningen) have adopted an OA mandate. The universities of Twente, Utrecht and Delft encourage open access publishing through a publication fund. VU University Amsterdam and Utrecht University and Maastricht University support researchers with setting up OA journals and, recently, Groningen University launched Groningen University Press, also with a focus on journals.

The Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (HvA), which merged with the University of Amsterdam, is a forerunner among the Dutch colleges. Under the leadership of rector Huib de Jong, HvA has established a framework with a range of instruments for OA: an OA fund for APCs; an OA mandate to deposit; a OA (self-) publishing service; and membership agreements with PeerJ, PLOS, Springer/BMC, and Frontiers.⁵⁵

Another notable development from the Netherlands is LingOA.⁵⁶ LingOA is an initiative of a group of prominent international linguists who want to make access to their scientific results less dependent on expensive commercial publishers.

With this initiative the linguists try to move other journals to the direction of affordable open access, based on a set of fair OA principles:

- ▶ The journal has a transparent ownership structure, and is controlled by, and responsive to, the scholarly community
- ▶ Authors of articles in the journal retain copyright
- ▶ All articles are published open access and an explicit open access licence is used
- ▶ Submission and publication is not conditional in any way on the payment of a fee from the author or its employing institution, or on membership of an institution or society
- ▶ Any fees paid on behalf of the journal to publishers are low, transparent, and in proportion to the work carried out

LingOA has received a grant from NWO to pay for APCs for five years. One of the OA journals is *Glossa*, which is run by the linguists formerly associated with an Elsevier journal, and published with Ubiquity Press in partnership with Open Library for Humanities.

Footnotes

52 http://vsnu.nl/en_GB/public-access-request

53 openaccess.nl/sites/www.openaccess.nl/files/documenten/amsterdam-call-for-action-on-open-science.pdf

54 <https://openscience.nl/en>

55 <http://www.amsterdamuas.com/content/news/news/2016/12/auas-aims-for-100-percent-open-access.html>

56 <http://lingoa.eu/about/mission/>

6.3.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in the Netherlands

The Netherlands has also been a forerunner in the transition to OA books. The first international initiative to develop OA monograph publishing was the EU co-funded project OAPEN, which was coordinated by Amsterdam University Press and involved the universities of Leiden and Amsterdam (2008-2011). After the close of the project, a number of Dutch academic institutions launched OAPEN Foundation, to continue the work OAPEN started and to develop services for OA monographs. The founders were Amsterdam University Press, the Universities of Amsterdam, Leiden and Utrecht, the National Library (KB) and KNAW.

OAPEN Foundation was established with financial support from NWO, and NWO was also one of the main funders of OAPEN-NL, the first example of a national pilot project to explore OA book publishing in collaboration with academic publishers (2011-2013).⁵⁷ OAPEN-NL led to similar projects in other countries (OAPEN-UK and OAPEN-CH), and in the Netherlands, the pilot resulted in the first OA monographs from established publishers such as Brill and Springer.

When NWO introduced its OA Incentive Fund to pay for OA charges, it included paying for BPCs. One of the outcomes of OAPEN-NL was that the original price cap of €5,000 per project, which was also used as the price cap for the books in the OAPEN-NL pilot, was raised to €6,000, to accommodate the higher costs of OA book publishing.

This price cap of €6,000 per funded project is still in place today, now that the OA policy has become mandated for all grants resulting from calls from December 2015 onwards, but as mentioned earlier, NWO will end the OA Incentive Fund.

The OA mandate from NWO differs from most other mandates, in that it requires immediate OA at the time of publication, without an embargo period. The OA requirement can be achieved through gold OA or through green OA, in which case authors can choose to deposit the “pre-review” version of the manuscript (the pre-print or submitted manuscript). NWO has chosen this approach because it prefers gold OA. NWO sees green OA as a temporary solution in the transition to gold. NWO argues that authors who do not wish to publish in OA can comply with NWO’s policy by making their submitted manuscript publicly available.

Although it is too early to monitor compliance with the OA mandate, and NWO has not taken any measures to enforce compliance, evidence suggests there has been very little uptake of the Incentive Fund for OA books since the close of OAPEN-NL in 2013, and there is no experience with the response of authors of monographs to NWO’s OA policy.

Two universities have OA publication funds that are open for payment of BPCs: Utrecht University and TU Delft. The experience at Utrecht University is similar to NWO, that there is little uptake from authors of monographs to publish OA. Evidence from our interviews suggests that most BPCs are covered through ad hoc payments from research departments or institutions, rather than through existing, centrally managed publication funds.

Both Utrecht and TU Delft provide OA publishing services. Utrecht has Uopen Journals (founded in 2003 as Igitur) and works with Ubiquity Press to provide a transitional model to sustainable OA journal publishing. TU Delft launched its service, TU Delft Open Publishing, earlier this year. Unlike Uopen, the service of TU Delft also includes book publications.

Many if not most of the academic book publishers in the Netherlands have an OA offering, and below we give a short description of the approach of some of these publishers.

Brill

Brill is one of the large international book publishers in the humanities and social sciences, but they are also active in international law and biology. They are based in Leiden with an office in Boston, USA.

Brill has grown through regular acquisitions, such as Martinus Nijhof (2003), Rodopi (2014), and most recently through the acquisition of Ferdinand Schöningh / Wilhelm Fink in Germany, which will bring the expected monograph output in 2017 to around 1,200. Brill started exploring OA for monographs in 2011, when it took part in the OAPEN-NL pilot, and has just over 200 OA titles. The list of OA books increased considerably when they acquired KITLV Press, an institutional OA publisher based in Leiden, in 2012. The most important funding scheme for OA monographs has been Knowledge Unlatched.

Brill charges a fixed fee for gold OA, depending on the type of licence: €18,500 for CC BY and €8,500 for CC BY-NC. The higher price for CC BY is based on the argument that the publisher has to give up all exclusive publication rights, whereas the lower fee reflects the fact that the publisher retains the right to commercial exploitation of non-OA editions. BPCs are fixed (except for books beyond 350 pages) and reviewed annually. Brill expects BPCs to increase as sales drop, because libraries (responsible for 85% of sales) will be better informed about the availability of OA editions. Brill does not sell e-books of titles that are available on OA licences.

Amsterdam University Press

Amsterdam University Press (AUP) was one of the early adopters of the OA book model, and played a prominent role as coordinator of the OAPEN project (starting in 2008) and of the OAPEN-NL pilot. AUP decided to make a large part of their backlist available through the OAPEN Library in 2010. This has led to the current total of 539 publicly available titles, of which 292 have a Creative Commons licence, which makes AUP one of the largest OA book publishers among the university presses.

However, AUP changed its approach to OA around 2011, when the University of Amsterdam appointed a new director and required the press to become self-sustaining. AUP moved from mission driven OA to market driven, and from predominantly academic to academic for the international market and non-fiction for the Dutch trade market. AUP now provides OA as there is increasing demand at government and funder level. AUP charges a flat fee of €4,500 for standard books. If the book is made OA after one year, the BPC drops by 50%. AUP allows immediate self-archiving for its books.

Footnotes

57 <http://oapen.org/download?type=export&export=oap-en-nl-final-report>

Leiden University Press

Leiden University Press (LUP) was re-established by Leiden University in two steps, first as an imprint of AUP, and in 2010 as a university press based in the university library, with a fixed annual subsidy to cover part of its costs. LUP's mission is to achieve open access for its publications, but so far only some of its books are publicly available. Of these 40 OA books, around half were made publicly available approximately three years after publication. The other half were gold OA: around 50% of the books were funded through KU, 40% were funded through contributions from research departments. LUP aims to continue with this model of delayed OA to achieve the target of 50% OA for its monograph output.

LUP works with Leuven University Press in Belgium for the production of its books, this includes the whole process from editing to printing. LUP does its own acquisition, peer review, marketing and sales. The collaboration with Leuven means BPCs are based on the production costs and are calculated separately for every publication.

6.3.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in the Netherlands

The Netherlands is firmly committed to achieving the full transition to gold OA as soon as possible, and is leading in the effort to do so through offsetting agreements with the main international publishers. The Netherlands is also committed to achieve this transition in collaboration with other countries, and several academic institutions in the Netherlands have signed the OA2020 Expression of Interest, the international initiative to induce a swift transformation to open access publishing hosted by the Max Planck Digital Library.⁵⁸ These Dutch stakeholders include NWO, the UKB (Dutch library consortium), the Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU) and a number of universities.

Although the focus in the Netherlands is clearly on achieving OA for articles, policies usually include books, and there is no reason why books cannot follow in the transition to OA. But books are not part of the discussion to achieve OA, and the risk is that they are left behind. Achieving OA for books will require more attention to the specific challenges around monographs. So far, there is little uptake of OA by authors, even when there are publication funds available. Compliance with NWO's OA mandate is not being monitored and there is no experience with how the policy works for books. And although a significant number of libraries in the Netherlands were early supporters of Knowledge Unlatched, most libraries have not yet made an ongoing commitment to support OA books through their acquisitions budgets.

6.4 Country study: France

Key observations:

- ▶ France benefits from state backing of OpenEdition, an open access platform for books and journals
- ▶ There is commitment to a number of large backlist digitisation projects
- ▶ University presses have been supported through institutions as cost centres. Some are now under pressure to begin to generate more income to the universities
- ▶ As sales of monographs are diminishing both commercial and university presses are looking more to possible new OA models to solve the problem

6.4.1 Introduction

France is one of the largest countries in our study and one of the most centralised. There are few global publishers (Hachette being the best known global publisher). Most of the monograph output is in French.

The platform CAIRN has estimated that there are 5000 new scholarly based works published each year by 160 publishers. Of these only about half are monographs (of which less than half are specialist monographs for a peer audience, the rest being high level cross-over books sold through the trade).

Publishing is starkly divided between small highly subsidised university presses and larger commercial publishers, many of which publish academic authors selling through the trade and bringing prestige to the publishing houses.

In 2016 the “Law for a Digital Republic” effectively authorised by strong encouragement, though stopped short of fully mandating OA for journal articles. The new law includes an article that essentially says:

“Free access to scientific articles resulting from public research provides the right given to researchers to make their articles available after a short embargo period of six to twelve months no matter what the agreement made between the researcher and the publisher of the journal in which the article appeared.”⁵⁹”

However, monographs and book chapters were not included in this new law. Nevertheless there is a growing sentiment that the subjects (generally in the humanities and social sciences) that favour books as a form of dissemination cannot be left behind.

Hosting of digital OA books from the university press sector is well catered for by OpenEdition which provides an open hosting platform as well as other services. The

commercial sector is only just beginning to discuss the opportunities that OA might bring to monographs.

6.4.2 Monograph publishing landscape in France

It is estimated that there are close to 160 publishers of monographs. Many of these are small with outputs of 20-30 new titles a year. Fifty percent of the output is produced by 50 large and medium sized publishers.

There are only 20 university presses that publish over 20 books a year. These are mostly monographs and annual reviews. The largest is the University of Rennes Press with 280 monographs published each year. The rest are published by commercial presses, of which 90% are independent (ie. not part of a conglomerate or publicly listed company).

University presses are funded as cost centres by their parent institutions (though accounting systems do vary). If they make a surplus they are generally expected to remit this back to the institution. Some exercise a certain amount of cross-subsidising within the press – publishing the odd textbook with sales of many thousands of copies, using the income to support the narrower and loss-making monographs. Even though most university presses have the benefit of rolling year budgets, there is a sense that they must justify the support received from the parent institution. Given that overall there is a loss that is absorbed by the institution there are limits to growth as there is limited money for investment. Some institutions have given notice that their support will reduce or be withdrawn altogether. (See description of PUFR in Chapter 7, Notable initiatives).

Footnotes

⁵⁸ <https://oa2020.org/>

⁵⁹ fieldfisher.com/publications/2016/12/law-for-a-digital-republic-of-7-october-2016#sthash.uRTAL5nr.sisbC1h3.dpbs

Many of the independent medium and large sized publishers are well known for monographs that cross over into the trade and are read avidly by French intellectuals and the educated public. These presses find that publishing a certain kind of monograph can bring distinction and prestige to the press even if sales generally are not as high as their more commercial non-fiction publications. Total life sales of monographs for scholars are reported as being in the range of 100 - 300 copies while books that are written based on scholarly research for a broader public generally sell between 1000 and 2000 copies, though, of course, a few sell vastly larger numbers.

French publishers make considerable use of publishing monographs in series. This not only gives structure to outputs but also reflects better its peer review processes. Generally it is the job of the series editor to review submissions for the presses. At some presses one or two staff members are also asked to evaluate the project, however, there is no standard approach to reviewing proposals as it is presumed that this will be done by whichever institution is paying for the publishing costs as it is in their interest to ensure the quality.

Open access for books is relatively undeveloped, though the infrastructure for delivery of OA content is well established through OpenEdition. Recently the average number of French university press books newly hosted by OpenEdition is just under 1,000 per annum. Of this 100 are new monographs and the rest are backlist books (coming on stream mainly due to a large-scale backlist digitisation project being undertaken by OpenEdition. France has the largest number of OA books listed in DOAB of all of the eight countries in this study, currently with just over 1,000 titles.⁶⁰

French monographs are relatively low priced when compared to their English counterparts. A number of factors account for this. Print runs are often longer, thus bringing down unit costs and these books are generally subsidised. Nevertheless, we were told that the average life income of a typical monograph has been in the region of 11,000 euros which is similar to revenues of higher priced, lower print run equivalents elsewhere. However, this would indicate more than a sale of 100-300 would suggest.

Monograph sales in France come to €28 million euros of which €18 million are to libraries and €10 million to individuals. Digital sales are in the region of 6% of sales.

There are two main publisher associations in France. AEDRES⁶¹ represents the interests of university presses while Syndicat National de l'Édition (SNE) represents the interests of commercial publishers. This is unlike some other countries where commercial and non-commercial mix inside various trade bodies.

6.4.3 OA policy landscape in France

There are no mandates for open access book publishing but the output of publicly funded research to be publicly available is strongly encouraged. The new “Law for a Digital Republic” of 2016 states that authors of journal articles stemming from publicly funded research will be able to make their articles available in open access regardless of arrangements with publishers, under embargoes no longer than six months for STM and 12 months for HSS. The new law created a great deal of controversy between ministries and between other stakeholders. Now, however, the work of implementing the new law has begun. Unlike a formal mandate it is an authorisation only.

Research itself is predominantly publicly funded. The ANR (Agence Nationale de la Recherche) is the body responsible for allocating research funding. It is independent of government and funds are

available under two streams – project-based calls and generic calls.⁶²

Some OA advocates would like to see another law come into force to cover monographs. Whether they will succeed is an open question and much will depend on the attitude of the commercial presses who are only just beginning to look at the advantages of a BPC based business model (especially in light of dwindling monograph sales).

The OA discussions on monographs are following in the footsteps of the debates on OA journals. A major report by the Institut de France's Académie des Sciences, **Les nouveaux enjeux de l'édition scientifique** by Jean-François Bach and Denis Jérôme in 2014 summarised the need to find a route to "free access to the information, for a regular or even decreasing budget outlay, whilst adhering to the fundamental principle of critical assessment of articles through peer review and the existence of journals to which the research scientists are attached".

Their recommendation was to issue national licences, paid for out of a national budget, "introducing an evolution of the principle of open access integrating a centralised flat fee subscription: a single multiannual subscription contract should be negotiated between the public authorities and each publisher, specifying which titles are eligible, organising free and immediate access via the publisher's site to all the articles of those reviews where one of the authors is employed by the institution that negotiated the subscription, consequently with payment of the flat fee plus a coefficient of revaluation designed to assure stable revenues for the publisher. Articles published in this system could also be archived as open access documents in the published format".

The Académie suggested that Couperin be charged with negotiating the flat fee agreements with publishers as they are also in discussions with them regarding APC policy.

Though sweeping in its design, CAIRN, amongst others, pointed out the dangers of unintended consequences of rapid change. In a recent presentation CAIRN showed that 60% of all views of journals on the CAIRN platform were made after 12 months – thereby making the argument against short embargos that would cause a dramatic decline of revenue. It is likely to also reduce print sales, which on the other hand would represent a significant saving to the libraries. From there a "platinum" model was suggested, requiring the establishment of a "payment system of publishing services by public institutions, probably grouping payments at the institutional level, with the support of the Ministry". Any such system would require a transition period to be supported by a national budget.

These same principles are being brought to the monograph discussion. It has become possible to envisage a mechanism whereby a "flip" could be introduced. Commercial concerns could be assuaged by compensations for lost revenue during a transition period until fees were settled. However, there is a strong perception of an ideological divide between the university presses and the commercial presses which makes it difficult at this time to bring the two parts of the publishing industry together.

Footnotes

⁶⁰ OpenEdition Books holds 3,800 open access academic monographs currently (june 2017). Only a small portion of it is indexed in DOAB.

⁶¹ aedes.fr/

⁶² <http://agence-nationale-recherche.fr/en/project-based-funding-to-advance-french-research>

6.4.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in France

University presses (publicly funded non-commercial entities) operate generally as cost centres within the parent institution and are migrating to open access – often tentatively at first – making use of the OpenEdition facility, which provides an easy hosting solution with freemium model income opportunities.

OpenEdition is a collection of four platforms that host both books and journals and it provides the freemium business model for monographs. (CCSD – is the unit that deals with open archives and runs HAL (Hyper Articles onLine) that serves as the National Repository.)

The centralisation and dominance of the public sector has led to a uniquely French evolution of OA that began first with the establishment of Revues.org in 1999 that led to the launch of OpenEdition in 2007 and which in 2013 became part of the state investment plan (Programme Investissements d’Avenir) and now has multiple year funding of its core running costs. The OpenEdition platform and its freemium services are available to publishers both inside and outside France.

Commercial publishers of monographs are beginning to show a greater interest in open access, especially if there will be ways to cover their costs (ie a BPC). This is because sales of monographs are dropping by 4-5% per annum and margins have been eroded. However, this can only be said of the specialist monographs written by scholars for scholars. Publishers refer to books that are scholarly but aimed at the broader market also as monographs and these are not likely candidates for OA. Sales substitution from e-books has not taken place in France, where the e-book market (both retail and institutional) is low in the region of 6%. This may ultimately be to the advantage of OA monographs as there is little digital market that would potentially be cannibalised by OA availability making any transition to OA from a business perspective easier to achieve. In the meantime, according to a leading

academic publisher, commercial publishers are abandoning monographs.

There are few platforms owned by publishers. The biggest private platform is CAIRN, a joint venture initially of four commercial publishers - La Découverte, De Boeck, Belin, Erès - to provide a platform for journals and magazines, and lately extended to books. The French National Library BNF joined the consortium in 2006.

CAIRN has a backlist of 8,000 titles (of which only 15 were open access at the end of 2016). Most of the 8000 books come from the large presses, most notably Presses Universitaires de France (PUF) that began life as a university press but is now a commercial entity. CAIRN does host closed monographs from other publishers and is looking at providing an OA offer sometime in the future. This would pitch them in direct competition with OpenEdition, which concentrates on the not-for-profit university presses. Cairn and OpenEdition do work together to some extent in the journal space. Where a journal needs the services of a platform for hosting closed content it uses CAIRN. Once the journal (or chapter) goes OA the publisher sometimes opts to move the content over to sit on the OpenEdition platform.

The university presses are funded by their parent institution and therefore do not need to charge authors for publication. Going open access is a natural extension from their traditional mission and with their publishing costs covered they then are able to avail themselves of further sales. Some continue to publish in print, others generate income through the freemium model offered by OpenEdition. This model hosts HTML free to view, while selling or renting PDFs and EPUBs either by bundles or individual books. However, the move to open access is being taken cautiously, especially by those university presses that are experiencing budget cuts from their host institutions.

The commercial press L'Harmattan publishes around 15% of all monographs. It charges authors and provides a no frills service for traditional closed (print) books. La Decouverte and L'Harmattan are important publishers in this area.

Publishing processes are formally outsourced much less than in other countries. A kind of non-cash economy exists where staff from various bodies such as CNRS are seconded or on loan to presses for activities such as copy editing.

There are no studies of what the cost of producing an OA monograph is likely to entail. There is a study on the editing cost of journal articles that is often referred to as a baseline. The study on the cost structure of HSS journal articles by OpenEdition arrived at a median cost of one article to be in the region of €1,330.⁶³ Assuming a book is made up of ten chapters each around the same length as a journal article the number would not be too dissimilar to BPC charges elsewhere.

Getting to first digital file is likely to be in line with other continental countries with similar wage structures. One publisher said:

“Getting to first digital copy costs is difficult as it is not a separate figure in an OA project since it is bundled with the total price charged to the funder. Charges depend on funder expectations and specifications for services. The simple hosting of a PDF can be €1,500 while the most expensive book with a great deal of pre-press work has been €50,000.”

BPCs are evolving in a way that “has grown out of the old subvention model where institutions or research funders paid for all costs including print. Now this money covers putting the book online in OA too”. The publisher interviewed expects costs to remain constant, though there may be some savings as print runs go down and variable sales costs decrease in line with the drop in sales. Nevertheless, that would result in lower contributions to overheads, and ongoing care of digital content.

In short her conclusion was “OA is still a big mess”. She would like each author to be in control of their own money for publication (wherever those funds come from) so that they can then take it to whichever publisher they want. But “politics intervenes”.

Technical formats can vary, but almost all monographs are produced as PDFs. Sometimes EPUBs are available too. If on the OpenEdition platform then the predominant OA version is in HTML though there are also PDF and EPUB versions available based on the original XML.⁶⁴

Historically most French monographs have been published only in French. However, as interest in greater visibility of French research increases there has been a growth in English as a language of dissemination especially when a monograph is published in OA.

Footnotes

⁶³ <https://fr.slideshare.net/revuesorg/a-cost-structure-study-for-french-hss-journals>

⁶⁴ See <http://books.openeditions.org/KSP/>

French publishers are generally happy to use the Creative Commons licensing suite. There is an active institutional repository network where green OA can be made available through the HAL platform. As in other countries it is too early to see how OA, whether green or gold, will impact on print sales.

6.4.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in France

The issues around OA monographs are beginning to be addressed in France; not only because of the controversies around the new law for journals, but also because of the distinct divide between commercial and non-commercial presses. Interviewees also stressed the differences between the two types of monographs, the one that is for a limited peer group and the other having more general trade appeal. Providing OA for the former inevitably will lead to stricter boundaries between both types.

Straddling the divide between both commercial and non-commercial presses is the Couperin Consortium, a non-profit association financed by the contributions of its 253 members, including 108 universities and similar institutions, 29 research organisations, 87 schools, three other libraries and 26 other organisations with a mission to promote higher education or research. It also receives a subsidy from the Ministry of Higher Education and Research. Couperin's mission is to:

- ▶ Collect and analyse the documentary needs of its members
- ▶ Evaluate, negotiate and organise the purchase of digital documentary resources for the benefit of its members
- ▶ Develop a national network of skills and exchanges on electronic documentation, including acquisitions policies, collections development plans, information systems, publishers' billing models, access ergonomics and usage statistics

- ▶ Contribute to clarifying and evolving contractual relationships with publishers
- ▶ Contribute to the development of an offer of French-language content
- ▶ Improve the scientific communication and promote the establishment of non-commercial systems of scientific and technical information (STI) through the development of appropriate tools
- ▶ Develop expertise and evaluation of information systems and their tools as well as methods for integrating them into the information systems of institutions, in coherence with other institutions in charge of development and - Implementation of information systems in the world of higher education and research and to promote national, European and international cooperation in the field of electronic documentation and publications

Comparable organisations in the other seven countries in our study are Jisc (UK), DEFF (DK), CSC (FI), DFG (DE), SURF (NL) and CRISTin (NO). The extent to which they engage with the OA question for monographs varies.

Couperin has been a strong advocate for open access and is likely to play a significant role in promoting OA for monographs in the future. It has a number of committees working on policy, technical and business issues and work with OpenEdition on a Knowledge Unlatched type pilot project underway called OpenEdition Unlocked where they are looking for library support to crowd-fund 40 titles. Building on the natural support of OpenEdition and university presses Couperin is hoping that commercial presses will take an interest in OA for monographs too. If there is to be any significant move to OA most people think there will need to be state support for a transition period while publishers find their way to sustainable models. Having said this, existing negotiations commitments have made

it difficult for Couperin to devote resources to OA books. Nevertheless, Couperin kindly worked with this study to translate, adapt and administer the library questionnaire for French librarians.

Libraries clearly will have an important role in determining the next stages of OA; that is a regular topic at the Association of French Library Directors. While there are technical issues around upgrades, and currently discussion is around improving research data management, these are not the main obstacles facing OA. As with other countries there needs to be a multiplicity of tipping points coming together from all stakeholder communities. One librarian summarised many of the barriers in our survey:

“ We would like to provide support for OA for research data and underlying data. The main barrier is the way research assessment works, both for individual researchers and for institutions. Researchers are not rewarded for publishing in OA and research assessment still uses criteria such as impact factor. Another barrier is the complexity and variety of publishers’ OA policies: that makes it very difficult for researchers to know what they’re allowed to do with their publications. In arts and humanities, many publishers don’t have an OA policy. ”

A number of interviewees said that authors are still reticent to put their monographs in open access. This may be because of the greater possibility of crossover books that sell to individuals through the book trade and not just to libraries. As noted above, the two types of monographs, are used interchangeably and cover both specialist books currently bought by institutions and crossover books that sell through the trade.

A survey by CAIRN indicated that more monographs were considered trade books than specialist titles for scholars only. Furthermore, there are significant numbers of librarians for whom OA monographs for new books are not high on their agenda. Whether this is because they already have access to a large and growing number of university press backlist outputs already on OpenEdition is an open question.

There is also discussion as to whether the green or gold route is preferable. Either way, costs will be examined along with establishing the best way to preserve the integrity of monographs. If central funding can be reallocated for the long term along with a transition fund France has many of the elements in place required to implement an OA policy for books.

Footnotes

- 65 http://cache.media.enseignementsuprecherche.gouv.fr/file/Infrastructures_de_recherche/16/4/infrastructures_UK_web_615164.pdf
-

France also has a French National Strategy on Research Infrastructures that is highly supportive of open access monograph publishing.⁶⁵ This highly integrated strategy for all disciplines includes publication via OpenEdition, stating in its 2016 edition:

“ The OpenEdition infrastructure designs new ways of digital scientific publication equipped with tools for online treatment, acquisition and collaboration. The infrastructure allows for improving the impact of interdisciplinary research projects and their ability to transfer their results to the social and economic stakeholders in order to meet the social challenges at the national and European levels. (page 12) ”

OpenEdition sits alongside the other smaller, but well supported means of distribution (HAL, the national repository, for pre-prints, Numedif and Collex Persee for books and library materials). All contribute to what could ultimately be an holistic approach to the distribution of publicly funded research outputs. Each are guaranteed multi-year funding.

OpenEdition itself has its annual operating costs of three million euros underwritten by state funding and also participates in EU projects that contribute to (and benefit from) its expertise.

Unfortunately the commercial and university presses rarely get together in order to discuss their differences. There are separate trade associations for each (Syndicat National de l'Édition) with commercial press

members and AEDRES for the university presses, thus providing few opportunities to meet informally. The missions and cultures have very diverse roots. Nevertheless, there is sufficient concern about the future of specialist monographs that CAIRN and others are now actively exploring the viability of OA.

Conclusion

France is sitting at a crossroads. The Bibliothèque Scientifique Numérique (BSN) has been tasked with roadmapping the implementation of the new digital law for journal articles and no doubt this will lead to further thinking about monographs. Discussions about gold versus green continue, though the people interviewed seemed to favour the gold model. Priority will be to get buy-in from all stakeholders, especially the Agence Nationale de la Recherche.

Awareness of OA possibilities for books appears in some ways less well developed in France than in Germany or the UK. This is mainly due to the assured outlets through both the university presses and the commercial ones. There has been less attack on print books from digital sales than in, say, the UK that makes for an unstable marketplace. And authors are not demanding OA. Nevertheless, much of the technical infrastructure is in place to deliver OA monographs to readers. The future of monographs is in enough danger now that solutions are being sought, and OA is one way to solve the problem.

6.5 Country study: United Kingdom

Key observations:

- ▶ The UK has led the way in encouraging and mandating open access
- ▶ The possible HEFCE mandate for OA books for the next but one REF (2026/27) is likely to be a game changer not least because of the large output of English language monographs
- ▶ UK publishers are, to varying degrees, embracing OA through BPCs due to the decline in monograph sales and it is only the lack of funding that is stopping greater adoption
- ▶ New university and academic-led presses are demonstrating the potential impact of OA books and are also experimenting with new forms of digital content, though this is at a very small scale

6.5.1 Introduction

The UK OA monograph landscape has been shaped by three drivers. Firstly there has been considerable thought and planning going into a policy framework at the national level. Secondly the UK is home to a traditional global publishing industry that is increasingly interested in OA, especially as the older business models for monographs are under threat. Thirdly, a rapidly growing number of institution (library) and academic-led born digital initiatives are experimenting with not only OA publishing but also how all aspects of the monograph might change in the future. For examples of this see the work of Open Book Publishers.

The single most important policy driver is HEFCE's intention to mandate that monographs are submitted to its Research Excellence Framework (REF). This is the review that determines block research grants to universities throughout the UK every six years. Following on from the Crossick Report⁶⁶ the Universities UK (UUK)

body has established a committee that has as its brief to propose a roadmap that ensures this policy can be brought into effect by 2026/7. We discuss this in greater detail below.

The UK's global English language academic publishing industry is the largest among our countries, and in the field of peer reviewed monographs is in all likelihood the largest in the world, with more titles being published than even from the United States. (The recent report by Joe Esposito⁶⁷ came to a figure of 4000 new monographs from all US university presses, while the total number of the top five in the UK, as reported from our survey exceeds that number.) Many global brands have their headquarters, or very sizeable branches, in the UK. With unit sales of monographs dwindling these publishers are actively looking for new models to keep their businesses sustainable. Coupled with digital opportunities, OA is an attractive option if funding can be secured. At the same time, the very size of the largest companies creates challenges in adapting workflows and staff skillsets. Nevertheless new staff in new OA departments for handling OA books is a signal that they are gearing up for a coming step change.

At the time of writing the Jisc sponsored report **Changing Publishing Ecologies: A Landscape Study of New University Presses and Academic-led Publishing** by Graham Stone and Janneke Adema found 33 new institution or academic-led new academic presses, primarily in the UK. There is an anticipation that the number will grow as more universities are

Footnotes

66 [hefce.ac.uk/media/hefce/content/pubs/indirreports/2015/Monographs_and_open_access/2014_monographs.pdf](https://www.hefce.ac.uk/media/hefce/content/pubs/indirreports/2015/Monographs_and_open_access/2014_monographs.pdf)

67 <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2016/05/10/the-open-access-monograph/>

considering how they might better serve the publishing interests of their scholars. A mini business ecosystem is emerging as the larger new presses offer services to the smaller ones. In some ways the institutional link of most of these presses echoes continental university press operations, in other ways they stand as beacons producing exciting new experiments with digital content, marketing and new business models. While the investment and outputs are at a very low level these initiatives bring fresh air to the monograph conundrum.

6.5.2 Monograph publishing landscape in the UK

Amongst the eight countries covered in this study the UK publishes the greatest number of monographs. The UK has the largest number of publishing companies working in the academic publishing space, with the largest number of HSS monographs currently emanating from Routledge, OUP, CUP, and the Palgrave imprint of SpringerNature. Together these four companies make up something in the region of two thirds of all monographs published in the UK.

The OA publishing landscape is dominated by the English language and global sourcing for both authors and sales. Specific figures are hard to come by and are often not comparable as much output originates in branches of the largest and even mid-sized companies around the world. The variety of types of presses is also greater in the UK than elsewhere with a strong presence of commercial presses.

Although Oxford University Press and Cambridge University Press account for a very large number of monographs (together close to 2,000 new monographs each year) as companies they are expected to make a surplus (profit) as are some of the smaller traditional university presses such as Edinburgh University Press, Liverpool University Press and Manchester University Press. Surpluses are re-allocated at the discretion of their respective universities and while not distributed to shareholders in the usual sense they often fund non-UP

activities, ie they are contributions to the universities' central budgets and therefore these presses are under similar pressures to commercial companies.

Most of the larger companies publish monographs as part of their general coverage of a range of academic output (including textbooks, reference works and e-resources). Most mid-sized and small companies also maintain a mixed portfolio, though many began as monograph publishers.

Monographs generally are not subsidised by the state and sales are dwindling. Those UK companies that relied heavily on monographs in the past are attempting to diversify their portfolios. This includes experimentations with multi-media publications, along with more niche course books, reference material and trade books. At the same time universities are stepping in with small-scale publishing initiatives to create more opportunities for academics to publish monographs. These new presses are mainly open access.

The UK does not have as strong a tradition of publishing PhD theses as other European countries. Indeed, generally only those PhDs that are substantially re-worked make it onto a publisher's list. From a sales and marketing perspective edited collections are treated the same as single authored books. In the past there was a general feeling that libraries had a bias against edited collections, and sales were generally lower than monographs. Obtaining review coverage also proved more difficult for edited collections. Now, with the digitisation of books, easier ways of drilling down to the chapter level facilitates assigning chapters instead of whole volumes for courses. There is, therefore, a resurging interest in edited volumes.

The UK publishing landscape generally differs from all the other countries in Europe. It is a large industry with over 2,000 book publishers producing outputs in both print and digital valued (according to the 2015

Publishers Association annual report) at £3.3 billion and another £1.1 billion for journals. Of the £1.42 billion in exports, two thirds were educational, academic and English language teaching (ELT) publications. These are large numbers in which monograph publishing is embedded. Academic and professional book sales for both print and digital in 2015 amounted to £1,049 million.

According to the Publishers Association, while digital sales have increased by 4%, this is still a relatively small number equalling 25% of the total print and digital book sales, and thus the total drop in sales in the sector has been 2%. Over a five year period (2011 -2015) digital has increased by 78.2% while print sales have declined by 14.8%.

While there are English language monograph publications emanating from all of the countries in this study the UK benefits from English being the mother tongue and therefore a longer history of publishing monographs in English. The top four referred to in the Crossick Report represent a significant share of monograph output though their experimentation with open access remains small.

Figure 1: Monograph output by UK publisher as at end 2016

Company	Monograph output	OA monographs listed in DOAB
OUP	1,000	32
CUP	650	7
Routledge	3,000	10
Palgrave (now part of Springe Nature)	2,000	45
Total	6,650	94

The number of monographs produced annually in the UK is not known. However, the top four UK companies produce nearly 7000 monographs while only accounting for 94 of the 594 UK OA titles listed in DOAB. This suggests that the larger companies have been slower than the smaller ones in adapting the workflow practices to accommodate OA monographs. Nevertheless, they have all now embraced OA (with information on their programmes on their websites) and these numbers are expected to grow rapidly.

Peer review practices vary to some extent. However, most UK publishers see peer review as an important element of quality control. Most publishers obtain two or more reviews of monograph proposals. Some, but not all, send the full manuscript out for peer review before starting the production process. These decisions are influenced by a number of trade-offs. Some don't want to slow down the progress of a publication by full peer reviews, others see it as an unnecessary cost and rely on their senior commissioning editors to take a view on the final manuscript even if they don't necessarily read it in full.

The benefits of publishing monographs in series is well recognised by UK and publishers elsewhere as series have the prospect (though not the certainty) of being considered as a single entity with something like a subscription commitment from libraries who take all of the books of any particular series, often through standing orders with vendors.

Distribution of print books has generally been provided by either large publishing houses that have their own warehouses, or by specialised warehousing services that distribute for a number of publishers. Some of these have also moved into distribution of digital files. The distribution of files is also offered by aggregation services – the largest of which are EBSCO and ProQuest in the commercial space. These are international companies with home bases in the USA along with the two best-

known non-commercial digital distributors, JSTOR and MUSE (both having developed book services following on from successful e-journal distribution activities).

Sales representation has on the whole been split between those sales agents (internal to large companies and external to smaller ones) who follow the old school of selling print books to the trade and to institutions around the world and those who specialise in e-book selling (globally).

The latter are mainly aggregators, though larger publishers have their own e-content sales forces and mid-sized companies are increasingly investing in direct selling to institutions and to individual customers (mainly through their websites and Amazon). For monographs this remains an unresolved issue as libraries do not, on the whole, wish to deal with large numbers of individual publishers. OUP and CUP have their own platforms (UPSO and Cambridge Core) that offer digital sales and distribution packages to other publishers.

As mentioned above the UK is distinctive because of its global reach. It is estimated that well over 50% and in many case 80% of print monograph sales come from exports. However, global reach does not mean large sales per title or greater readership. The average number of copies sold is now under 200. At this point that means that about 20-100 copies of monographs are sold within the UK. This is in the context of having 186 universities and over two million students. According to Nielson Bookscan and cited in the **Academic Book of the Future** report sales of HSS monographs through retail channels – another incomplete way of measuring sales - is between 60-100 books in the main English language markets.

Although the split between print and digital for monographs is plateauing out at about an 80/20% split the different e-book sale models to libraries (such as PDA, DDA, EBA, STL etc) is making “sales” difficult to track.

There is less standardisation of marketing practices than before, especially given the pressures to experiment with social media. The marketing budgets for monographs vary from as low as 4% of sales for closed books of a traditional press and by extension to any BPC income plus additional sales of other formats – to a number expressed as 25% of total income to cover costs not covered by a supporting institution. This makes it very difficult to establish like for like comparisons. In addition many of the intermediaries that sell for UK publishers undertake marketing efforts that are covered by the discount they receive from the publisher. Suffice to say that costs of marketing may now be lower than before since it is about clever use of digital opportunities rather than printing leaflets and taking out advertising space in print media.

6.5.3 OA policy landscape in the UK

The UK introduced its policy and mandate on OA journal articles following on from the Finch Report **Accessibility, sustainability, excellence: how to expand access to research publications**⁶⁸ published in 2012. The funding and enforcement of the mandate fell to both Research Councils UK (RCUK) and the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) which is responsible for administering the REF for all of the UK. Together RCUK and HEFCE (along with smaller funding bodies for Scotland, Northern Ireland and Wales) have been responsible for most of the UK public funding available for research. These research councils will (mostly) be consolidated (subject to legislation) under one body, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) in 2018, though HEFCE will keep some of its non-funding responsibilities.

The REF is the review of research that takes place every six or seven years upon which state block grant funding for research is then based going forward for the next six or seven years. HEFCE implemented its policy to accept only OA articles for the next REF (2021) through either green or gold methods for all articles published

after April 2016. HEFCE has been more cautious with monographs following on from the findings of the Crossick Report. However, for the time being it encourages monographs and edited collections to be published as OA through extra carrots rather than sticks. HEFCE has stated its intention to bring books in line with journal articles in the next but one REF, though uncertainties around Brexit etc. are a challenge. A consultation document issued this year on the next REF includes a section on OA monographs.⁶⁹

The report concluded that:

- ▶ Open access offers both short and long-term advantages for monograph publication and use; many of these are bound up with a transition to digital publishing that has not been at the same speed as that for journals
- ▶ There is no single dominant emerging business model for supporting open access publishing of monographs; a range of approaches will coexist for some time and it is unlikely that any single model will emerge as dominant
- ▶ Printed books will continue to be preferred for extensive reading and may form a part of many future business models; they will therefore continue to a considerable extent to be available alongside their open access versions

The aim at this point is to set out a direction of travel and to reassure the community that a nuanced approach will be taken with regards to monographs given the complexities, for instance, with third party rights permission, sensitivities around licensing and a multitude of business models.

The UUK Open Access Coordination Group has recently established an OA monographs working group (chaired by Professor Shearer West (Deputy Vice

Chancellor, University of Sheffield and from October 2017 Vice Chancellor of the University of Nottingham). The group brings together a range of stakeholders such as publishers (traditional, new and academic-led), research librarians, funders, and representatives from learned societies. This group aims to address the obstacles and barriers (publisher requirements, licensing and copyright issues) in order to move forward with OA monograph policy. The group is also addressing what needs to be done to bring about a cultural shift within the academic community.

Administration of the RCUK funds is mostly carried out by libraries, though in some cases it flows through faculties. Block grants from HEFCE are only secured through to 2018; there is as yet no decision on what will follow thereafter (pending the mergers as a result of UKRI). It is likely that there will be a preference for gold OA for books, but it is too early to be sure.

Wellcome, based in the UK, has been a big and early player in promoting OA in the field of medicine – primarily in journals where most medical research is published. It has a lesser-known fund and strategy for monograph publishing of books in the area of medical history and these funds are available to authors with Wellcome grants around the world. As with journal articles Wellcome has been a pioneer in setting standards for OA monograph publishing.

Footnotes

⁶⁸ <https://acu.ac.uk/research-information-network/finch-report>

⁶⁹ hefce.ac.uk/pubs/year/2016/201636/

The AHRC funded study on **The Academic Book of the Future**⁷⁰ published its findings in June 2017. Broad in scope, much of the project and its findings will feed into further debate on how to handle open access for monographs. It does not anticipate the speed of OA growth anticipated by the Simba Information study that suggests a 30% annual increase in open access books generally.⁷¹

One issue that remains unaddressed, however, is where sufficient funding for OA outputs will come from. Some libraries have carved out small funds from their discretionary spending budgets. Some institutions have begun to set aside funds from central budgets for OA monograph support. There is interest in initiatives such as Knowledge Unlatched, where funding is sourced from the global library community. To date, 13 UK presses have participated in the KU programme (over half of the 60 presses come from North America and the rest from Europe and other parts of the world). Can such initiatives scale and will they be able to sit alongside larger block funds from the funding bodies as they move to mandating or at least seriously encouraging OA? The discussion on how to re-route current funds to support OA is going on in the UK now. Given the numbers involved (over 8,000 books submitted to the REF 2014) the sums needed will be considerable.

6.5.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in the UK

Despite a great deal of discussion most publishers have not experimented extensively with OA. Of the 11 UK publishers responding to the Simba survey Bloomsbury Academic published the largest number of OA titles (137). The average amongst the remaining ten was 15 titles per company – though even this number is high as it includes the born digital OA presses Open Book Publishers and UCL Press. The numbers are much lower amongst the traditional presses as is evident in the DOAB.

Of the three large countries in the study, the UK lags behind with only 594 OA books listed in DOAB as compared with over 1,000 from both Germany and France.

As a comparative historical context, there is less of a tradition of asking authors for payment for publishing monographs in the UK as compared with the rest of Europe. However, authors are regularly asked to pay for extra charges such as third party rights permissions, colour plates etc. In the past this was often funded by a reduction of royalties. However, as sales of monographs are now so low (as are royalty rates) royalties do not always cover these costs. They now come out of departmental budgets or the pockets of authors themselves.

New university and academic-led presses

There is now an increasing number of new university presses that were either the initiative of a department of a university, a university library or led by the drive of a single or small group of academics. A comprehensive report is available from Jisc: **Changing Publishing Ecologies: A Landscape Study of New University Presses and Academic-led Publishing** by Graham Stone and Janneke Adema. The study looks at 33 new institution and/or academic-led publishing initiatives, primarily in the UK. Stone estimates further growth. Two of the twelve libraries responding to our questionnaire have library-led new OA presses, and two were considering creating new university presses.

At this point all new institution-led university presses require institutional support and the question of scaling is not yet on the agenda. Nevertheless, they are experimenting not just with new business models but also with different publishing formats, multimedia publishing and new modes of marketing, sales and distribution. These new university presses are struggling to enter the traditional sales channels, often under pressure from authors who want to see their books sold as well as available in OA.

In addition to new university presses there are also new academic-led presses some of which have institutional support.

These include; Counter Press, Electric Press, Goldsmiths Press, Mattering Press, MayFly Books, Media Commons Press, Open Book Publishers, Open Humanities Press, Punctum books, Roving Eye Press and Ubiquity Press. A few focus on books only, but most publish a mix of books, journals and multimedia publications.

Business models and pricing of BPCs

Most publishers who offer open access do so on the basis of charging a Book Processing Charge. There are a few exceptions where print sales are expected to cover the full publishing costs. However, as discoverability, visibility and greater willingness to read on screen grows the future of print sales remains unknown.

Figure 2: BPC charges and licensing options by UK publisher

Publisher	BPC charge	Licensing options*
OUP	Tailored to each title	CC BY-NC-ND
CUP	£6,500	CC BY-NC
Routledge	£9,500	CC BY-NC-ND
Palgrave	£11,000	CC BY
Bloomsbury	£6,500 - £8,500	CC BY-NC-ND
Manchester University Press	£10,000	CC BY-NC and ND

* licences tend to be negotiated with authors and the licences in the list are the ones found to be used predominantly at this time.

Costs of getting to first digital file vary from publisher to publisher. The range reported in our survey from traditional presses (whether university or commercial) was between 5,000 and 15,000 euros. Much depended

on how much overhead was included, while most of the core costs such as copy editing, typesetting, design had far less variation. The new university presses, whether in our survey or not, have different ways of accounting for overheads – much of which is absorbed by the institution, in particular the library budget. For more information on why BPC charges vary so much see Appendices, Part four, Chapter 10).

6.5.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in the UK

Over the next few years the work of a number of committees will coalesce into a policy proposal for the UK. This is taking place at a time of flux as HEFCE itself is under reorganisation with parts of it merging with RCUK to form UKRI. While the framework for moving ahead was set by the Crossick Report⁷² and the HEFCE REF consultation document, the UUK OA Monograph Group is seen as taking the lead in the matter going forward. Jisc Futures is another body that is providing intellectual muscle in particular on platform issues and a wider OA group is envisaged at the time of writing.

It is probably fair to say that the research councils remain to be convinced that there is strong market (author) demand for open access though they believe it will come and they will react positively to it. Indeed, as was reported in our interviews, once authors understood the benefits of OA they were very enthusiastic. Everyone is hoping that there will be less controversy over OA monographs than there has been over journal articles. The pressures on universities and HEFCE resulting from Brexit are another challenge.

Footnotes

70 <https://academicbookfuture.org/>

71 <https://simbainformation.com/Open-Access-Book-10410716/>

72 hefce.ac.uk/pubs/rereports/year/2015/monographs/

A National Monograph Strategy has been in the making for the last few years. A roadmap was published in 2014 with the focus on efficiencies in collection development, greater use of e-books, web-based services and infrastructure. The ultimate aim as defined then was “a collaborative, national infrastructure that provides answers to the past, present and future challenges of the scholarly monograph”.⁷³ A common platform was proposed, but there has been little appetite for this since. Except for openness of software and data there was little mention of open access. This is being revisited in light of the expected HEFCE mandate for monographs. A new National Bibliographic Knowledgebase for metadata is now being built by OCLC, aiming to aggregate academic bibliographic data at scale, improve library collection management and resource discovery for students and researchers – to be delivered by the end of 2017.

The Academic Book of the Future report presents a view of OA from an arts and humanities perspective – where, as HEFCE acknowledges, there are still challenging hurdles to overcome. Nevertheless, the Simba Report and others that have followed the Crossick Report are optimistic that the challenges will be overcome. The key will be to accept that there will be no single route to open access.

As mentioned above Wellcome has led the way with specific guidelines on open access encouraging, but not mandating, a more liberal licensing policy than that of HEFCE or RCUK. It is likely that different policies from the various funding bodies will continue to be a feature of the UK landscape. The administration of the varying policies and the motivations for supporting OA monographs inside institutions are looked at more closely below from both the specific library perspective and the overall institutional perspective. In a further new development the Arcadia Foundation has announced that it will be re-entering the policy discussions on OA and it is yet to be seen if there might be additional funds for experimenting with OA monographs.

Library perspectives

UK institutional libraries are supporters of open access in principle. Libraries have, on the whole, been the university department tasked with administering APCs and increasingly BPCs. Guidelines from the various funders vary and administering these correctly is a burden on the libraries. For example, UCL (University College London) Library lists 39 different funder policies on its website. There are differing views on the efficacy of the process both for journals and books and for many libraries open access is not high on their agenda when compared with more pressing issues such as budget cuts, currency devaluation etc.

Libraries often provide training on open access for academics delivering information both online and in person – both through seminars and one to one. Many have allocated a small amount of funding to supporting individual OA initiatives such as the Open Library of the Humanities (currently only serving journals), Open Book Publishers and Knowledge Unlatched. These effectively employ crowd-funding mechanisms to support OA publishing and reach beyond the interests of the institution and its academics as authors.

Institutional perspectives

UK universities are competitive with one another for research funding from both RCUK and HEFCE (along with its sister bodies covering Scotland, Northern Ireland and Wales). The criteria for block grants from HEFCE rest on REF success, the criteria for which changes with each round and is hotly debated. Universities invest heavily in ensuring that they score well with stages of pre-submission vetting. As one of the increasingly important measurements of research importance is its impact, universities are increasingly looking at altmetrics and other measurements. There is a growing interest in downloads, and open access provides a better indicator of “market” penetration than simply sales. As a result funds are being garnered to

support OA from various budgets. For example, one university that runs a Vice Chancellor's Strategic Innovation Fund allocated £50000 for monographs in addition to a larger sum set aside to pay for APCs where no other funding was available. It would be expected that the number of universities providing such funding will grow once OA becomes compulsory for monograph submissions to the next but one REF round (or its equivalent) by 2026/27.

At the time of writing the OA monograph publishing landscape has taken a backseat to fine-tuning the way that APCs are administered as the mandate for journal articles took effect only in April 2016 while books and book chapters have a long lead in time if, as expected, the mandate will only apply to books submitted for the 2026/27 REF, or even only the one after that.

Conclusion

In summary there is slow movement towards some set of national level policies flexible enough to embrace the varying requirements of the multitude of funding bodies and business models that nudge OA along wherever possible without coming into conflict with intractable issues (such as third-party permissions for images). There is recognition that there will be multiple roads to open access for monographs.

There is some interest within an increasing number of institutions to support monograph publishing through a number of initiatives, ranging from allocating funding for BPCs to more sizable investments in born OA university presses.

Publishers facing decreased sales of closed monographs are increasingly interested in covering costs by going OA and attracting BPCs. At this point there is little empirical work on matching costs and revenues from both print and digital. However, while revenues are expected to drop overall for OA books as visibility and discoverability of OA versions improves

there is no doubt that the market for print will remain – the question will be whether all sources of income, whether BPCs or sales, will be sufficient to cover costs.

6.6 Introduction to the Nordic countries

Of the Nordic countries⁷⁴ Denmark, Finland and Norway are very similar in population size (between five and six million inhabitants each). Together with the other two Nordic countries, Sweden and Iceland, they share a long and profound history that has been formalised as Nordic co-operation for more than 60 years (the Nordic Council of Ministers and the Nordic Council).

As small countries the Nordics share the challenges of small languages. Danish, Norwegian, and Swedish are very similar languages, which gives some possibilities in terms of closer collaboration whereas Icelandic and in particular Finnish are distinctively different. However, all of the languages are small and within academia very often overtaken by English as the **lingua franca**. The language issue in the Nordic region is, therefore, prominent both within policymaking and academic publishing and also part of the discussion around OA. The language issues are probably even more significant for monograph publishing than for journal publishing.

Footnotes

⁷³ <http://jisc.ac.uk/reports/a-national-monograph-strategyroadmap>

⁷⁴ Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, and Sweden are commonly referred to as the Nordic countries. Only Denmark and Finland are part of Knowledge Exchange and therefore included in this study. Norway has actively opted in to become part of the study as well.

In terms of OA all five countries are members of Science Europe and thereby all supportive of the Science Europe principles on the transition to OA for research publications.⁷⁵ However, the countries are moving at different speeds and with different priorities towards open access and open science in general. Despite the many similarities between the countries in the region there is no formal collaboration or forum for the development of OA, however informal forums exist and flourish fueled by a variety of Nordic conferences on OA related subjects, most prominently perhaps the Munin annual conference at the UiT The Arctic University of Norway in Tromsø⁷⁶ which was held for the 11th time in 2016.

NordForsk, which is a Nordic Council of Ministers institution for research, has open access and open science as strategic goals. As such NordForsk has been particularly focused on open data and initiated workshops and a Nordic landscape study⁷⁷ on this topic.

In Denmark, Finland and Norway national lists of authorised research publication channels are used for indicators in the national performance-based research funding systems. Such a system is not in place in Sweden and Iceland. In Denmark and Norway this system has been in place for around ten years (first introduced in Norway in 2004, then in Denmark in 2009 and in 2011 in Finland).⁷⁸

There have been many reactions to the system since it influences the distribution of state funding among the research performing organisations. It is, therefore, commonly included in the strategic management of university administrators, which may have an effect on the authors' choice of publication channel especially within the humanities and social sciences. Since there are no national book publishers at the highest level of the authorised lists (the BFI lists⁷⁹) authors will have to look for international book publishers if they want their

institutions to get maximum reward for their book publishing efforts. However, in Denmark for instance, there are a number of book series attached to Danish publishers which are at the highest level. Publishing books in those series are given the same number of points as publishing with publishers at the highest level. Aiming for the high level publishers or book series, though, generally implies publishing in the English language which, all other things being equal, has a negative effect on national language book publishing. However, in Finland the four major book publishers are all at the second highest level, which is at the level of numerous international publishers. This makes the language issue less prominent.

Although Sweden is not part of this landscape study three fairly new initiatives that include OA monographs should be mentioned: Stockholm University Press, Kriterium and Lund University Press.

Stockholm University Press (SUP) is a newly established OA university press (founded in 2012) based at the Stockholm University Library. The press was established after a decision made by the Vice Chancellor of Stockholm University. Library staff and faculty members are part of the governance structure. It is a rather small enterprise with one book editor and one journals editor. All books and journals are peer reviewed. SUP is part of the Ubiquity network and uses the Ubiquity production and distribution services for its books and journals. So far SUP has published ten OA books. The BPC for publishing services for a book of 70,000 words and 20 images (roughly 200 pages) is estimated to be approximately £3,250 (+VAT). However SUP does individual calculations for each book proposal. The BPC includes all production, distribution and marketing.

Kriterium is not a publisher but a mark of quality. Formally, Kriterium is a series in which publication always occurs in collaboration with another publisher. The titles included in Kriterium are also simultaneously

published through another established channel: a university series, a commercial publisher or another academic series. These channels handle the practical aspects of publishing, while Kriterium supplies and manages the academic quality review. So far a total of six books have been published through Kriterium. The books are available online OA through the Ubiquity platform.

Kriterium is a collaborative venture between the universities of Gothenburg, Lund and Uppsala. The Swedish Research Council, Riksbankens Jubileumsfond, the National Library of Sweden and the publishers Nordic Academic Press and Makadam are involved in the project, as are the ACTA series and publication series of the universities.⁸⁰

Lund University Press (LUP) should be mentioned as a new OA publishing initiative closely attached to the faculties of humanities and theology at Lund University. The mission of LUP is to publish in book form the best scholarly output from these faculties to an international audience. Therefore the press will only publish in English. The press also acknowledges the growing international demand for OA and therefore has based its model on OA publishing. The publishing operations will be carried out in collaboration with Manchester University Press which will produce, market and sell LUP books. The books will be made available on the OAPEN platform and also as printed books in small print runs. The Royal Swedish Academy of Letters, History and Antiquities (Kungl. Vitterhetsakademien) does also publish a few OA monographs annually. On the policy side the Swedish Research Council is currently investigating whether monographs should be part of the general OA policy or not. As a strategic objective the council has proposed that from 2025 all scientific publications and artistic works resulting from research financed with public funds shall be published immediately with open access which would then include monographs.

While quite a few things are going on in Sweden in terms of monographs and OA the situation in Iceland is quite different. Iceland is a very small country with just above 320,000 inhabitants. OA is part of the national funder policy but only for journals. Currently monographs are not part of the general OA conversation and as part of this study no experiments with OA monographs have been identified in Iceland.

Footnotes

75 scienceeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/SE_POA_Pos_Statement_WEB_FINAL_20150617.pdf

76 <http://site.uit.no/muninconf/>

77 https://nordforsk.org/en/publications/publications_container/open-access-to-research-data-2013-status-issues-and-outlook/view

78 Collaboration on this issue has been proposed as an attempt to reduce costs, improve, and streamline the funding system. Moreover, collaboration would also provide higher quality and more updated information in each country and facilitate analyses comparing research output in the Nordic countries.

79 BFI = Bibliometrisk Forskningsindikator (in English that translates to bibliometric research indicator).

80 Source: kriterium.se

6.7 Country study: Denmark

Key observations:

- ▶ No policies on OA monographs
- ▶ Only few OA monograph publishing initiatives
- ▶ No national funding scheme for OA monographs in place

6.7.1 Introduction

Denmark is a fairly small country, also when it comes to scholarly publishing. Publishers of scholarly monographs are few and relatively small. There are no major multinational players in the market hence the landscape of scholarly publishing is locally based.

An important factor for scholarly publishing in Denmark is the bibliometric research indicator (BFI)⁸¹ which is part of the performance-based model for the distribution of base funding for universities in Denmark. The main purpose of the BFI is to reflect the universities' research activity. The universities are given points according to the number of publications coming from each university and those publication channels in which they are published. Every year these points make the basis for distribution of 25 per cent of new base funding to the universities that equals 5% of the total base funding. In the Danish BFI system there are two levels of publishers and book series: Level 1 and 2.⁸²

Monographs published with level 2 publishers give the most points hence those publishers are more attractive for the researchers and the university administrators since the distribution of funding depends on these points. All the Danish scholarly publishers are at level 1, however there are three Danish based book series (out of 176) at level 2. The selection of publishers and book series is done by approx. 430 researchers divided into 67 research field panels and the lists are evaluated biannually, however points are counted every year. The BFI has been much debated in Denmark since its introduction in 2009. In Norway and Finland similar systems are in place.

Table 11: Points in the Danish BFI system (updated 2012).

Publication type	Point	
	Level 1	Level 2
Monographs with publishers	5	8
Monographs in book series	5	8
Articles in series (journals and conference series)	1	3
Contributions/chapters in book series	1	3
Contributions/chapters with publishers	1	3
Doctoral dissertations		5
Patents		1

Source: <http://ufm.dk/forskning-og-innovation/statistik-og-analyser/den-bibliometriske-forskningsindikator/autoritetslister/notat-bogserier-og-konferenceserier.pdf>

6.7.2 Monograph publishing landscape in Denmark

Among the Nordic countries Denmark has the most classical university press structure for publishing monographs. It is made up of five university presses plus a couple of small imprints and a few commercial publishers with academic lists. Yet, scholarly monograph publishing is not a commercial activity since hardly any monographs are financially viable without some kind of funding. Historically there has been a variety of funding opportunities for monographs including public and private funds. However, the number of funds directly funding monographs is shrinking and for around a decade now direct publishing costs are not eligible for public research funding (through the public research councils). Combined with declining print sales the monograph is challenged as we have also seen in other countries. However, the scholarly monograph publishing landscape has not

changed much over the last decade and the number of published monographs is fairly steady. Further details about actors and the publishing landscape will be given below (6.7.4).

6.7.3 OA policy landscape in Denmark

The total number of monographs published at presses and in book series in Denmark in 2016 was 343 of which only a marginal number were OA (approx. 5%). The OA policy for public research councils and foundations from 2012⁸³ signed by all the major public funders does not include monographs, nor does the National OA strategy from 2014.⁸⁴ We have found that the private funders who often support book publishing are not preoccupied with the OA agenda, although some have expressed that they are open to the idea. None of them have reported that they specifically support OA monograph publishing. On the contrary some of the larger funds have clearly stated that they do not allow grant money to be spent on OA publishing, e.g. the Carlsberg Foundation writes in its grant FAQ: “The Carlsberg Foundation expects the host institution to provide funding for ‘open access’.”⁸⁵

The open access policy for public research councils and foundations only addresses journal articles and is based on green OA. Journal articles are to be self-archived within six to 12 months unless the researcher has good reasons for not doing so. One good reason for non-compliance, according to the policy, is that the author has acceptance from a high impact journal that does not allow self-archiving. Both the policy for public research councils and foundations and the national OA strategy are green in the sense that no extra funding has been allocated to implement the policy.

The signatories of the open access policy for public research councils and foundations are the Innovation Fund Denmark, the Danish National Research Foundation and the Danish Council for Independent Research. Some of them believe – like the private funds

– that the costs of APCs and eventually BPCs should be handled by the institutions themselves. Others think that APC/BPC payments could be taken from the grant. If monographs were to be included in the policy, the funders would generally expect monographs to be part of the same green OA strategy. However, the policy is not likely to be changed in the near future and OA monographs are not on the policy agenda currently in Denmark.

In 2014 a national OA strategy was launched. It is a green OA strategy that specifically targets journal articles and conference proceedings and explicitly excludes monographs. To monitor the implementation of the national strategy an OA Indicator⁸⁶ has been developed. The strategy aims at achieving by 2017 via digital archives – repositories – unimpeded, digital access for all to 80% of Danish peer reviewed scientific articles from Danish research institutions published in 2016 and, from 2022 onwards, unimpeded, digital access for 100% of all Danish peer reviewed scientific articles from Danish research institutions that are published from 2021 and onwards.

Footnotes

81 <http://ufm.dk/forskning-og-innovation/statistik-og-analyser/den-bibliometriske-forskningsindikator/autoritetslister/autoritetslisten-for-forlag-2016-2017-til-hjemmeside.pdf>

82 As of autumn 2017 an extra level (Level 3) will be added to the BFI list (as the most excellent channel).

83 http://ufm.dk/en/research-and-innovation/councils-and-commissions/the-danish-council-for-independent-research/open-access-policy?set_language=en&cl=en

84 ufm.dk/en/research-and-innovation/cooperation-between-research-and-innovation/open-science/open-access-to-research-publications/engelsk-version-national-strategy-for-open-access.pdf

85 <http://carlsbergfondet.dk/da/Ansoeger/Sog-Stotte/FAQ/#q23> (accessed 17-01-2017)

86 http://forskningsdatabasen.dk/en/open_access/overview (accessed 17-01-2017)

In the 2016 **Government Statement about Research and Innovation**⁸⁷ the Danish minister stresses the importance of open science. The government will increase its open science initiatives with special reference to open data and research integrity. As regards OA publications the statement refers to the open access policy for public research councils and foundations and the national strategy. As we have seen, both these documents concern peer reviewed articles and conference proceedings and specifically leave out monographs. The statement equally refrains from mentioning monographs. However, this increased and explicit focus on open science may have similar effects as those in Finland, as we shall see later.

The Danish universities support the national strategy in so far as they all have varying degrees of green OA policies. Furthermore, they are members of the National Committee on Open Access which is intended to coordinate the implementation of the National Strategy on Open Access. None of the universities have hard mandates and some only recommend green OA. All the policies relate to journal articles just as the open access policy for public research councils and foundations. The university libraries clearly support their institutions by maintaining institutional repositories, publishing platforms and by training and supporting researchers. The publishing platforms that are hosted by the libraries are mainly OJS for journals. However, Aarhus University Library has set up an OMP platform for e-books.⁸⁸ The OMP is basically used as an open e-book repository, ie. the publishing tools are not exploited. It mainly contains grey literature (around 150 titles). The library offers to add to the publication a DOI and ISBN and to upload the PDF on the platform.

Only one library – The University of Southern Denmark Library – has a publication fund (approx. 100,000 EUR annually) supporting APC and BPC payments for researchers of their university. The fund is very popular

among the scholars, however only for articles since no application has yet been made for monographs (BPC). However, they support OA for monographs through membership of Knowledge Unlatched.

In Denmark there are no library presses although Aalborg University Press is working closely with the university library in fulfilling the OA policy of the university. Aalborg University Press is the only Danish university press with a clear OA monograph publishing operation.

6.7.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in Denmark

There are eight universities in Denmark. University of Copenhagen, the largest in Denmark, has no university press. DTU, the Technical University of Denmark, has a small textbook publisher affiliated (Polyteknisk forlag). Roskilde University Press and Copenhagen Business School Press are both imprints of the textbook publisher Samfundslitteratur. Only three universities have university presses affiliated: Aalborg University Press, Aarhus University Press, and University Press of Southern Denmark. The two latter of these are the largest university presses in Denmark together with the independent scholarly publisher Museum Tusulanum Press. Each of these presses publishes between 50 and 100 new peer reviewed academic titles annually mainly in Danish and English, but occasionally in other languages too.

The Danish university presses are all organised differently in financial terms. Some get financial contributions from their mother institutions, others seek funding elsewhere, and most apply for (in particular private) funding for each monograph to be published. They all work on a not-for-profit basis but compete in market terms. The larger commercial publishers in the academic field, like Gyldendal, DJØF forlag and Samfundslitteratur, are mainly focused on textbook

publishing although they occasionally publish monographs. In addition there are a few independent, commercial but dedicated academic publishers like Vandkunstens forlag and Multivers. The latter operates an academic imprint that has an OA option. The first OA titles (a 12-volume monographic work) came out in 2016 and three new OA monographs are expected in 2017. The 2016 OA titles were funded by a private fund and published free of charge as an EPUB file with all rights reserved to the publisher.

The public research funds don't support monograph publishing in Denmark directly. In 2007 the Danish Council for Independent Research decided that researchers should include publication costs in their research budgets. However, book manuscripts tend not to be ready for publishing before long after the end of research projects. And then the grants are often already spent. This has led to an increased pressure on private funds that still financially support monograph publishing. Among the private funders there are no mandates for OA for monographs.

Although the Danish Council for Independent Research in the Humanities doesn't directly fund monograph production it values the monograph highly as a scholarly genre. The monograph allows space for thorough and elaborate arguments to evolve and this is much needed especially in the humanities. According to the council there is no contradiction between this need and the digitisation of the monograph. The council also acknowledges the need for further conversations about including monographs in the open access policy for public research councils and foundations. Having experienced recent and extensive budget cuts the council does not see itself currently to be in a position to support gold OA publishing. Already the council has a rejection rate of approx. 87% (in 2015)⁸⁹ and thus wants to prioritise its money for research activities rather than publishing. Still, the applicants are allowed to

assign some grant funding for proofreading and layout although it is not entirely clear whether there is a price cap to this.

6.7.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in Denmark

Overall, OA for monographs in Denmark is not on the agenda. As we have seen, monographs are specifically left out of the national policy discussions. Authors are generally not asking for OA for monographs and private funders don't seem to have an interest either. Libraries are only sparsely targeting the field and only very few publishers experiment with OA. As we have seen the recent development at Aalborg University is the most dedicated OA book publishing initiative and the emerging activities at Multivers may also contribute to a slow growth in the number of OA monographs in Denmark. Early experiments were performed by Museum Tusulanum Press which was part of the EU funded project OAPEN (Open Access Publishing in European Networks) which is today a foundation running a platform and services for OA books. However, the experiment was terminated when the project ended since the Danish public research funding bodies did not want to support OA books. The press then also stopped making books available OA.

Footnotes

87 <http://ufm.dk/publikationer/2016/filer/forsknings-og-innovationspolitisk-redegorelse-2016.pdf>

88 Open Monograph Press: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/omp/>

89 <http://ufm.dk/publikationer/2016/tal-om-forskning-og-innovation-2015>

Yet, as long as the scholars are not being evaluated on the basis of openness criteria, and as long as OA publishing is not being foregrounded in the BFI, it does not seem likely that the scholars will be demanding OA publishing options from the Danish scholarly presses. Therefore those presses will most certainly maintain their current business models rooted in the print age. Several interviewees have pointed to the need for new business models if OA for monographs is going to take off in Denmark. An author side demand would put pressure on the existing publishers to change models and probably new publishing initiatives would surface as we've seen in other countries. However, if this development is going to be successful and turn into sustainable solutions new funding options have to be brought forward as well.

It is very hard to predict how OA for monographs will develop in Denmark simply because so little is happening at the moment. **Bene vixit, qui bene latuit?** Well, it is definitely questionable if the monograph in the long run will prosper from its hidden life. Digitisation fits better with shorter text forms and this may mean that more authors will turn to publishing articles or contributions to edited collections. Along the same lines, some authors have argued that it is faster to get BFI points through journal article or book chapter publishing than through monograph publishing.⁹⁰ Will this affect the monograph as a scholarly genre? Will it motivate authors to become digitally more visible e.g. through OA publishing? So far there are no signs or initiatives indicating such a development in Denmark.

6.8 Country study: Finland

Key observations:

- ▶ Emerging policies on OA monographs although not yet in place
- ▶ Ongoing OA monograph publishing initiatives but at small scale
- ▶ Some funding initiatives for OA monographs are tested

6.8.1 Introduction

Open science is currently very much on the agenda in Finland. The Open Science and Research Initiative was set out in 2014 and intended to end in 2017. Many activities have been launched as part of the initiative. Although the main focus is on data and journal articles there is clearly also some interest in monographs. A few ongoing experiments in Finland illustrate this interest, e.g. at the Finnish Literature Society and Tampere University Press as we shall see below.

The national and research organisations' OA mandates – which almost all universities in Finland now have – are explicit about OA for journal articles but not for monographs. However, in a press release⁹¹ the Ministry of Education and Culture recently emphasised that open science should be all inclusive and thus encompass monographs. As such this suggests that the landscape may very well change in Finland.

6.8.2 Monograph publishing landscape in Finland

In terms of academic publishing Finland is characterised by a large number of small learned society publishers (approx. 140). Most of these societies publish very little, for instance one journal or one book series annually and only around 30 of the societies publish monographs. The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies plays a significant role for the societies as it administers government subsidies for scholarly publishing activities

and it offers a set of services for the learned societies, e.g. some distribution and sales services. In certain areas of the arts and humanities (e.g. history) commercial publishers also play a significant role for the scholarly community. The estimated number of monographs published in 2015 was just above 500 which includes doctoral dissertation monographs of which around 12% were published OA.

The federation allocates around one million euros of state funding for the publication-related activities of the societies. About two thirds of the funding is allocated to journals and one third to book publishers. The demand for this funding is high and not all applications are successful. The federation used to be financed by the Academy of Finland but since 2014 (since the launch of the Open Science Initiative) it is financed by the Ministry of Education and Culture. The federation has a board that specifically takes decisions about the applications. The societies can apply for funding of all publication costs. Should they make a profit from those publication activities that have been funded by the federation, the surplus has to be paid back to the ministry. Such decisions are based on annual reports and audits.

Of the learned society publishers the Finnish Literature Society (founded in 1831) is the largest book publisher with an annual production of around 30 peer reviewed academic titles. Publishing is partly based on public subsidies, partly dependent on sales. The Finnish Literature Society is the beacon of scholarly monograph publishing in Finland although there are a few other key players on the arena as well. As we shall see in the section below on OA publishing in Finland (6.8.4) the university libraries are actively engaging in the field of monograph publishing either directly with new university press initiatives or as part-takers in collaborative funding schemes for OA monographs.

6.8.3 OA policy landscape in Finland

The Academy of Finland is the main public funder of science and scholarship in Finland with an annual budget of more than 437 million euros. The first OA recommendations were formulated by the Ministry of Education and Culture and the Academy of Finland already in 2005 in the document **Recommendations for the promotion of open access in scientific publishing in Finland**.⁹² In July 2015 the Academy of Finland decided to turn the recommendations into a mandate that now reads:

“ We require that all academy-funded researchers see to that all publications produced with funding from the Academy of Finland are made freely available, where possible. This requirement particularly concerns peer reviewed scientific articles.”⁹³

The academy specified its mandate in May of 2017. Now it requires that all academy-funded peer-reviewed scientific articles have to be published via open access publication channels, either gold or green.⁹⁴

Footnotes

- ⁹⁰ Three articles at level 2 gives nine points whereas one monograph at level 2 gives eight points.
- ⁹¹ http://minedu.fi/artikkeli/-/asset_publisher/open-science-must-be-promoted-by-all-means-necessary?_101_INSTANCE_0R8wCyp3oebu_languageId=en_US
- ⁹² http://minedu.fi/OPM/Julkaisut/2005/avoimen_tieteellisen_julkaisutoiminnan_tyoryhman_muistio?lang=fi&extra_locale=en
- ⁹³ aka.fi/en/funding/how-to-apply/application-guidelines/open-science/
- ⁹⁴ <http://.aka.fi/en/about-us/media/press-releases/2017/academy-of-finland-refines-its-policy-on-open-access-publishing/>

This current mandate still does not include monographs but it allows for spending grant funding on OA monographs. The previous recommendations did not mention monographs either but reminded that there are other publication modes such as monographs that can be regarded, too.

Why are monographs not part of the mandate?

While acknowledging that there is a variety of scholarly outputs that ought to be included in the OA mandate the academy wanted to concentrate on peer reviewed articles because this is the main and most important publishing mode of the scientific community not only in Finland but globally and mandating OA for articles would make the most significant push for the open science agenda in Finland.

When it comes to scientific book publishing, both academic and commercial publishers are relevant in Finland for scholars who want to publish their results in the book format. Therefore, there are various business and peer-review models that need to be considered before a workable mandate on OA monographs in publishing scientific results in Finland can be demanded. Also this means that the scale of possible payments varies very much; indeed, there is currently no exact information on how much such costs might be.

Secondly, in Finland the boundaries of the scholarly monograph are somewhat blurred. On the one hand there is a strong tradition of scholarly books that are not peer reviewed while on the other hand a national peer review label exists which is used by all scholarly publishers. The Academy of Finland recommends further conversations about how to handle monographs in the mandate before including them. Extended work as part of the Open Science and Research Initiative or collaboration with academic publishers may clarify the situation.

In alignment with this position the Ministry of Education and Culture in Finland holds the opinion that publishing models and business models for OA monographs have to be tested verifiably workable before imposing national mandates for monographs.

In Finland, as in Denmark, a performance based model for distribution of public funding to universities is in operation. The model, which is called the Publication Forum⁹⁵, is very similar to the Danish BFI, although it operates four levels⁹⁶ (0-3).

6.8.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in Finland

There is a clear willingness in Finland to experiment with OA for monographs and the Ministry of Education and Culture is very supportive of this. There is agreement that experimentation is needed since book publishing in the humanities and social sciences is not yet mature for OA. Models for OA book publishing need to be tested and stabilised. One such experiment is currently being carried out. The Finnish Literature Society is running a pilot (as of August 2016) with funding from a consortium of seven Finnish libraries. The consortium, which was jointly initiated by the Finnish Literature Society and the Helsinki University Library, is called **Aleksandria** and as a first round ten Finnish language monographs will be made OA by the Finnish Literature Society.

Besides the Aleksandria consortium the Finnish Literature Society has its own OA publishing programme based on the Ubiquity platform.⁹⁷ All OA books are available as PDF and EPUB, and offered in print. To increase visibility they are indexed in international catalogues like OAPEN and DOAB. The English language **Studia Fennica** series is completely OA without any author facing charges. For the publication of any other book as OA the society charges a BPC of €6,000.⁹⁸ All of the society's scholarly series are peer reviewed.

Their ongoing experimentation with OA monograph publishing not least through the Aleksandria consortium initiative shows a proactive publisher interest in the OA developments as a constructive response to the overarching Finnish Open Science Initiative. It is the society's impression that OA monographs are particularly well suited for English language titles since OA publishing circumvents the traditional barriers for small publishers to be distributed internationally.

It is still too early to evaluate the effects of the society's OA programme but the point is exactly that experimentation is needed in the search for the optimal model. For that purpose public funding plays a crucial part.

Some Finnish libraries have also embarked on the OA publishing scene. This is the case at the University of Tampere. During 2016 their university press changed profile from a small print sales based press to a fully OA library-driven digital-only press. Fifteen monograph titles were published in 2015 and seven monographs in 2016 along with approx. 120 dissertations as a library service. The monograph titles are peer reviewed by external experts (with a rejection rate of around 40 %) and their comments and suggested corrections are left with the author to add to the monograph. The press is only staffed with three persons and there is hardly any time left for editing.

The experience of Tampere University Press reflects the perception of the Ministry of Education and Culture and the Academy of Finland that there is a huge knowledge gap to overcome and a lot of cultural barriers to pass if OA for monographs is to become the standard. Authors don't know about OA or about licences. However, they have trust in the library and therefore Tampere UP has been successful in communicating with authors about OA. Furthermore, since the press staff at Tampere UP is paid by the library the cost of publishing is very low. Tampere UP charges a basic BPC of 350 euros plus a

layout and design fee of 1,450 euros (excl. VAT) for a 300 page monograph. Of course this does not reflect the real costs since the BPC does not cover salaries and overheads. But if the OA model is meant to scale up additional funding has to be added. Several sources could come into play including the university itself since the library-driven press supports the strategy of the university.

In fact turning the press into an OA operation was based upon the OA strategy of the university. The university funding could also be established as publication funds managed by the library.

As for other small scholarly presses in the Nordic countries Tampere UP also struggles getting visibility for its monographs internationally. Therefore platforms like OAPEN and DOAB are very important to such small publishing operations. Publishers commonly emphasise the need for maintaining a high level of quality for the OA monographs and they all address the need of a quality based international platform for OA monographs. The major book publishers, though, use a designated Finnish quality label for peer reviewed publication to mark the academic monographs so that they are easy to separate from non-fiction literature.⁹⁹

Footnotes

95 <http://julkaisufoorumi.fi/en/publication-forum>

96 <http://julkaisufoorumi.fi/en/evaluations/classification-criteria>

97 <http://oa.finlit.fi>

98 <http://oa.finlit.fi/site/publish/>

99 <https://tsv.fi/en/services/label-for-peer-reviewed-scholarly-publications>

In Finland there are only a couple of commercial scholarly publishers, Gaudeamus and Vastapaino, which are in fact owned by different universities. This is partly because of the many learned society publishers and partly because Finnish scholars tend to publish with international presses when they write in English. The publisher Gaudeamus/Helsinki University Press has not published OA yet but is definitely very positive about doing so if the funding is in place. Besides funding from the Academy of Finland, the universities and university libraries the big private funds in Finland could be addressed.¹⁰⁰

The funding could simply be based on a BPC model. A publisher like Gaudeamus looks towards the UK and Sweden and notices good examples that should also be workable in Finland. Two other academic presses, Vastapaino and Turun historiallinen yhdistys, have released some backlist titles OA with long embargos and don't carry frontlist OA programmes.

Finally, most of the master theses and doctoral dissertations in Finland are made available OA in repositories at universities and university libraries (if not published by commercial publishers), e.g. <https://theseus.fi> for theses and publications of universities of applied sciences and <https://ethesis.helsinki.fi/en/tietoa-palvelusta> (at University of Helsinki). Still, ten years ago most doctoral dissertations, especially in the humanities, were published by learned societies as monographs of which the majority have now been turned into institutional OA publishing.

The Finnish performance-based publication evaluation system called Publication Forum works basically the same way as the Danish BFI system, with some minor differences. The evaluation is performed by 23 discipline-specific expert panels composed of some 200 Finnish or Finland-based scholars. The Finnish system operates four levels (the Danish system will

increase to four levels by autumn 2017) with level 3 being the highest. More importantly it differs from the Danish system by having the most important academic publishers¹⁰¹ in Finland at level 2 and the rest at either level 1 or level 0. Of the 457 publishing entities listed in the Publication Forum less than 1% is at level 2 and 7% are at level 1. The rest are at level 0. Fifteen international publishers are at level 3. Differentiating the Finnish publishers in the Publication Forum increases the motivation to publish with the level 2 Finnish publishers. The size of funding that is being distributed on the basis of the Publication Forum is 13% (which equals approx. 210 million euros) of the total state funding to the universities.

There are differences in opinion about the relation between OA and local language. However, there is general agreement among the publishers that OA works best for English language titles. There are different reasons for this. Some think that it improves distribution while some think that OA for Finnish language titles would affect the sales of those titles too heavily.

6.8.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in Finland

The Open Science Initiative in Finland definitely has pushed the agenda for OA monographs although the landscape is yet in its genesis. The initiative ends in 2017 and since we don't yet know what will then happen that makes the future of the OA monograph from a policy perspective in Finland uncertain. The experiment of the Finnish Literature Society will be interesting to follow and clearly the outcome of this experiment can be decisive for the future of OA monograph publishing and for the development of business models. Another major scholarly publisher in Finland, Gaudeamus, has expressed a very positive interest in OA publishing but also stresses the importance of developing viable business models. Since the four major scholarly Finnish publishers (among these

are the Finnish Literature Society and Gaudeamus) are at level 2 of the Publication Forum that gives hope for a successful combination of OA and financial reward for those institutions that have authors publishing with the national publishers.

6.9 Country Study: Norway

Key observations:

- ▶ No national OA strategy for monographs but it's currently being considered
- ▶ Viable OA monograph publishing initiatives in place among commercial publishers
- ▶ Significant funding set-up for OA monographs in place

6.9.1 Introduction

The Norwegian publishing landscape is quite different to the landscapes in other Nordic countries that, in turn, have fostered different approaches to OA monographs and different kinds of experimentation. The legacy publishers have been more proactively engaged in OA than anywhere else in the region and although the newly proposed guidelines for OA in Norway do not include monographs, monographs are likely to be included soon.

At a first glance this may appear somewhat surprising. The academic publishers in Norway are primarily concerned with well edited textbooks for the Norwegian market. They tend not to compete on the international market hence the amount of English language titles published is relatively small. Authors who want to be published in English typically seek international publishers who are currently not present in Norway. Unlike the rest of the Nordic countries there has been an interesting development in Norway where universities and libraries have been active in setting up publication funds to help authors choose OA when publishing through

financing of APCs and BPCs. Although these funds have slowly begun to see monograph applications the focus is still on journal articles. This also holds true for the policies. As in the neighbouring countries the focus has mainly been on journal articles.

6.9.2 Monograph publishing landscape in Norway

Of the three Nordic countries in this study Norway probably has the best integrated model for commercial book publishing and monograph publishing. In Denmark academic textbook publishers normally don't deal with scholarly monographs whereas in Norway these are more intertwined. As we shall see below under the section on OA publishing (6.9.4) Norway also has the most interesting Nordic case of commercial publishers entering the OA publishing arena. It seems probable that the explanation for this is to be found in the above mentioned composition of the Norwegian publishers.

6.9.3 OA policy landscape in Norway

In the Norwegian Research Council's principles for OA for scientific publications monographs are acknowledged but explicitly left out:

Footnotes

- 100** For instance Finnish Cultural Foundation: <https://skr.fi/en>
 - Kone Foundation: <http://koneensaatio.fi/en>, Alfred Kordelin Foundation: <http://kordelin.fi/en/frontpage>, Wihuri Foundation: <http://wihurinrahasto.fi/?lang=en>
- 101** Gaudeamus, Vastapaino, the Finnish Literature Society and the Finnish Academy of Sciences and Letters.
-

“Open access publishing is not limited to articles in scientific journals. Articles in anthologies and monographs are examples of other peer-reviewed publications that may be viewed in the context of open access. However, as journal articles are the primary form of publication both internationally and across subject areas, it will be most constructive at this time to restrict the Research Council’s open access principles to this type of publication.”¹⁰²

This view, however, seems to be changing since the recently proposed national guidelines for OA for research results recommends including monographs:

“The working group’s mandate is limited to guidelines for open access to articles. We believe this has been wise, as this is the area where the work on open access has progressed the most at the international level. However, it is important that the Government also proceed on equivalent work both for open access to research data and to scientific monographs and anthologies.”¹⁰³

One reason for the research council to exclude monographs from the policies has been lack of knowledge about the funding opportunities for researchers. The council would not like to impose tough mandates for monographs if there are no available funding mechanisms in place. This is very much in line with the approach of the Finnish Ministry for Education and Research and the Academy of Finland.

According to ROARMAP¹⁰⁴ there are eight institutional OA policies in Norway. However, none of these specifically require OA for monographs. Yet, those institutions and a number of others (altogether 18 Norwegian institutions have publication funds)¹⁰⁵ have set up publication funds intended to support those affiliated researchers that want to publish in journals where an APC is required or need funding for OA monograph publishing (BPC). The size of these funds varies greatly with the majority being quite small. However, the funds at the universities in Bergen and Tromsø are rather large, at least in a Nordic context (e.g. 600,000-700,000 euros per annum in Bergen). These funds are generally quite popular among researchers and important for the development of OA for monographs in Norway. However, funding of OA monographs also comes from a variety of other sources like foundations, commissioning entities, research grants, the Norwegian Research Council or the author’s institution.

Open access in general and in particular addressing monographs in the new Norwegian proposed national guidelines for OA to research results have led to protests from the Non-Fiction Writers and Translators Organisation in Norway. In particular they argue that the implementation of Creative Commons licences for books will mean that the current funds (derived from copyright payments, payments from library loans etc) will diminish. Those funds are considerable in size (around ten million euros are distributed annually) and offer researchers the opportunity to apply for stipends and other types of grants (for publishing, travelling etc). The system with national lists of authorised research

publication channels used for indicators in the national performance-based research funding system was first introduced in Norway (in 2004), hence the popular phrase the Norwegian model. Its proper name is the Norwegian Register for Scientific Journals, Series and Publishers or just the publishing indicator.¹⁰⁶

As a consequence of this system, researchers and especially research administrators have become increasingly aware of the need to increase the number of publications published at the highest level of the publishing indicator. According to an independent evaluation¹⁰⁷ in 2014 the introduction of the publishing indicator does not seem to have influenced the publishing patterns among scholars. Monographs are still being published and scholars still write in their national language. However, researchers and research administrators have broadly argued that the model would favour those disciplines where the journal article is the most commonly used channel for scholarly output leaving the monograph less attractive as a publication channel. This argument has also been raised in several interviews during this landscape study. Still, it was not substantiated by the evaluation.

6.9.4 OA monograph publishing landscape in Norway

Scandinavian University Press and Cappelen Damm are the main legacy publishers that have entered the OA monograph arena in Norway. Other major textbook publishers in Norway like Fagbokforlaget and Gyldendal Akademisk, have not engaged themselves in OA activities. Neither have two other smaller academic presses, NOVUS and Scandinavian Academic Press/Spartacus. There are a few library-driven OA publishing services in Norway (UiT The Arctic University of Norway (Tromsø), University of Oslo, Norwegian University of Science and Technology and University of Bergen) but these are primarily running journal services. However, experiments with OA monograph publishing have been carried out at the University of Bergen using the OJS software.¹⁰⁸ They support one book series called Bergen Language and Linguistic Studies (BeLLS) and another book series is under way to be

published with technical support only from the library. BeLLS is an OA peer reviewed electronic only book series, started in 2009 by two scholars which aims at publishing original research on language and linguistics. So far seven books have been published in this series.

Norway does not have a tradition of traditional university presses although the current academic and commercial publisher Scandinavian University Press (Universitetsforlaget in Norwegian) in Oslo used to be a common endeavour of the Norwegian universities until sometime in the 1990s when the press's international journals were sold to Taylor & Francis. Scandinavian University Press is a large press compared to other academic publishers in the Nordic countries with a comprehensive journal portfolio comprising 60 journals of which 27 are OA and an extensive book programme of around 140 new titles annually (mainly textbooks). Scandinavian University Press has set up an OA publishing programme intended for highly academic monographs with very limited commercial potential. Due to the Norwegian publication funds that are quite common such monographs get a chance of being published on the basis of the same standard of peer review as other academic publications. Scandinavian

Footnotes

102 http://forskingsradet.no/en/Article/Open_access_to_publications/1254008525829?lang=en (accessed 15-02-2017).

103 <http://cristin.no/english/open-access-eng/national-guidelines-for-open-access-to-research-re/national-guidelines-for-open-access-to-research-results.pdf> (accessed 15-02-2017).

104 <http://roarmap.eprints.org> (accessed 15-02-2017).

105 openaccess.no/Finansiering/publiseringfond/

106 https://dbh.nsd.uib.no/publiseringsskanaler/Forside.action;jsessionid=1RDspBSRKKuS8jIBZ6r2Or2e.undefined?request_locale=en

107 http://uhr.no/documents/evaluering_af_den_norske_publiceringsindikator.pdf

108 Open Monograph Press: <https://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs>

University Press is using a proprietary platform for its OA monographs called Idunn¹⁰⁹ which was originally developed for the journal portfolio.

Another major commercial publisher in Norway, Cappelen Damm, has also introduced an OA branch as part of its academic publishing called Nordic Open Access Scholarly Publishing (NOASP). Cappelen Damm Academic is, like Scandinavian University Press, mainly a textbook publisher with an annual output of around 100 titles. With the OA option the publisher has opened up new publication options for the scholars. For instance it becomes possible to publish highly academic titles within narrow subjects, and in the Norwegian language, too. NOASP publishes the OA titles in a variety of formats (PDF, EPUB, HTML, XML) and expects no sales from the OA monographs (there is no print-on-demand service attached although the publisher very often supplies authors with small print runs which is done using the state-of-the-art print technology). NOASP uses the Open Monograph Press software for publishing its OA catalogue.

Both publishers' OA models are based on BPCs. The level of the BPC is based on individual calculations and will therefore differ significantly depending on for instance the complexity and length of the book. Both publishers make the BPC cover the total publication costs, i.e. the model is sustainable without sales and without the presses losing money.

Founded in 2007 Co-Action Publishing was a fully OA scholarly publisher of journals and books based in Norway. However, their book list only counted two publications. In 2017 Co-Action was acquired by Taylor & Francis.

As in other countries it is often stressed in the Norwegian context that the publishing of monographs OA must not compromise the quality of the content. The same high standards for peer review must prevail and in fact more effort is often spent on ensuring rigorous peer review procedures for the OA titles to avoid the common misunderstanding among authors that OA titles are of

lesser quality than non-OA titles. Moreover, to receive support from the publication funds it is necessary that the book is published by a publication channel (publisher) on level 1 or 2 of the publishing indicator.

6.9.5 The future of OA monograph publishing in Norway

Those Norwegian publishers that have engaged with OA monograph publishing have had to invest quite a lot of resources informing authors about open licences and about what OA is and is not. Slowly, new models of OA monograph publishing are emerging and the number of published titles is growing. The 18 existing publication funds are important sources of funding but it is believed that their role will decrease in the future as the importance of other sources will rise. In particular it is expected that author institutions will play a more prominent role as direct funders in the future. The institutionally based publication funds are typically based on rather short-term decisions (e.g. up to three years). This is a short horizon to work against. Basing business models on these sources of funding alone would therefore make the publishers too vulnerable to changes in institutional policies and practices. However, the signals in the proposed national guidelines for OA to research results suggest that there will be a policy backup for upholding some kind of funding mechanism and thus a willingness to explore funding solutions that can ensure sustainable solutions. But just as important is the increase in faculty level author support, i.e. institutions that fund their authors.

Despite the negative response to OA from the Non-Fiction Writers and Translators Organisation the attitude at both the national and the institutional level seems to be positive towards engaging into more concrete conversations about how to handle and support OA monograph publishing in Norway. In fact, such conversations are generally expected to accelerate within the next couple of years.

Footnotes

109 <https://idunn.no/?languageId=2>

Part three

3

7. Notable initiatives and projects

We struggled with the title of this section because at first we were calling it “good practices”. However, we soon found that applying any single set of criteria to deem a practice as good was fraught with difficulties. Do we judge an innovation by its ability to keep costs down, to succeed in dissemination, to be best in peer review, to be able to scale, or simply to achieve its remit – whether this be modest or bold?

Once we began thinking of interesting examples of innovation we found a plethora of initiatives from which all interested in OA and monographs can learn. We discuss only a few here by way of illustration. Others are woven into the country studies. Some are discussed more than once. We apologise if we have omitted any that should have been included. There are simply too many initiatives – which is in itself promising. Not all will succeed, but they all pave the way to more OA monographs.

7.1 Vignettes

We have written the examples as small vignettes around 14 themes.

7.1.1 Library-university press collaboration

[UCL Press \(UK\)](#)

UCL Press is the largest open access university press in the UK, publishing in 2017 50 new books and several journals. Spearheaded by Paul Ayres, UCL’s librarian, and managed by Lara Speicher, it aims to make the best use of technology and is grounded in the open science/open scholarship agenda. It publishes UCL scholars without levying a BPC charge, but does so when publishing non-UCL scholars. It has sufficient funding to support experimental modes of publishing while applying all the quality assurance processes expected of traditional presses. UCL Press is being carefully watched as it grows and moves to a business model that relies on multiple sources of funding. It has already been successful in gaining library support through the Knowledge Unlatched programme.

[Aalborg University Press \(Denmark\)](#)

At Aalborg University (AAU) a new collaboration was initiated between the library and the press. The press was established in 1978 just four years after the university itself and it was mainly established as a publication channel for AAU researchers. Today this still holds true although the press also publishes a number of non-AAU researchers. All books are peer reviewed and signed-off by a publishing committee. In 2012 the library and the press began experimenting with OA. Inspired by the early findings of the Canadian Athabasca University Press the publishing committee decided to introduce an OA option for its authors. This was done to increase the visibility and impact of the books that otherwise were only published in very small print runs with marginal sales and hardly any royalties for authors. All OA editions are published in the library’s CRIS system (PURE). Using PURE as the platform/repository for OA books has the advantage that authors need to register their publications in PURE anyway.

There has been an annual increase in the amount of OA books published by AAU press and the author demand for OA is increasing too. OA books are treated similarly to non-OA books with regards to peer review and editorial assistance (in general the press does not offer editorial assistance but relies on the authors to ensure the quality of the manuscript – there are only 2.5 FTE attached to the press). The business model is based on a BPC calculated on a book by book basis. This model also exists for non-OA books where an author/author’s institution typically will be charged 5,000 euros per book (incl. print of approx. 300 copies). The services that the library offers in terms of depositing and hosting books in PURE is carried out free of charge for the press.

[University of Huddersfield Press \(UK\)](#)

University of Huddersfield Press was established in 2007 and then re-launched as an open access press in 2010, then working at the university library and now at Jisc. It aims to be an outlet for early career researchers and to

act as an outlet for niche and interdisciplinary research. It does not aim to replace traditional publishing. On a very small budget the press is able to publish a dozen journals, and 15 books. In 2016/17 it received about a quarter of its budget from authors and outside funders. The rest is covered by the university which recognises the reputational benefits. It uses Eprints as its repository. Huddersfield and UCL are two of a dozen new UK university presses. For more information see UK country chapter in this report.

[Aarhus University Library \(Denmark\)](#)

Aarhus University Library set up the AU Library Scholarly Publishing Service which is an OMP platform for e-books where researchers and staff at Aarhus University can publish books, PhD theses, working papers etc free of charge. The OMP is basically used as an open e-book repository, ie the publishing tools are not exploited. The platform is fully user-driven and AU Library takes no responsibility in terms of the content. The library only makes the platform available and maintains it technically. Any content uploaded to the platform must be open access.

[Lapland University Press \(Finland\)](#)

Lapland University Press is a unit of the Lapland University. As such the press receives financial support from the university although not enough to cover all its costs. Revenues come from sales of printed books, since the press, usually, does not charge BPCs for its OA editions. The press takes care of peer review, layout, editing and distribution.

[Presses Universitaire Francois Rabelais \(France\)](#)

PUFR was established in 2002. It was nearly ten years ago that the University of Tours (which owns PUFR) discovered that the press was not performing as well as it had hoped. It aimed to reduce or even eliminate its subsidies. To that end the university worked with the press to professionalise and diversify the press. It is growing from 20 books a year to 35 in 2017 and

while it accepts authors from everywhere it has aligned its mission to the university's. It now publishes monographs, textbooks and general books for the public. The textbook side of the business is proving to be especially lucrative and cross-subsidises the monograph programme. PUFR is very clear in its mind which types of books will benefit from going OA and in which formats to publish. It expects revenue from the OpenEdition model to increase over time.

7.1.2 New university press-traditional press collaboration

There are many new collaborations, though we have only written about two below.

[Leuven-Leiden University Press \(Netherlands\)](#)

Leiden University Press was re-established by Leiden University in two steps, first as an imprint of AUP, and in 2010 as a university press based in the university library, with a fixed annual subsidy to cover part of its costs. LUP works with Leuven University Press in Belgium for the production of its books, this includes the whole process from editing to printing. LUP does its own acquisition, peer review, marketing and sales. The collaboration with Leuven means BPCs are based on the production costs and are calculated separately for every publication. The collaboration enables Leiden to make use of the services of an established UP, without the up front costs connected to in-house personnel, and creates economies of scale for Leuven UP.

[Lund University Press-Manchester University Press \(Sweden\)](#)

The establishment of Lund University Press was spearheaded by Marianne Thormählen after an independent research evaluation concluded that Lund research in the humanities and theology should be better recognised internationally. To this end Thormählen and her colleagues devised the new Lund University Press in such a way that it combined the best of the old and new ways of publishing. Books will be

published in English and in open access from the start. Having officially opened its doors in 2015, the first books will be published in 2018. While peer review remains with Lund UP all other publishing functions have been subcontracted to Manchester University Press. Funding for the start-up phase came first from the Vice-Chancellor's budget, but is now carried by the joint faculties of humanities and theology. Lund UP expects to sell other formats through the Manchester University press channels and also encourage donations from foundations and individuals.

7.1.3 Including monographs in OA policies and moving towards mandates

[Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture](#)

The Ministry of Education and Culture in Finland has stated that open access should be the norm for all peer reviewed scholarly output. Although they have preliminary focused on journal articles, monographs are in principle part of the same thinking and policy. Guided by good examples and practices this thinking could eventually turn into mandates for monographs, too.

[HEFCE \(UK\)](#)

The Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) is leading the way in attempting to achieve mandated OA for most books and book chapters to be a requirement to the REF exercise that allocates state funding to all universities in the UK. At present it is anticipated that this will be achieved by the mid 20's REF and could potentially impact several thousands of books. For more information see the UK country study in this report.

7.1.4 Allowing monograph BPCs to be paid for from general OA publication funds

[University of Southern Denmark and several Norwegian universities](#)

University of Southern Denmark, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, University of Bergen and other Norwegian institutional funds have opened their funds for BPCs without a price cap. This gives authors, publishers and the funders themselves room for experimentation with BPC funding and OA monographs in general.

7.1.5 Co-ordinated approach to OA monographs

[HEFCE, UUK, Jisc \(UK\)](#)

HEFCE and Jisc have recognised the need to tread carefully as the prospect of mandating OA for monographs comes closer. To this end several committees have been established to do more work on how to achieve this goal without destabilising publishing to such an extent that publishers move out of monograph publishing and authors find it more difficult to get published. Involving all stakeholders has been a priority in the UK. At present Universities UK (UUK), the representative organisation for the UK's universities, has been tasked with consolidating perspectives and developing a roadmap for the future. For more information on the issues confronting UUK see the UK country study in this report.

[Wellcome \(UK\)](#)

The Wellcome Trust has been in the vanguard of open access for many years. A few years ago it developed an OA programme for books and book chapters written by authors whose research they had supported. On the whole this is restricted to medicine and in particular medical history and ethics. Most of the output from Wellcome funded projects is in the form of articles. Nevertheless, the model proposed is important as it is a benchmark for others.

The main difference at the moment is that while articles are to be licensed as CC BY, books and book chapters may take a more restricted form of licensing such as CC BY-NC or C-C-BY-NC-ND (and technically CC BY-ND, although this is rarely used). Wellcome have a strong preference for CC BY even for books, but recognise that the publishing industry is not ready for this as it would allow others to sell, for instance, printed books, the rights of which both publisher and author would like to restrict to the originating publisher. ND is often requested by the author in order to control, for instance, the quality of translations. Neither ND nor NC mean that others can't make translations or commercial use of the material, but rather that this is controlled by the rights holder to the benefit of the author and publisher. Wellcome has also worked with publishers to develop standards of compliance.

[Guides for OA monograph publishing](#)

A number of stakeholders have developed guides for OA monograph publishing. Wellcome produced a guide for publishers, to help them comply with funder requirements. Jisc developed a guide for OA monographs directed at humanities and social sciences authors, as part of the OAPEN-UK project. And Jisc/OAPEN ran a project investigating centralised OA monograph services, which resulted in two short guides, one on metadata for OA monographs, and one on information publishers should make available on their website. A number of people have suggested extending these guides to develop a comprehensive toolkit for OA book publishers.

7.1.6 Supporting investigation and experimentation [OAPEN-UK and other pilots \(Netherlands and Switzerland\)](#)

OAPEN worked with stakeholders in different countries to explore OA book publishing. OAPEN-NL was conducted with support from NWO, OAPEN-UK was managed by Jisc and funded by Jisc and AHRC, and OAPEN-CH is an ongoing project, led and funded by

SNSF. Although these pilots were different in each country, they all included a practical experiment to publish a number of OA books in collaboration with publishers, combined with research into the effects of OA on usage and sales. In the Netherlands, the pilot also included a study into the costs of OA books, and in the UK, the pilot was accompanied by an extensive research project (with Research Information Network [RIN]) among all stakeholders to explore the issues around OA monographs. In each case, these pilot projects formed a starting point for stakeholders to collaboratively address the challenges around OA for monographs.

7.1.7 Collaborative funding

[Finnish Literature Society \(Finland\)](#)

When the Finnish Literature Society initially received a grant from the Jane and Aatos Erkko Foundation for the "Open science and cultural heritage" project, part of this grant was used to help setting up an open access publishing programme based on the Ubiquity platform. Then the Finnish Literature Society together with the Helsinki University Library initiated an OA funding membership scheme (similar to Knowledge Unlatched, however much smaller and only in a Finnish context) which initially included seven Finnish libraries as a consortium called Aleksandria. As a first round the consortium has funded ten Finnish language titles to be published OA by the Finnish Literature Society. The package of these ten books consists of three books to be published in 2017 and seven backlist books. All books will be licensed under a Creative Commons licence, provided with a permanent identifier (DOI), uploaded to the society's publication platform, made available in PDF and EPUB-format, and uploaded to OAPEN Library and the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB). For the next round it is hoped that more publishers and libraries will be included in the consortium.

Knowledge Unlatched (Germany)

It has been said that Knowledge Unlatched is currently the largest funder of Open Access books anywhere, yet it does not have funds of its own. It is in effect a crowd-sourcing mechanism that invites publishers to submit monographs that are then vetted by a library selection committee. Once a shortlist is compiled the books are offered to libraries that are then invited to pledge their support for the packages. If enough libraries participate then the title fee (similar to a BPC) is paid to the publishers to “unlatch” the books – i.e. make them open access. Knowledge Unlatched ensures full MARC records and hosting on OAPEN and HathiTrust platforms. For more information about Knowledge Unlatched see Chapter 3 of this report.

7.1.8 Public funding of an OA platform

OpenEdition (France)

As early as 1999 Marin Dacos developed a platform for journals while working on his PhD at the University of Avignon. Out of this he began Revues.org which is now part of OpenEdition. Until 2007 small amounts of funding came from a variety of sources. After that other institutions; Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), Ecole des Haute Etude de Sciences Sociales (EHESS) and Aix-Marseille University supported the endeavour with it becoming a Unite Mixte de Services (UNS) that provides national support for national projects through a funding model that draws from the resources of a handful of institutions. In 2013 OpenEdition received significant funding from the state (part of its investment plan “Programme Investissements d’Avenir”) to develop OpenEdition Books with its freemium model and to expand beyond France. From 2016 OpenEdition has become a national infrastructure, with direct funding coming from the state, in addition to funding from the supporting institutions and sales of services.

7.1.9 Supporting infrastructure development to set up OA book publisher

DFG (Heidelberg, LSP)

DFG (Deutsches Forschungsgemeinschaft) funded two infrastructure projects, which helped to establish two new OA presses: Language Science Press and Heidelberg University Publishing. The knowledge gained by both these presses (including infrastructure, workflow, publication and business models), may be valuable when considering similar projects in other countries or other disciplines.

7.1.10 Building a disciplinary academic community around a new publishing venture

Language Science Press (Germany)

LSP is a pure OA, academic-led publisher. LSP has a discipline specific approach and was set up as a community enterprise, with currently 800 supporters from around the world. This approach has helped LSP to overcome one of the main barriers that new entrants have to face: to gain credibility among the community and attract authors.

BeLLS (Norway)

Bergen Language and Linguistic Studies (BeLLS) is an OA peer reviewed electronic-only book series, started in 2009 by two scholars which aims at publishing original research on language and linguistics. So far seven books have been published in this series. The books are published with technical support by the University of Bergen Library, which uses the OJS platform for this.

7.1.11 Example(s) of clear governance structure around new press

Stockholm University Press (Sweden)

Stockholm University Press (SUP) is a newly established OA university press (founded in 2012) based at the Stockholm University Library. The press was established after a decision made by the Vice Chancellor of Stockholm University. Both library staff and faculty members are part of the governance structure. It is a

rather small enterprise with one book editor and one journals editor. All books and journals are peer reviewed. SUP is part of the Ubiquity network and uses the Ubiquity production and distribution services for its books and journals.

7.1.12 Collaboration on developing standards in and sharing of services for infrastructure

[OPERAS/HIRMEOS \(Europe\)](#)

OPERAS is a new initiative of OpenEdition, for a coordinated approach to open science in the humanities and social sciences. Currently consisting of 20 members in ten countries, the main objectives are: to adopt common standards; share R&D; identify and adopt best practices; assess sustainable economic models; advocate for OA in HSS; and to provide seamless services at European level.

HIRMEOS is one of the H2020 projects being conducted by a number of OPERAS partners. The project aims to implement a number of shared services on various OA book platforms, thereby making these services available to publishers all over Europe.

7.1.13 Joint label to support quality assurance and dissemination

[Kriterium \(Sweden\)](#)

Kriterium is a series in which publication always occurs in collaboration with another publisher. The titles included in Kriterium are also simultaneously published through another established channel: a university series, a commercial publisher or another academic series. These channels handle the practical aspects of publishing, while Kriterium supplies and manages the academic quality review.

[Finnish peer review label \(Finland\)](#)

In Finland a peer review label was introduced in 2014. A steering group - comprising representatives from the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies, Ministry of Education and Culture as well as professionals from

the publishing sector - is responsible for the development of the label.

7.1.14 OA fund for specific aspects or types of monographs

Both of the examples below demonstrate the role that funders can play in developing standards and processes that foster the maintenance of quality and publishing standards for OA.

[FWF \(Austria\)](#)

FWF's funding programme for stand-alone publications was launched in 2009, after mandating OA for all scholarly publications in 2008. The programme funds OA charges for both innovative formats (web-based, enriched with multimedia, apps, databases, etc) and conventional formats (such as books). The funding programme for books is modular, with a basic module to cover costs for gold OA and other modules to cover costs of editorial support (including foreign language editing) and of additional costs (for higher amount of pages, for illustrations, etc). There is a separate, discretionary fund for books that would benefit from an English language edition and international dissemination. FWF ensures that all books are peer reviewed, either through the application procedure, or through a certification process involving detailed requirements for participating publishers (see country study for further details).

[Wellcome \(UK\)](#)

We have discussed the Wellcome Trust elsewhere (and above under theme 5), but mention it here as well under this heading because of its focus around life sciences and, in the case of books, a particular emphasis on the research it funds into the history of medicine.

8. Information gaps and stakeholder recommendations

The following is a short list of information gaps that could be usefully filled with further research so as to enable monitoring of progress and better understanding of the key issues. Some of these gaps are also identified in the literature review in Chapter 9, where they are presented under 9.4 (Conclusions).

A longer list of recommendations follows on, and these are grouped under stakeholder headings rather than issues. Although there are obvious areas that can be identified by specific stakeholders we also encourage cross-stakeholder information sharing and action.

8.1 Information gaps

- ▶ Monograph output in numbers, geographically, by type, by openness (and compared with volume and language of closed books)
- ▶ Output of OA books (not all are available through DOAB)
- ▶ Compliance with OA requirements (funders, libraries, publishers) especially more understanding of how these are communicated and conveyed
- ▶ Usage data (policies, aggregation, standardisation) and the needs of the various stakeholders
- ▶ Transparency around OA charges
- ▶ Deeper analysis of publishing costs on a country by country basis
- ▶ Quality assurance and service levels for books
- ▶ Self-archiving policies for books

8.2 Recommendations

We have below specific recommendations for each of the key stakeholder categories. The recommendations for Knowledge Exchange can be found in Chapter 4 and in the executive summary.

In many ways the separation into stakeholder groups is artificial in that all are involved in the research dissemination eco-system. When it comes to fulfilling stakeholders' prime agendas they may choose to leave the complex monograph publishing challenge for another day. However, we believe that the "funding problem" is not one of absolute scarcity of money, but rather the employment of inefficient models. By working together stakeholders can bring down the costs per book and still retain quality and all the other positive features of monograph publishing.

8.2.1 Funders

These are the bodies that provide funding for research and the institutions in which the research is conducted – whether public or private - and who may or may not be the source of funds for research dissemination. However, to date funders are the most important influencers and making OA a condition of grant-making will be key to making OA a success:

- ▶ Funders should consider including monographs in their OA policies and also whether to move to mandating OA
- ▶ Do more work to promote understanding of OA benefits to authors
- ▶ Promote an understanding of how OA would support the standing of HSS

- ▶ Encourage and support more experimentation with different OA models. Become a partner with publishers and libraries in finding novel solutions. There is no master plan at this stage for the transition to OA books and research shows that having one may not be the best way forward. One area to explore is how the OA2020 initiative might be applied to monographs
 - ▶ Collaborative solutions should be encouraged
 - ▶ Not all the policies made for journals fit monographs; more funders should be thinking about what would work for books
 - ▶ Monographs need to be part of open science, and open science statements and policies need to acknowledge different formats and disciplines. Funders have a role in underscoring this
 - ▶ Make more transparent what grant committees are looking for with regards to dissemination when reviewing applications
 - ▶ Funders should share information amongst themselves (be they private or public) on how to achieve OA for monographs
 - ▶ Streamline compliance and requirements in the way BPCs are administered and monitored between funders
- 8.2.2 Policy makers**
- Policy makers have been reluctant to tackle the monograph publishing issue. It is seen as difficult and with little reward. However, to maintain the flow of knowledge in HSS subjects especially the long-form publication (whether solely text or now multimedia) is still important to the scholars and readers themselves:
- ▶ Be aware everywhere of the importance of monographs
 - ▶ Work with funders at all levels to develop cost effective ways of enabling monographs to be published OA
 - ▶ Politically address issues of copyright, accessibility and re-usability with regards to the monograph
 - ▶ Explore moving from “encouraging” to mandating OA for books and book chapters
- 8.2.3 Authors**
- Authors are obviously the most diverse stakeholder group and hold the widest range of views on the benefits (or otherwise) of OA. They should be entitled to full representation with full understanding of OA. To this end we feel that, while there is much work to be done, we now have a collection of authors far and wide who have experienced the benefits to them when they’ve published in OA:
- ▶ Develop a platform where authors can post the benefits of going OA (to include case studies)
 - ▶ Help raise awareness among authors through various professional bodies
 - ▶ Campaign through blogs etc. that explain the merits and address the misconceptions around OA books in simple terms, “myth-cracking” the assumption that OA books must be inferior products

8.2.4 University administrators

Individual country circumstances differ, of course, but across the board universities are asking for and being asked for greater evidence of impact. Especially for HSS subjects this is better gauged by employing methods that are not restricted to the reading of only a few books found in wealthy libraries. Our country studies touch on these issues in greater depth:

- ▶ Address issues around the reward system (acknowledge value of validation and impact of OA)
- ▶ Make more transparent what tenure committees are looking at when reviewing applications
- ▶ Consider the Rentier solution: “it is only counted if it is in my (or other OA) repository”
- ▶ Look into how OA supports HSS.

8.2.5 Publishers

Moving to OA for monographs may become part of a transition where publishing of monographs becomes more of a service offer with funders, institutions and authors having more of a say about how monographs get published. The following is just a short list of suggestions that can help move this forward:

- ▶ Not all monographs are equal, and different monographs require different service levels for different purposes

- ▶ Be transparent about services and pricing
- ▶ Make sure information of different formats and pricing is presented clearly in one place
- ▶ Publishers should use a common set of metadata
- ▶ List books in discovery systems (such as DOAB and elsewhere)
- ▶ Make backlist books that have little commercial potential life available OA retroactively

8.2.6 Libraries

Libraries have a very important role to play. Much of the funding for acquisitions can be more progressively applied to funding BPCs, whether to authors from institutions, or through crowd-sourcing models:

- ▶ Libraries should consider taking the initiative to establish a collaborative programme to reserve an increasing percentage of acquisitions budget for OA books and perhaps infrastructure services (as recommended by the Max Planck Society)
- ▶ Consider policy options that foster OA for monographs
- ▶ Libraries should include OA content, (including monographs) in their discovery systems (making use of DOAB)

- ▶ OA working groups should include various departments that are affected by OA (e.g. licensing, acquisition, and accounting staff)
- ▶ Libraries should take an integrated approach to content management and look at OA licensing and acquisitions in a coordinated manner
- ▶ Identify key infrastructure services to support OA book publishing
- ▶ Explore where new workflows can bring cost savings
- ▶ Develop business and governance models to sustain key infrastructures

8.2.7 Infrastructure services

These services are integral to the delivery of OA content. They consist of a mix of services stemming from the print world, services developed for e-publishing and services specifically developed for OA content and OA books. In streamlining workflows there can be considerable savings to the overall cost of publishing. They are generally supported by library and publisher budgets:

8.2.8 Conclusion

In short we recommend deeper understanding of the differences between countries while promoting policies and business models that can be adopted across countries. Europe is a beacon in this space and others will follow.

Part four
Appendices

4

9. Literature review

Open access monographs in the humanities and social sciences

By Thor Rydin

This literature review serves to locate knowledge and knowledge gaps with regard to OA monograph publishing along the following lines:

- ▶ The general economic models described in the literature for OA monograph publishing
- ▶ The stakeholders involved, as well as their respective kinds of policy options described in the literature
- ▶ The effects of the respective OA policies on the actual monograph in terms of e.g. quality, dissemination, sales, citation, and (academic) impact.

The review attempts to include all the latest studies on OA monograph publishing models and relevant developments therein. In order to create an overview, the review is subdivided into two sections. The first section concerns general business models for OA publishing, identifies and discusses all stakeholders and lists a number of their individual policy options. The second section deals with the effect such policy choices may have on the monograph and on the publishing mechanism as a whole.

In this review “monograph” is defined as follows: a long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, and extended to also include peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.

9.1 Model, stakeholders and policy

9.1.1 OA business models

Generally publishers, both OA and non-OA, add value to an author’s work at two different stages: production and consumption. The former concerns editorial activities, design, peer review etc; the latter concerns activities such as branding, marketing and distribution (Crossick 2015a: 54-55). Eve (2014: 113-136) has identified four business models that allow OA publishers to finance and profit from these activities: (1) book processing charges, (2) print subsidies, (3) institutional subsidies, and (4) freemium. For other business model overviews see e.g. the Oberlin Group study (2013: 17-20), Morrison’s **Economics of Scholarly Communication Transition** (2013), Esposito’s **The Open Access Monograph (2016)**, Moore’s **Pasteur4OA Briefing Paper: Open Access Monographs** (2016), and the Science Europe study by Kita, Duchange and Ponsati (2016: 15). These alternative typologies are all more or less compatible with Eve’s typology discussed below. See Hacker and Carrao (2017: 85-87) for a number of considerations new publishers may have putting together their OA business models.

The BPC model relies on a book processing charge to cover the expenses of producing OA material, either in combination with additional profit margins, or not. As such, the BPC model is, in fact, a reversal of the traditional toll-access (TA) models. In the conventional TA models, generally, authors receive royalties from the publisher (though minimal for monographs) and obtain prestige from the scientific community for externally funded work, whilst the publisher sells the monograph(s) to (funded) libraries and other academics. In BPC models, on the other hand, (usually) external funders pay publishers for an OA publication of the respective piece of work in the name of the author,

thus often omitting author royalties and purchase funding. In this case, publishers are no longer paid for the micro-monopoly in the particular piece of literature, but, rather, for their more competitive, non-monopoly production and dissemination services.

Martin Eve (2014: 130-135) also distinguishes three non-BPC business models for OA monograph publishing: print subsidy, institutional subsidy and freemium. In such non-BPC models various elements of the production and processing costs remain to be covered by payments from purchasing parties. A concise overview of Eve's models is offered below. It is important to keep in mind that all models could, at least theoretically, be complemented by certain BPC elements.

- ▶ In print subsidy models, publishers provide OA for their monographs “based upon a belief in continuing desire for the features of print that are currently hard to replicate in an online environment” (Eve 2014: 131). A study by OAPEN-NL (Ferwerda et al. 2013: 4) has shown evidence for this relation with regard to monographs. Still, according to Eve, it is not unlikely that OA may boost sales, as monograph readers continue to prefer physical copies. Eve (2014: 117) has, however, tentatively raised a potential OA sales impediment, yet to be properly explored in the literature: conventional readers may become suspicious of a monograph's quality when the publisher offers OA
- ▶ In institutional subsidy models uncertainties and concerns regarding the relation between OA and physical monograph sales are a feature of institutional subsidies. These subsidies may consist in a contractual promise by a number of institutions to purchase an OA monograph prior to its production. Such institutions could be universities that provide central funding through various departments or

other funding bodies that provide block grants to universities.¹¹⁰ This model, as well as the print subsidy model, suffers from a free-rider problem. Still, partnership in such cooperation does pay off in terms of prestige and subsequent strategic benefits (Eve 2014: 75)

- ▶ In so-called freemium models, publishers offer OA versions of restricted quality relative to the non-OA version. Readers then continue to be encouraged to purchase the monograph, whilst the publishers benefit from the monograph's increased exposure. The limitations are, however, obvious: depending on the nature of the restrictions (e.g. citing restrictions) the access crisis and, thus, price crisis are still not solved

Each of these OA models, hybrid or not, can be profitable. In the cases of both BPC and non-BPC, publishers may charge profitable payments for their respective services, whilst publishing OA material.

9.2 Costs of OA publications and the question of pricing

The OAPEN-NL Final Report (Ferwerda et al. 2013: 43) found costs for OA monographs in The Netherlands (both in Dutch and in English) to range roughly from €5,000 to €10,000. A later study commissioned by Ithaka S+R and carried out by Maron, Mulhern, Rossman and Schmelzinger (2016: 4) compiled a similar, detailed report “on the costs of producing the first digital copy of a ‘high quality digital monograph’”. Maron et al. (ibid: 21) broke down OA monograph production costs into five debit entries – acquisitions, manuscript editorial labour, production, design and marketing – so as to investigate the average basic cost for the production of a monograph by university presses, varying by discipline. “Basic costs” here include “just staff and non-staff expenses directly incurred when producing the book” (ibid: 16), and

thus leave out costs to do with e.g. royalties and press-level overhead costs. See table below for their results.

Table 12: The average basic production cost for monographs per discipline, together with the respective standard deviation and sample size

Discipline	Mean	Standard Deviation	Number
American studies	\$29,354.65	11,041.88	26
Anthropology	\$21,696.95	6,911.64	14
Art/architecture	\$39,654.71	14,912.79	16
Archaeology	\$30,528.80	26,850.42	12
Area studies	\$28,373.74	10,081.88	34
Arts/film	\$31,317.31	13,034.35	26
History	\$28,996.74	10,163.60	66
Humanities	\$28,598.06	13,990.45	76
Religion	\$19,427.28	5,993.97	31
Science	\$36,603.63	10,722.11	22
Social science	\$26,819.29	10,332.65	54

Source: Maron et al. 2016: 35

The differences between the findings of the OAPEN-NL final report (Ferwerda et al. 2013) and Maron et al. (2016) could be connected to a number of parameters: different definitions of costs, inclusion of data from different publisher types, national market differences, and available licence options. Maron et al. (ibid: 13-14), for one, considered exclusively US university presses producing Anglophone monographs. OAPEN-NL (Ferwerda et al. 2013: 87-88), on the other hand considered Dutch publishers of various kinds producing both English and Dutch monographs. In the PASTEUR4OA briefing paper by Moore (2016) it has been suggested that the figures presented in the Ithaka S+R report findings do not reflect the production costs

accurately, considering these numbers include (significant) profit margins. Moore's paper supports this claim by referring to known monograph production costs from Open Book Publishers, and alternative cost structures at Open Humanities Press.

In support of this claim, OA monograph costs later found by Gatti and Mierowsky (2016: 458) lie closer to those found by OAPEN-NL, at an average of \$8,333 per monograph. In a study funded by the Mellon Foundation, Walters and Hilton (2015: 47-48), on the other hand, found monograph production costs at the University of Michigan and Indiana University to be much closer to Maron et al.'s figures: \$28,000 and \$27,000 respectively. These figures from the Mellon study include physical printing costs, but these were negligible with regard to the total costs: approximately \$1,000 (Michigan) and \$500 (Indiana) per monograph. Studies are still to be conducted on the nature of OA monograph production costs, and the nature of production cost differences, as a function of e.g. the kind of publisher, and its market.

Footnotes

110 Eve (2014: 134-135) mentions a fourth non-BPC model, too: collective funding. For current purposes, this model is sufficiently similar to institutional subsidy to consider it as a mere variation. Roughly, Eve considers collective funding as a collaboration among stakeholding institutions to cover the publishing costs belonging to the first production of an OA monograph, whereas institutional subsidy aims at financially facilitating OA activity more generally.

Table 13: Overview of book production costs found by other studies and referred to above.

Study	Costs found
OAPEN-NL (2013)	€5,000-€10,000
Mellon Report (2015)	\$28,000, \$129,000
Gatti & Mierowsky (2016)	± \$8,500

Translating cost to price has proven a challenging task to publishers (OAPEN-UK 2016: 49). By and large publishers, even commercial ones, do not expect to make significant profit on monographs; monographs are then published mainly for the sake of reputation (Crossick 2015a: 55). Even though OA publishing diminishes the extent of possible, unexpected sales profits, prices charged by publishers for OA monographs so far seem to be calculated primarily towards simply not making a loss (OAPEN-UK 2016: 51).

A few current BPCs from a number of publishers have been listed by Eve (2014: 130): \$2,450/chapter from de Gruyter, €640/chapter from InTech, £5,900 from Manchester University Press (for monographs up to 80,000 words)¹¹¹, £11,000 Palgrave, and approximately €15,000 from Springer. Gatti and Mierowsky (2016: 457) found Brill to charge \$6,675 for a monograph under a CC BY-NC licence (we turn to the matter of licence in section 9.3.2), and Palgrave Open to charge \$17,000 for a monograph under CC BY. Certain required refinements notwithstanding, the juxtaposition of the figures such as those cited from OAPEN-NL (2013) and Maron et al. (2016) with current BPCs, might serve as fertile soil for quantitative investigations into the composition of economically sustainable BPCs for different publishers. See Greco and Spendley (2016: 108-110) for an overview of conventional monograph prices in the period 2012-2014 dissected along academic disciplines.

In addition to current uncertainties surrounding the computation of sustainable BPCs based on production costs, publishers may be hesitant to engage with OA for a number of other reasons (Eve 2014: 34), even though the BPC model allows publishers to profit from OA: decreasing profit margins following (1) a restriction of their conventional value-adding activities and (2) the loss of the monograph micro-monopoly, as well as the fear of loss of prestige through a limitation of copyright policies, to which we turn in section 9.2.2.

9.2.1 Publisher typology from the HEFCE report by Crossick

In annexe 4 to the HEFCE report by Crossick (2015b) a publisher typology is offered based on different business models. Six different publisher business models are discerned: traditional publishers, new university press OA, mission-oriented OA, freemium OA, aggregator/distributor, and the author payment model. These types are then assessed along three general lines: character, economics and performance. Below a (very) concise overview is to be found of these profile sketches. This typology proves helpful to understanding certain (side) effects of publisher policy (see section 9.3).

Traditional publisher

This publisher adopts an altogether entrepreneurial approach to monograph publishing, seeking to minimise costs and maximise revenue at every step in the chain of monograph publishing. Such concerns inspire it to target almost exclusively university libraries and academics. These disseminative confinements have made publishers sensitive to current strains on university budgets, making their business models unsustainable. They are however, an important contributor to the publishing landscape's diversity, as many traditional publishers have disciplinary strengths and inclinations.

New university press OA

This publisher in effect, charges author-side fees, which are then covered by the university to which the press belongs. It has been suggested that this model may be harmful to monograph quality, as it can lead to vanity publishing; these presses are usually presented with university policy obligations to publish a number of in-house works annually. The same incentive towards achieving and supporting reputation also limits the incentive to disseminate works beyond the scholarly realm. For some more detailed differences in practice between (new) university presses and traditional publishers, see Greco and Spendley 2016. For literature on recent developments within new UPs see e.g. Cond (2016), Lockett and Speicher (2016), Llewellyn and David (2016), and Adema and Stone (2017).

Mission-oriented OA

This press operates on ideological grounds, inherently motivated to promote OA publishing, and to see academics “take control” of their published outputs. It publishes under highly permissive licences and usually rejects freemium income models. Limited economic sustainability strains quality control, and endangers long-term availability of the OA material published. It thus relies on an author, consumer and funder devoted to its cause. Not coincidentally, these presses are often scholar-led or belong to a university.

Freemium OA

This publisher relies on revenue from services in addition to the freely available OA material. As such, the freemium publisher must be highly sensitive to consumer demands, as it relies on being aware of the add-on functions demanded by readers. Moreover, these publishers are stimulated to disseminate material widely, and beyond the scholarly community, as the marginal costs of their services are next to nothing. It is the only OA publisher relying on reader-side payments.

Aggregator/distributor

This actor is, in fact, not a publisher, yet it carries out a number of a publisher’s usual activities such as the promotion, quality assurance and dissemination of OA material, which makes it worth mentioning in the current context. At present, aggregators such as DOAB and OAPEN are of prime importance to the discoverability of OA monographs.

Author payment model

This publisher reverses altogether the traditional publishing business model: as described in section 9.1.1, many OA publishers opt for a business model wherein author-side (usually funded through research grants or university departmental budget) monograph payments (BPC) need to be made to cover production costs, and to pre-emptively compensate for potential financial loss. However, this model poses a threat to a publisher’s incentive towards quality assurance and dissemination.

9.2.2 Publisher: OA policies and licences

Publisher policy, in the sense discussed here, concerns (1) OA licensing, (2) pricing, (3) formats and editions, (4) quality assurance, (5) dissemination paths and (6) self-archiving options. (4), (5) and (6) are discussed under separate headings (9.3.1, 9.3.2, 9.3.3). In this subsection publisher choices pertaining to licensing, formats and editions are discussed. See section 9.2 for information on monograph production costs and pricing.

Footnotes

111 At present, MUP charges £10,000 for monographs up to 100,000 words.

The Creative Commons (CC) licences have become the standard within OA monograph publishing. All CC varieties have the following in common: they allow the monograph in question to be redistributed indefinitely without further permission required (Crossick 2015a: 43). The six most common CC licences are: (1) CC BY, (2) CC BY-SA, (3) CC BY-NC, (4) CC BY-NC-SA, (5) CC BY-ND, (6) CC BY-NC-ND. Though these licences allow for different kinds of activities (other than distribution, activities such as remixing, tweaking, extending of the work in question) for different kinds of purposes (commercial, non-commercial), all licences require the user to attribute the content used to the original author. CC BY is the most liberal of these licences, CC BY-NC-ND the most restrictive. See for a precise overview of the restriction in each of the six licences Eve (2014: 94).

Publishers choose the licences according to their business model (see for general typology section 9.2.1), and, as we explore in the sections to come, according to funder, and library and/or institutional policy. Recent literature has shown that publisher policy will need to be connected more extensively to library policy in order to further OA usage. McCollough (2017), for one, shows publishers need to be involved with the improvement of library discovery tools in order to increase their products' discoverability (see section 9.3.4). In a similar vein, Fisher and Jubb (2016) recognise the publisher's need to improve for the sake of discoverability both the extent and the consistency of monograph metadata on all platforms involved.

With regard to formats and editions made available by publishers, Lake (2016: 93-94) has identified three main reasons for the current drop in textbook sales experienced by publishers, all of which have to do with new developments and demands in terms of book formats. New demands relating to sharing options, online availability and integrated functions are identified as key elements to this trend. Pinter (2016: 43) has reported signals indicating that enhanced e-book

production has started to receive significant attention by publishers. One of the main impediments to this development thus far is that currently different e-book platforms offer different functions. Section 9.3.3 will turn to the question of OA infrastructure in greater detail.

The Oberlin Group study (2013) identified prevalent publishing models as a function of a publisher's format choice. Here, "OA PDF" was connected to author-side payments and freemium, as well as TA print sales; "OA all e-formats" was connected to TA print sales; "OA HTML" was connected to freemium and TA print sales.

9.2.3 Funders: OA policies and mandates

Funders have been identified as one of the main (potential) forces behind the OA monograph transition (Suber 2012: 77-78). Depending on the size of the fund, its targeted discipline(s), and its social agenda, funders have numerous routes through which to promote OA monograph publishing (OAPEN-UK 2016: 39). Suber (2012: 77-81) has identified four general kinds of mandates funders may enforce: so called "encouragement policies", "loophole mandates", "deposit mandates", and "rights-retention mandates". These policy models are concisely discussed below, as well as what is known about their actual proliferation. However, these four general mandate definitions were derived from APCs and require further elaboration concerning mandates for monographs.

- ▶ **Encouragement policies** are the least demanding of the four policies here mentioned: they non-bindingly request that the authors of the respective institution, or applicants of the respective funder body, have their work published by OA publishers

- ▶ **Loophole mandates** are of a slightly stronger kind: they require the author to, at the very least, officially request the respective publisher to provide OA services. If the publisher is not willing to comply, there are, however, no consequences
- ▶ **Deposit mandates** require (not request) authors to deposit their work in a digital repository. If the publishers do not grant permission to make the deposited material OA, the material is kept dark until permission is granted, and the publisher lifts the embargo. For journal articles functional embargo periods have been established, but Adema (2010: 17) has noted a number of complications to the establishment of respective periods for monographs. No literature has been identified on quantitative assessments of these monograph embargo periods. There is still considerable debate around what the appropriate length of an embargo period should be for different disciplines and different types of publication.
- ▶ **Rights-retention mandates** differ from deposit mandates in that they employ legal means guaranteeing the embargo is (eventually) lifted. Authors always possess initial copyright until they sell it to, say, a publisher. Rights-retention mandates require authors to provide the university with the rights for OA before the copyright is transferred to the publisher. The university, or funding institution, then, need not wait for a publisher embargo to be lifted, let alone for an embargo to be offered at all. This policy, however, runs the risk of limiting the number of publishers willing to accept the author's monograph.

A rich analysis of OA policies that are in effect (Archambault et al. 2014), conducted for the European Commission, has carefully mapped the different OA journal policies adopted by governments, (national) funding bodies, and research institutions worldwide.

Among governments actively seeking to proliferate OA, deposit mandates (Spain, Italy, Ireland) and rights-retention mandates (Germany, Lithuania) seem most common (ibid: 2-9). The most prolific OA funding bodies are to be found in the United Kingdom, Canada, United States, Denmark, Ireland and France, and among them deposit mandates seem most widely pursued (ibid: 17-19). Differences arise in how they expect these mandates to be adhered to and funded. However, it must be noted that this is only for journal article mandates. Among all the funding bodies investigated by the cited study, only the Wellcome Trust (UK) extended its OA policy beyond the journal article to monographs (ibid: 10). More recently, a Science Europe study (Kita, Duchange, Ponsati 2016: 14) found FWF, NWO, and SNSF to have included monographs in their OA policy, too. For more detailed expositions of OA policy tendencies, see also Ferwerda, Snijder and Adema (2013b: 23-26), Adema (2010: 20-53), and Moore's (2016) PASTEUR4OA Briefing Paper. For suggested extensions of OA mandates in the future see Suber 2012 (90-95). For literature on the extension of funder policy towards publisher metadata, see the Science Europe study (Kita, Duchange, Ponsati 2016: 4).

Lastly, funder mandates are a precarious matter, as they can easily be (perceived as) infringements upon academic freedom (particularly in the case of rights-retention mandates), even though a study by Alma Swan and Sheridan Brown (2003) shows that nearly 80% of the questioned academic authors said they would accept OA mandates of sorts. Moreover, Suber (2012: 84) argues that such funder policies do not limit faculty freedom, as (1) authors are free to apply for funding elsewhere, and (2) most publishers nowadays are willing to comply.

9.2.4 Libraries: OA policies and mandates

When libraries operate as funders, they have the same mandate options listed in the previous subsection. Of special interest is the current development wherein libraries opt for funding cooperation. In such consortium subsidy models, libraries agree to fund author-side payments of OA works together, thus reducing their individual expenditure whilst gaining literature then open for everyone to access. A number of institutions aid such consortium formation for precisely this purpose – arXiv, SCOAP, and Open Library of Humanities are notable examples for journals. Knowledge Unlatched is the only pure library consortium for monographs. Other than through funding, libraries may also support OA through their digital infrastructure towards dissemination, discovery and archiving, as well as providing author guidance and advocacy. We turn to this topic in 9.3.2.

The OAPEN-UK study found 80% of the libraries find OA monographs “positive/very positive”, and 96% think the same of OA journals. Though these transitions, from the library perspective, aim to serve the pressured library budgets, it also requires libraries to rethink their position in society, Eve (2014: 41) noted. After all, if literature can be accessed and printed on demand, other social-intellectual roles will have to be explored by the library in order to subsist as an institution.

One of the new roles open for libraries in an OA world is that of the digital repository, wherein authors and/or publishers can deposit monographs, articles, etc. (Eve 2014: 9). As such, Eve argues that libraries could aid publishers in the OA transition by offering the infrastructure by which OA material is to be stored and offered (see section 9.3.3). Authors may deposit their pre-print/post-print work there either by their own incentive, or by institutional mandate demands. As was discussed in section 9.2.2, an increasing amount of literature has identified the mutual need of publishers

and libraries to improve on available OA metadata for discoverability. For other and more detailed library policy (changes) towards discoverability, see Fisher and Jubb (2016) and McCollough (2017: 181-182). For a typology of the different kinds of relation libraries and publishers may enter among each other see Maricevic (2016) and Watkinson (2016: 344). For an overview of developments in the relation libraries may have towards academics, see Smyth (2016).

9.2.5 Authors and readers

Once basic economic independence has been achieved, the academic author, generally, no longer operates according to economic incentives: personal intellectual gratification and professional prestige coming with quality work are, then, the main incentives (Suber 2012: 11-12). In the OAPEN-UK study (2016: 44) it was, for example, found that only 14% of the authors interviewed had royalties and improved contractual agreements been important to their decision to change publisher. On the other hand, the income from royalties, it has been found, is commonly negligible compared to the author's tenure income (Suber 2012: 107). The OAPEN-UK report found (1) dissemination (54%), (2) quality assurance (43%), and (3) disciplinary reputation (35%) to be among the three most important pillars for authors when browsing for companies through which to publish their work. Authors have two interconnected, non-economic incentives: to publish with a prestigious publisher, and to see wide dissemination of their work. For a number of other developments in the wishes expressed by monograph authors in terms of the monograph features, see McCall and Bourke-Waite (2016).

Although the OAPEN-UK report found that only 1% of the interviewed authors held OA services as an explicit criterion in selecting publishers of interest, 48% of the authors indicated OA monographs to be “positive/very positive” for their field (2016: 21). Most likely, this has to do with, as amongst others Eve (2014: 116) has noted,

that authors are still doubtful whether unestablished OA publishers and formats are able to translate the author's tremendous effort in writing a monograph into the longed-for reputational gain within the academic community. Among the OA licences authors however would consider using, OAPEN-UK found the interest to be distributed as follows: CC BY (19%), CC BY-SA (22%), CC BY-NC (24%), CC BY-NC-SA (43%), CC BY-ND (57%), CC BY-NC-ND (79%). See Hacker and Carrao (2017: 80) for a number of practical strategies they adopted when setting up heiUP (Heidelberg's new OA university publisher) to enthuse authors about engaging with an unproven OA publisher.

Readers are generally concerned with two features: a work's quality, and its accessibility (OAPEN-UK 2016: 37). With regard to the former, readers are still hesitant about OA monographs, sceptical about "free quality:" and about whether free material has been reviewed properly (Eve 2014: 117). With regard to the latter, readers are, of course, generally enthusiastic, as digital OA monographs enlarge the scope of checking and retrieving content, and cross-referencing. In so far as detailed reading is concerned, print is still in favour among readers. Although, no significant sales increase has been measured as monographs turn OA (OAPEN-NL 2012: 53), it is largely agreed that OA is conducive to readership (Suber 2012: 145).

9.3 Policy implications

9.3.1 Quality assurance and peer review

As was suggested in section 9.2.1, different publishing business models have different consequences for the reviewing process by which quality is ensured. Crossick (2015a: 26) defines three general types of quality assurances at play in monograph publishing: (1) pre-publication peer review, (2) the publisher's reputation, and (3) post-publication review. Especially the first, pre-publication peer review, may be strained in a number of OA business models,

most notably wherein vanity publishing looms: new university presses OA, and author payment models (Crossick 2015b: 15).

OA publishing, however, also enables new mechanisms for quality assurance, such as open peer review, and certain alternatives to traditional post-publication peer review (Crossick 2015a: 27; Lake 2016). Open peer review can be done, for example, by making available the preprint draft, so as to collect (anonymous) feedback. In a similar vein, post-publication peer review enables material to be reviewed more easily and anonymously after the monograph has appeared. Peter Mole (2016: 13), moreover, has discussed new OA options for post-publication revision. The OA journal transition relies on being able to guarantee the same quality as traditional publishers have been offering, to the extent that some (eg. Harnad 2009) imagine future OA publishers to be solely devoted to managing (new) peer review mechanisms. Concerning monographs, however, the OAPEN-UK study (2016: 19) found authors to value publisher services such as distribution (81%) and marketing (81%) practically as much as peer review coordination (78%).

9.3.2 Dissemination and discovery

As with quality assurance, we have seen incentives to further dissemination and discoverability to be connected to a publisher's respective business model. According to Crossick (2015b: 30-31), as a publisher comes to (increasingly) rely on author-side payments as opposed to toll access charges, the economic incentive to disseminate diminishes. Moreover, especially new OA presses, who have not yet established an extensive network and accompanying marketing strategy, are at risk of falling short in terms of dissemination (OAPEN-UK 2016: 49). Lastly, sustainable dissemination relies on the durability of the repository used by the publisher. Unstable publishing models, such as mission-driven programmes, run risks in this respect (Crossick 2015b: 31).

Concerns such as these underline the (potentially increased) importance of aggregators to the OA transition, as discussed in the section 9.2.1 (see also Fisher and Jubb 2016). Eve (2014: 68) has noted that many such green repositories are not included by traditional library search engines. Improved understanding of dissemination effectiveness relies on accurate impact metrics, to which section 9.4 is devoted. With regard to the effect of OA on traditional dissemination paths, a study by OAPEN-NL (2013: 4-5) has shown OA to not measurably interfere with traditional sales, though digital usage did increase. Also, while OA seems to benefit journal citation scores, they found no such improvement with regard to monographs that had been published OA (Eve 2014: 123; OAPEN-NL 2013: 4-5). (Anecdotal comments suggest that since 2013 OA has caused traditional sales to decrease. However, there is no way of knowing at this time how much of that is because of slightly improved visibility and how much is simply a part of the general decline in monographs – open or closed.)

Finally, and as was touched upon in section 9.2.4, aggregation requires comprehensive and up-to-date metadata. Metadata generally concerns “information about books and their availability in different formats and from different sources” (Fisher & Jubb 2016). Other than the challenge of actually collecting particular information and keeping it updated, a number of challenges are: how to catalogue (increasingly) interdisciplinary works (Pinter 2016); the possibility of including metadata not only in catalogues, but in the actual book (Pinter 2016); how to ensure metadata is unaffected by different digital environments (O’Neill 2016); improving systematic metadata dissemination from publishers to repositories (McCollough 2017).

9.3.3 OA infrastructure

After the actual monograph production, OA infrastructure is meant to serve two connected purposes: dissemination and (long-term) preservation.

With regard to the latter, the OAPEN-UK study found libraries to be in favour of central repositories, so as to ensure the content’s durability (OAPEN-UK 2016: 53). Without long-term financial security, repositories will be unattractive for authors considering OA (ibid). The OAPEN-UK study (ibid: 31) found 82% of the interviewed libraries to “strongly agree/agree” with the development of a central OA monograph repository for their respective country. In their study, both libraries and researchers expressed concern about whether publishers can be entrusted to ensure long-term availability of OA material, as the costs involved are still uncertain. Print-on-demand has made such repositories of interest to publishers, too, in the sense that titles can be kept profitable for a longer time, even when sales drop, as physical storage costs disappear (McCall & BourkWaite 2016). As to dissemination, OAPEN-UK (2016: 55-56) identified four main dissemination paths, listed and discussed below:

▶ A. Third party sites

Under this heading fall library vendors, OA aggregators and retail websites such as Google and Amazon. Retail websites especially are often not equipped to distribute OA material, the OAPEN-UK study noted

▶ B. Libraries

In addition to their individual repositories and vendor services, libraries might work together with organisations such as DOAB and OAPEN Library. These aggregators present and integrate the OA material in library discovery systems

▶ C. Institutional and subject repositories

These repositories are often set up by individual libraries, universities or research institutions. Such repositories often work with OA material published under CC licences

▶ D. Self-archiving

One speaks of self-archiving when the author deposits her work either into an institutional or subject repository (by mandate or not) or into a personal website of sorts for the sake of OA. This practice may pose problems for repository managers, as most publishers do not have explicit and pre-arranged policies concerning self-archiving. ResearchGate and Academia.edu belong to the most important self-archiving platforms

9.3.4 Impact metrics

Accurate bibliometrics are important both to OA and non-OA monographs. In the case of OA material, however, such assessments are both more central and more arduous: more central because OA's core aspiration is to increase access; more arduous because most CC licences permit the reader to distribute copies of the monograph, and most of the time this will be hidden for assessments (OAPEN-UK 2016: 57). This problem can be avoided to an extent by measuring not readership but its proxy citations, or scholarly impact (Snijder 2016: 5). Moreover, impact of books is generally reflected less by citation scores than the impact journal articles, for which most impact metrics have been designed (Halevi, Nicolas & Bar-Ilan 2016).

In addition to collecting citation scores, assessors may also extend their scope so as to include altmetrics, by which one measures online scholarly activity concerning a particular body of work by tracing activities on blogs, Facebook, Scopus citations, CiteULike bookmarks and Mendeley references (Snijder 2016: 6; see also Halevi, Nicolas & Bar-Ilan 2016). Such assessments, however, have thus far been carried out especially with regard to journal articles, and it remains to be seen whether they may be applied to monographs, too. Monographs, for one, usually do not figure in Mendeley. Although recently, Springer and Altmetric have developed an altmetrics service for books called Bookmetrix.

9.4 Conclusion

This review is an attempt to identify what is known and unknown with regard to three main points in OA monograph publishing. These points are:

- ▶ Economic models for OA monograph publishing
- ▶ Stakeholders in OA monograph publishing and their policies
- ▶ The effect of different stakeholder OA policy on the actual monograph

This concluding section sets out to pinpoint and elaborate on the according knowledge gaps identified in the literature. These fall into five groups:

- ▶ **How to break down and calculate monograph production costs accurately (see e.g. 9.2)**
 - › A number of important studies on OA monograph production costs have been cited in this review: the OAPEN-NL Final Report by Ferwerda et al. (2013), the Mellon Foundation Report by Walters and Hilton (2015), the Ithaka S+R Report by Maron et al. (2016), and the study by Gatti and Mierowsky (2016). These studies have found widely different OA monograph production costs, and they disagree with regard to the cost elements one needs to include in such assessment. More research needs to be done on this topic. Future research would amongst others benefit from defining OA monograph production costs as a function of e.g. publisher kind and monograph discipline. Beyond this there is a need for the whole community to take a look at just what aspects of production are essential and which could be dispensed with without compromising the integrity of the monograph. Such work has begun in the United States.

- ▶ **The effect OA has on the sales of physical monograph copies (see e.g. 9.2.5 and 9.3.2)**
 - › Monograph readers generally still prefer physical copies for reading; OA versions serve mainly the reader's ability to find, share, cite and search literature. There is no conclusive evidence yet about how OA availability affects sales as some studies show increase and others show decrease in print sales. Further research on this topic is of importance to the OA transition, both in terms of developing publishing models and extending publisher enthusiasm. This is not something that is static, or moving at a similar pace across countries. Therefore the study would need to be granular
- ▶ **How to assure monograph quality in OA publishing, and what kind of new review mechanisms OA could support towards this cause (see e.g. 9.3.2)**
 - › The quality assurance mechanism of OA material may be strained at three points: A) There is perception in some places that a number of OA publishing models are more susceptible to vanity publishing than, say, traditional TA or OA freemium publishing; B) quality assurance relies amongst others on the reputation previously gained by the respective publishers, and new presses (whether OA or not) have generally not achieved this reputational position; C) quality assurance relies on an elaborate editorial network within the monograph's respective discipline and here, too, new presses suffer a disadvantage with regard to established publishers. More research remains to be done on the precise influence of OA with regard to each of these points. In turn, more research is also needed to explore a number of altogether new quality assurance mechanisms enabled by OA, both in pre and post-print stages of the monograph.
- ▶ **How to produce, sustain, and catalogue accurate and complete metadata over different platforms and from different publishers, so as to increase discoverability (see e.g. 9.3.2)**
 - › At present, there is neither a definitive agreement with regard to the kind of metadata publishers should deliver to their distribution channels, nor a protocol for synchronising such data on different technological platforms. There have been various initiatives to identify metadata for OA books, from Editeur for ONIX, Jisc/OAPEN and CrossRef. In order to further discoverability and accessibility, it is important to research methods to improve on these two points. Bringing together standards bodies and examining how they might work together to develop global standards would be advisable
- ▶ **How to develop accurate OA impact metrics (see e.g. 9.3.4)**
 - › This point is tangentially related to the second point discussed above: in order to further OA, it is important for authors and publishers to know what open access generally does for the monograph in terms of discoverability, dissemination, sales, etc. Traditional monograph impact metrics fall short when assessing the OA monograph: OA licences often allow for readers to distribute material along paths where it cannot be traced. Work thus needs to be done on reliable sources of proxy data – that is, other than downloads and sales

9.5 Literature review annexe

9.5.1 Open Access Book Publishing 2016-2020 – a report by Simba Information (October 2016)

The Simba Report, aimed primarily at the multinational publishing community, covers STM and SSH publishing from a global perspective and, while it focuses on English, it includes observations for the German, French, Dutch, Spanish and Portuguese languages, especially in SSH publishing.

Their forecasts estimate an annual growth in the open access “market” of 30%, ie funds will be found for BPCs either from research funders or other sources such as Knowledge Unlatched and Lever Press. They base their 2016-2020 forecasts on trends such as the growth of books coming on stream in DOAB, the willingness to experiment with new business models and the likelihood of one or more of the larger companies (such as Springer Nature or Informa) finding ways of funding OA. They see the opportunities of digital and journalising of book collections as paving the way.

The Simba Report also finds that once funders extend their mandates to books and book chapters this will provide a lift to STM OA books as well. Overall the report is optimistic about the growth of OA and books. And while growth will start from a low base globally they see European growth to be greater than elsewhere.

9.5.2 The Academic Book of the Future – a policy report from the AHRC/British Library project by Michael Jubb

This policy report arose out of the 2014-2016 Academic Book of the Future project funded by the AHRC and British Library. The aim of the project was to “look in detail at the academic book from the perspectives of publishers, libraries and intermediaries, in particular analysing the policy implications of new developments in the funding and assessment regimes currently affecting academe, and the changes in publishing

and libraries necessitated by the onward march of the digital, of funding constraints, and by the rapid moves towards open access for books” (page 4). The project engaged with a broad range of UK stakeholders and from various activities concluded:

“ that the academic book/monograph is still greatly valued in the academy for many reasons: the ability to produce a sustained argument within a more capacious framework than that permitted by the article format; the engagement of the reader at a deep level with such arguments; its central place in career progression in the arts and humanities; its reach beyond the academy (for some titles) into bookshops and into the hands of a wider public. It seems that the future is likely to be a mixed economy of print, e-versions of print and networked enhanced monographs of greater or lesser complexity” (page 11). ”

The policy report contains a great deal of very important and useful information, especially in areas that have hitherto remained somewhat opaque such as the role of intermediaries (thanks to the diligent research undertaken by Richard Fisher and Michael Jubb). However, it must be noted that findings were primarily (though not exclusively) drawn from the world of humanities book publishing only, and the project brief and budget limited most activities to the UK.

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10. Why book processing charges vary so much

By Frances Pinter

10.1 Introduction

In this study we have come across a wide range of monograph publishing with BPCs ranging from €500 to €18,500. In this annexe we aim to explain why by looking at what services are offered for a BPC and also explain why coming up with precise and comparable costs is problematic.

This annexe is written from the perspective of a British academic publisher. Although the figures are taken mainly from UK and global English-language publishing, the basic considerations do not differ greatly from those found elsewhere.

A glossary of accounting terms is provided as section 10.7 at the end of this chapter.

The available literature is presented in section 9.2 above (Costs of OA publications and the question of pricing).

10.2 Determining the cost of a monograph

Observers of monograph publishing often complain of a lack of transparency around publishing “costs”. There is the sense that BPCs are arbitrary and do not relate to real costs. The actual story is both simpler and more complicated. BPCs are based on direct and indirect, fixed and variable costs of acquiring, editing, designing, producing and marketing a monograph. They carry within them an allocation for overheads, and profit or surplus. It is how these are accounted for that is the challenge.

Open access publishing lends itself to a “cost plus” accounting model rather than a “mark-up” way of charging for costs because it is a service offer with costs recovered from sources other than the sale of individual “copies” (print or digital) of the book. There are differences between cost plus - a model more generally associated with non-profit and smaller university presses and the mark-up model traditionally employed by larger, older and for-profit companies.

“Observers of monograph publishing often complain of a lack of transparency around publishing “costs”.”

Another challenge is that accounting for university presses can sometimes be forced to follow the format of the university itself, especially where a press is either a department of the university or embedded in the library. While this is in itself not a problem it can lead to difficulties when comparing with profit and loss accounts of commercial companies. For example, handling of accruals can vary along with different write-off conventions.

Cost plus consists of direct costs plus various fixed costs, without reference to variable expenses traditionally associated with sales, such as fees paid to sales representatives and in some cases a proportion of other staff costs.

Extensive lists of publishing functions have been produced from time to time, ranging from 50-100 distinct tasks. The diagram below (page 131) takes us through the key stages (acquisitions, manuscript editorial, design, production, marketing and sales).

BPCs of OA publications are generally in line with costs incurred by the publisher, although traditional presses may include an element of income substitution for lost sales of print and digital versions. Here we show a range of models and what is included in the service before turning to how these are accounted for. Further on we look at the Ithaka study on monograph costs for US university presses.

The categories to be found in our countries are:

- ▶ Hosting the book and distribution of metadata through some channels. This is a service provided by KIT Scientific Publishing, based in Germany. Generally charging under €1,000 for a BPC, KIT does not undertake peer review nor does it provide any editorial guidance or copy editing. The author is asked to put their book on a CC BY-SA 4.0 licence and produce a ready to load PDF to KIT. Print books are available through Amazon's POD services. No bespoke marketing is offered
- ▶ Small university/library-based publishing (such as University of Huddersfield Press) that have specific aims – in this case to act as an outlet for early career researchers as well as an outlet for niche/ interdisciplinary research for Huddersfield scholars - is not intended to divert authors from publishing with traditional, prestigious publishers. Monograph production costs for two books a year amount to £4,500 per book. However, management, administrative support and infrastructure support is absorbed by the university. Nevertheless, UHP contributes from its own budget £2,000 towards repository maintenance and £1,000 on marketing along with another £2,000 annual expenditures on supporting DOAB, DOAJ and SPARC. If these costs were included in the direct book costs the full BPC would, in all likelihood be over £7,000 per book
- ▶ Larger new university/library-based publishing such as UCL Press. In this case UCL absorbs the publishing costs for UCL authors. It also offers publication to non-UCL authors for a fee of £5,000
- ▶ Traditional university presses in the UK charge anything from £8,000 to £10,000 for a BPC. This includes supporting a full suite of infrastructure costs that some refer to as legacy costs. These chiefly concern the fixed costs associated with

servicing sales and distribution that are still expected of these presses. Whether these BPCs cover all such costs is contested mainly because it is difficult to ascribe these costs to any single book as we'll see below. Most university presses prefer to publish under a CC BY-NC licence with over 50% of OA books so far carrying the ND restriction, often at the request of the author

- ▶ BPC charges from commercial presses are generally higher, either because more infrastructure investment is being charged to each monograph, or licensing terms are more liberal, or there is a need to provide a profit, though this is generally significantly less than can be extracted from journal publishing. These charges are typical examples where licences are restricted to CC BY-NC: Brill, €8,500, deGruyter €10,000, Bloomsbury up to £8,500, Routledge, £10,000. Examples of BPCs with a CC BY licence are: Brill €18,500 and Palgrave €17,000. In these cases there is an assumption that there will be no further sales from other formats to cover the full costs of publishing. Many of these publishers offer chapter OA opportunities with costs listed on their websites. They also have varying policies concerning what can be hosted as OA on the author's (or their institution's) websites – usually pre-prints of a single chapter

Before looking at how traditional companies determine the cost of a monograph we summarise here the way Open Book Publishers account for their costs.

Figure 5: OBP publication and distribution costs, per title

The title set-up cost is based on fixed costs, but the allocation of overheads depends on dividing the total annual overhead costs by the number of books published in the year. The costs for sales and distribution are the result of sales of the five formats in which the book is available, with the average above calculated after the end of the year by dividing the costs by the number of units sold (all at different prices and with different discount structures).

In the twelve months between 1 September 2014 and 31 August 2015 Open Book Publishers revenues came from four sources: Sales - \$82,873, grants to OBP - \$15,708, library membership - \$30,986 and “title grants” (BPCs from outside sources such as research funders) - \$68,396. The total costs for 18 new books were covered by income of \$189,216. Further details on the types of formats and sources of sales are available here: <http://blogs.openbookpublishers.com/introducing-data-to-the-open-access-debate-obps-business-model-part-three/>

Open Book Publishers is an example of an academic-led press that has over the years tried to offer both new and traditional services to authors. This requires infrastructure investments that often take time to bear fruit.

The best-resourced new university press in the UK is UCL Press, which had a budget of £400,000. In 2016 it published 25 books and six journals. UCL Press includes less in its direct costs than OBP, however, as OBP says, their “title setup (direct costs) is a catchall for everything else – including all staff costs – as that is our primary day-to-day activity, but I should note that some of this time is also spent in R&D, developing innovative products and systems”. Many of these costs are in UCL Press’s “digital development and systems” heading under operational costs and in staff costs that are accounted for separately. https://ucl.ac.uk/ucl-press/docs/UCL_Press_Annual_Report/

Both models are essentially cost plus models with some costs associated with variables dependent on sales. In the case of traditional presses some are shifting some of their publications to cost plus while still aiming to find ways to cover all costs. Whether they make a profit/surplus and what happens with this money is a different issue from establishing ways of understanding and accounting for true costs.

Publishers build a profile of each publishing project making assumptions of how much it will cost to make and then how much income can be expected. In the case of monographs the cost of sale generally consists of both fixed and variable costs. These include the production costs and royalties (or fees) to the author. In the days of print this would include all pre-press fixed costs and printing costs that are variable. The unit print cost of a book depends on how many are printed but the cost of sale in any year depends on the numbers actually sold. For the digital object the cost of

“ At this point in time HSS publishers of English language books still derive approximately 80% of their sales from printed books. ”

production is the cost of getting to first digital file. There is no print cost for the digital object, but there are other costs associated with it that are both fixed and variable, such as file maintenance and storage and these are different to the printed object. While establishing an overall cost of sale the project needs to take into account all costs of production, and this typically includes estimates of print costs based on the number to be printed and sold over a designated period (anything from one to three years).

At this point in time HSS publishers of English language books still derive approximately 80% of their sales from printed books, though this is expected to drop at some point – though perhaps not as much as originally predicted a few years ago. Publishers in other languages derive a lower percentage of sales from digital – at the moment.

Many presses make losses on their monographs but finance them through cross-subsidisation with profits from other types of books. Some monographs, on the other hand, produce surprises such as being adopted on courses that can lead to multiple print sales, or chapter sales in digital form if that opportunity is available. Sales of backlist books produce income to cover fixed running costs.

If a royalty is to be paid to the author then the expected royalty is added to the cost of sale, and the same thing applies if it is a fee. While the royalty is generally expressed as a percentage and is only paid if sales are made (thereby a variable cost), a fee paid up front is divided by the number of units a publisher expects to sell and allocated to each unit sale or written off in the first year of publication. The fee is not recoverable if sales do not meet expectations. Some publishers pay no royalties at all on monographs. New institutionally based university presses tend not to depend on sales to fund their operations, tend not to offer royalties to authors and therefore this is not a consideration when calculating cost of sale.

So, if a cost of sale is, say 30% of the price received by the publisher that leaves another 70% to allocate to all the other publishing costs. This is not 70% of the recommended retail price (RRP), but 70% of the publisher's net receipts.

Establishing the total income from any single book project requires a certain amount of guesswork. It is not derived from the recommended retail price (or cover price) listed in the publisher catalogues, but rather a composite net figure that takes into account the varying discounts given off the cover price through different channels. These discounts can vary from as low as 20% to as high as 70% depending on the negotiating power of the intermediary seller (wholesalers, distributors, vendors such as Amazon, EBSCO, Proquest, JSTOR, MUSE and others). Intermediaries mark up the item from the price they paid sufficiently to cover their costs and then offer the item to their customers (Amazon selling mainly but not exclusively direct to the end reader, while the others sell mainly to libraries). This can result in a price that is above that paid to the publisher but below the recommended retail price listed by the publisher. (The margin taken by the intermediary can be up to 50% of the recommended retail price) as noted in the Academic Book of the Future report (section 9.5.2).

“ Many presses make losses on their monographs but finance them through cross-subsidisation with profits from other types of books. ”

The larger publishers (such as OUP, CUP and Palgrave) are less dependent on sales through intermediaries, but instead invest in their own platforms and sell from there. The gross profits are then higher, but they do have higher operating costs of hosting and selling.

The sales also depend on where the potential readers are – whether the book is of local or global interest. Differing discounts and shipping costs are taken into account, as well as terms of credit. Generally, the further away the destination is the longer the credit period will be.

The other publishing costs that sit between the cost of sale and the net profit are made up of both fixed and variable costs. They include staff (generally at all levels as well as acquisitions editors), office overheads, IT, (some) marketing, sales, distribution and various post publication costs associated with taking care of the book after its launch. These can also be a mix of either fixed or variable costs. For example, a large company may employ a sales force (fixed costs) while a small company pays an agency a commission based on results (variable cost). But either way there is a management overhead in taking care of sales.

As we've seen in the definition of fixed and variable costs (see glossary), if fixed costs are spread across a diminishing number of units sold then each unit must carry a greater burden of fixed costs which are often overheads that are difficult to adjust quickly in a contracting market.

The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation funded an Ithaka S&R study **The Costs of Publishing Monographs: Toward a Transparent Methodology** authored by Nancy Maron. It covered 20 US university presses. When first published in February 2016 alarm bells rang

as the cost of monographs ranged from \$15,000 to \$129,000! The latter was the outlier, but demonstrated the point that not all monographs cost the same. The report detailed the publishing processes and distinguished between three cost tiers. These were:

- ▶ Basic – including staff time, staff overheads and direct costs
- ▶ Full cost – including the above plus press-level overheads
- ▶ Full cost plus – including all above plus in-kind contributions

The study also showed how the above costs vary between small, medium and large university presses, divided up into four groups – clarifying important differences.

The lead author of the report, Nancy Maron, developed a costing tool available at: <http://aaupnet.org/resources/for-members/handbooks-and-toolkits/digital-monograph-costing-tool>. She is now examining where costs can be brought down by greater templating, smoother workflows etc.

“ The margin taken by the intermediary can be up to 50% of the recommended retail price ”

“ The cost of publishing is not the actual price charged as a BPC. ”

Key Stages in the Publishing Process

Maron illustrates above the key stages of monograph publishing (from ALPSP presentation 22 February 2017). The first four steps are considered fixed costs. Just what marketing should consist of is hotly debated. It is not enough simply to put a book on a platform and hope people find it especially if a funder or institution is paying for its publication as OA. A certain amount of marketing has to be carried out for OA books even if no sales are expected of other formats. Sales and distribution costs are generally calculated as a variable cost – depending on the number of units sold.

The Ithaka report provided the publishing industry with some benchmarks against which to examine their own costs. Large European publishers appear to have lower costs than American university presses. But they still have the same issues around determining exactly what their costs are.

University presses vary everywhere with hidden and not so hidden institutional subsidies presenting different pictures. Nevertheless, most publishers calculate their costs by using templated cost sheets. Editors fill these in with help from their colleagues in production. These sheets accompany the initial proposal that then needs to pass scrutiny by the marketing and sales departments. Once a book project is approved the costs are allocated to a budget that will then need be calendarised to account for when payments become due.

10.3 Relating BPCs to the cost of publishing

The cost of publishing is not the actual price charged as a BPC. The price will take into account the potential revenue of the book and other subsidies. It will look at whether cross-subsiding open from closed is a possibility and whether charging full cost recovery including hidden overheads currently paid by institutions for most university presses is necessary, or will be so at some future date.

For the moment BPCs are in flux as publishers are still gathering data to check that the project makes the kind of return they expect from a similar closed volume. All this is taking place during a time when monograph sales are tumbling due to library budget squeezes, the split between print and digital sales have not stabilised and new buying options such as PDA, DDA, EDA, short term loans etc are still in experimental mode.

To date the data on which publishers might reflect has been slow in coming in, given that there are still fewer than 10,000 titles in OA, spread across hundreds of publishers.

10.4 Relating BPCs to monograph sales

If monograph sales were static and predictable it would be relatively easy for a publisher to determine income by past performance. The publisher would also know how much income was needed to cover costs. However, they are not predictable and there are a number of factors that need to be taken into account. They are:

- ▶ Monograph sales are falling in print format (due to budget cuts, better inter-library loan services etc)
- ▶ Digital sales grew a few years ago and now appear to have plateaued off, but they have, in any case, not reached the point where they substitute for the drop in print sales
- ▶ The various library schemes on offer from vendors mean that sales are coming through later in the life cycle of the book and there are fewer automatic sales through approval and other types of predictable plans
- ▶ Libraries are buying less for collections and being led more by the demands of their users. This leads to surprising and unpredictable sales patterns

“ If monograph sales were static and predictable it would be relatively easy for a publisher to determine income by past performance. ”

10.5 The changing models of monograph purchasing

Libraries, quite rightly, are moving away from collecting materials that may or may not have a rationale for their collections and focusing more on the services to their communities. As Caroline Brazier, Chief librarian at the British Library once said succinctly, “libraries are moving from collecting to connecting”. Libraries have been keen to work with vendors to reduce the cost of monographs by making best use of schemes that can be developed for digital content. The following are therefore emerging:

- ▶ Demand driven acquisition (DDA)
- ▶ Patron driven acquisition (PDA)
- ▶ Evidence based acquisition (EBA)
- ▶ Short term loans (STL)
- ▶ Sale by chapter (eligible for some or all of the above schemes)

During the short time that these schemes have been developed, trialed and refined publishers have been unable to predict what the impact will be on the overall income of a monograph that had hitherto sold most of its first print run to a stable set of libraries in the first year of publication, leaving a thin long tail for sale over a period of two to three years and possibly beyond. It's also changed the pattern of cash flow.

Michael Zeoli, Vice President of Content Development & Partner Relations GOBI Library Solutions, has spoken at numerous conferences about the shifts in buying patterns from his work at GOBI Library Solutions and what was previously called Yankee Book Peddler, the well-known

vendor to libraries and now part of EBSCO. He demonstrates with the data of three well-established university presses just what has happened between 2012 and 2015.

An extensive discussion of the impact of these changes can be found here, [http://niso.org/news/events/2015/virtual_conferences/eternal_ebooks/ - slides](http://niso.org/news/events/2015/virtual_conferences/eternal_ebooks/)

While the results differ a bit from publisher to publisher the changes are evident. The press illustrated below has seen a significant drop in print sales as well as a significant growth in DDA records being made available

in the hope that digital sales will follow. Short-term loans increased in 2015, however, in 2016 many publishers introduced embargos or increased the term of existing embargos for STLs because of fears that the overall revenue would decline very rapidly. Publishers also increased the STL charges. Approval plans, where the vendor matches purchases to library profiles and made purchases at the point of publication (thus securing early returns for publishers), are on the decline.

Example University Press #2, 35 new titles/year

Example University Press #2, digital detail

Example University Press #2

There are numerous imponderables around these numbers as we know that HSS books take longer to become known in their communities and usage grows more slowly than in other disciplines. This makes it difficult to predict sales. Backlist digital books are often sold at a much greater discount than is customary for print books. And while print books carry the costs of manufacturing and distribution, the savings on digital sales are not always enough to compensate for the contribution that print used to bring to fixed overheads.

At the moment publishers, even many of the OA not-for-profit publishers, are attempting to keep all channels for both free and charged for content serviced. Doing so has grown in complexity with the addition of e-book formats, each of which require different ways of servicing for the various channels, thus adding additional costs. While none of this is insurmountable it does mean publishers need to have the right skills in house to manage these relationships if books are to be sold in any format.

10.6 What does this mean for monograph publishing and BPCs?

Income from sales has dropped significantly over the years and is now \$7,000 to \$12,000 per average monograph project and expected to drop further. (This figure is derived from multiplying unit sales by average income per sale, and is based on interviews with publishers.) Publishers continue to increase the prices of print and e-books in order to be able to amortise their fixed and indirect costs across an ever smaller number of units sold. Major university and commercial presses are now selling less than 200 copies of monographs over three or more years. Getting the estimates wrong by only a few units makes the difference between profit and loss.

The struggle to anticipate income is a feature of any business or service. For example, if a university's intake of students is 10% less than anticipated, then teaching each student will cost more as the fixed costs are amortised across the lower number of students. To compensate, universities may introduce more online courses, open campuses elsewhere, or raise fees where possible etc. None of these types of concerns are restricted to academia or academic publishing. Most other sectors are struggling to adapt to change.

The immediate future for scholarly publishing is full of risks. Increasingly though, publishers see OA as an opportunity that may mitigate that risk and are therefore willing to accept decreased income – provided they can cover their costs, which may be reduced with simpler workflows and more modern infrastructures.

“ Publishers and vendors will be selling services rather than content. ”

Costs in the supply chain can be significantly reduced as well. The role of intermediaries will change. While libraries will continue to depend on a variety of services from companies such as EBSCO and Proquest the services around free content will be different and conceivably (but not yet conclusively) cost less once duplications and complications are extracted from the supply chain. Publishers and vendors will be selling services rather than content. With well-developed identifiers, metadata and transparency along with long term storage there can be a system that produces monographs with less friction throughout the chain.

One purpose of this chapter has been to indicate that BPCs and APCs are not the same and to show how greater transparency can lead to getting to reasonable BPCs with less acrimony than has been the case with journal APCs. We believe the recent antipathy towards APCs has arisen due to considering them to be in effect profit input substitutions rather than reflecting real costs of publishing. In the case of monographs there is far less profit to be had and a larger proportion of books are published by a larger number of small publishers – many of whom do not seek profits at all.

10.7 Glossary of accounting terms

Cost

In business, cost is usually a monetary valuation of (1) effort, (2) material, (3) resources, (4) time and utilities consumed, (5) risks incurred, and (6) opportunity forgone in production and delivery of a good or service. All expenses are costs, but not all costs (such as those incurred in acquisition of an income-generating asset) are expenses, [businessdictionary.com/definition/cost.html](https://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/cost.html)

In **business** (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Business>), the cost may be one of acquisition, in which case the amount of money expended to acquire it is counted as cost. In this case, money is the input that has gone in order to acquire the thing.....[cost can also refer to] **accounting cost** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Accounting_cost),

opportunity cost (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Opportunity_cost), **historical cost** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Historical_cost), **marginal cost** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marginal_cost), **sunk cost** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sunk_cost), and **transaction cost** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transaction_cost). (Source: Wikipedia).

Price

Price sometimes refers to the quantity of payment requested by a seller of goods or services, rather than the eventual payment amount. This requested amount is often called the **asking price** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ask_price) or selling price, while the actual payment may be called the transaction price or traded price. (Source: Wikipedia).

Recommended Retail Price (or “cover” or “list” price):

The list price, also known as the manufacturer’s suggested retail price (MSRP), or the recommended retail price (RRP), or the suggested retail price (SRP), of a product is the price at which the manufacturer recommends that the retailer sell the product. (Source: Wikipedia).

A price that the producer or wholesaler (a seller that sells to businesses rather than to the public) of a product suggests that it should be sold for in shops. (Source: Ft.com/lexicon).

Discount

They can occur anywhere in the **distribution channel** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distribution_channel), modifying either the manufacturer’s list price (determined by the manufacturer and often printed on the package), the retail price (set by the retailer and often attached to the **product** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Product_%28business%29) with a sticker), or the list price (which is quoted to a potential buyer, usually in written form). (Source: Wikipedia).

Cost of goods sold, or cost of sale

Costs of goods sold (COGS) are the **direct costs** (investopedia.com/terms/d/directcost.asp)

attributable to the production of the goods sold by a company. This amount includes the cost of the materials used in creating the good along with the direct labour costs used to produce the good. Publishers tend to use the phrase “cost of sale”.

(Source: investopedia.com/terms/c/cogs.asp#ixzz4ePB8Augk).

Gross profit

Gross profit is a company’s total revenue (equivalent to total sales) minus the cost of goods sold. Gross profit is the profit a company makes after deducting the costs associated with making and selling its products, or the costs associated with providing its services. Publishers tend to include only the cost of the product – and this is discussed in more detail below.

(Source: investopedia.com/terms/g/grossprofit.asp).

Net profit

Net profit, also referred to as the bottom line, net income, or net earnings is a measure of the profitability of a venture after accounting for all costs. It is the actual profit without inclusion of working expense in the calculation of gross profit. (Source: Wikipedia). For a comparison of the differences between gross and net profit see

investorwords.com/article/gross-vs-net.html

Margin

Margin is the difference between a product or service’s selling price and its cost of production or to the ratio between a company’s revenues and expenses. In business accounting, margin refers to the difference between revenue and expenses, and businesses typically track their gross profit margins, operating margins and net profit margins. **Gross profit margin** (investopedia.com/terms/g/gross_profit_margin.asp) measures the relationship between a company’s revenues and its cost of goods sold (COGS); operating

profit margin takes into account COGS and operating expenses and compares them to revenue; and net profit margin takes all of these expenses.

(Source: investopedia.com/terms/m/margin.asp#ixzz4ePDEbchV).

Mark up

The total cost reflects the total amount of both fixed and variable expenses to produce and distribute a product.

[1] Mark up can be expressed as a fixed amount or as a percentage of the total cost or selling price.[2] Retail mark up is commonly calculated as the difference between wholesale price and retail price, as a percentage of wholesale. (Source: Wikipedia).

Direct costs

A direct cost is a price that can be completely attributed to the production of specific goods or services. Some costs, such as depreciation or administrative expenses, are more difficult to assign to a specific product and therefore are considered to be indirect costs.

<http://investopedia.com/terms/d/directcost.asp>

Indirect costs

Indirect costs are costs that are not directly accountable to a **cost object** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cost_object) (such as a particular project, facility, function or product). Indirect costs may be either fixed or variable. Indirect costs include administration, personnel and security costs. These are those costs that are not directly related to production. Some indirect costs may be **overhead** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Overhead_%28business%29). But some overhead costs can be directly attributed to a project and are direct costs. (Source: Wikipedia).

Fixed cost

A fixed cost is a cost that does not change with an increase or decrease in the amount of goods or services produced or sold. Fixed costs are expenses that have to be paid by a company, independent of any business activity. It is one of the two components of the total cost of running a business, along with **variable cost** (investopedia.com/terms/v/variablecost.asp).

Examples of fixed costs include insurance, interest expense, property taxes, utilities expenses and depreciation of assets. Also, if a company pays annual salaries to its employees irrespective of the number of hours worked, such salaries must be counted as fixed costs. A company's **lease** (investopedia.com/terms/l/lease.asp) on a building is another common example of fixed costs. (Source: <http://investopedia.com/terms/f/fixedcost.asp#ixzz4ePGPNLYd>).

Variable cost

A variable cost is a corporate expense that varies with production output. Variable costs are those costs that vary depending on a company's production volume; they rise as production increases and fall as production decreases. **Variable costs** (investopedia.com/video/play/variable-costs) differ from **fixed costs** (investopedia.com/terms/f/fixedcost.asp) such as rent, advertising, insurance and office supplies, which tend to remain the same regardless of production output. Fixed costs and variable costs comprise total cost. Variable costs can include direct material costs or direct labour costs necessary to complete a certain project. For example, a company may have variable costs associated with the packaging of one of its products. As the company moves more of this product, the costs for packaging will increase. Conversely, when fewer of these products are sold the costs for packaging will consequently decrease.

(Source: investopedia.com/terms/v/variablecost.asp#ixzz4ePHnj5h0).

Profit/surplus

Profit is a financial benefit that is realised when the amount of revenue gained from a business activity exceeds the expenses, costs and taxes needed to sustain the activity. A **surplus** often occurs in a **budget** (investopedia.com/terms/b/budget.asp), when expenses are less than the income taken in. (Source: <http://investopedia.com/terms/s/surplus.asp#ixzz4eVkCnhC0>).

Profits and surpluses are derived in the same way. The different connotations within the publishing industry distinguish between commercial and non-commercial entities. OUP and CUP are not-for-profits but make significant surpluses. Taxation policies differ between commercial and non-commercial entities, as does decision-making on how much is to be re-invested in the business or distributed to the owners.

11. Assessing the impact of open access books

By Ronald Snijder

The impact of open access books can be measured in several ways. As these books are available online, the most obvious measurement is the number of downloads a book has received. However, the impact of scholarly publications has traditionally been assessed through citations, and, more recently, altmetrics have come into use as another type of impact measure. Here, altmetrics are defined as the measurement of online activities about scholarly publications. This section will discuss all three measurements.

11.1 Online availability and downloads

Open access books have to be made available online, leading to the question of what platform – or platforms – to use. Each platform has its own affordances. For instance, disseminating books via an institutional repository may underline the relation with the organisation. The Google Books platform has other strong points: besides being directly linked to the Google search engine, it allows rights owners precise control over how much of the books is made visible to the public. A platform such as the OAPEN Library is optimised for OA books and dissemination via academic libraries; the Directory of Open Access Books may amplify the use, but only for books with an open licence (Snijder, 2015a). In short, understanding the strengths and weaknesses of platforms is vital for choosing a dissemination strategy.

Online dissemination platforms shape what the reader can do with a book, which affects its usage. The usage data can be used to assess the impact of the books on the platform, an idea that was investigated by Herb et al. (2010). Most web-based platforms report the name of the organisation that grants internet access to the reader, and the country of origin. This publicly available information can be used to understand who is using the books and to assess the performance of the platform. This method is used by Snijder (2013b).

If the country of the readers is known, this information can be used to compare book usage of freely available

books compared by readers from developed and developing countries to books that are only partly available online. As it turns out, open access publishing enhances discovery and online usage in developing countries, strengthening the claims of open access advocates: researchers from the developing countries do benefit from free academic books (Snijder, 2013a). Assessments like this also help to describe the impact of collection of books in another language than English; such as the book made available through FWF, the Austrian Science Fund (Snijder, 2015b).

Each online dissemination platform provides a unique way to measure its usage, and the number of downloads may also be inflated by automated processes (“bots”). In other words, it may be possible to “game” outcomes. One way to overcome this is the deployment of standardised guidelines, such as COUNTER.

Counting Online Usage of Networked Electronic Resources (COUNTER) is an international initiative serving librarians, publishers and intermediaries by setting standards that facilitate the recording and reporting of online usage statistics in a consistent, credible and compatible way. By reporting use based on the COUNTER Code of Practice, the dissemination platform makes sure that all reported data is based on the same standard. The main purpose of COUNTER is to filter out unusual download behaviour and downloads by bots (COUNTER Online Metrics, 2014). For instance, the OAPEN Library has provided COUNTER compliant download reports since 2013.

11.2 Citations and altmetrics

Until recently, books have been largely ignored by those attempting to measure impact: both in the realm of citations and altmetrics. A recent paper by Snijder (2016) analysed the role of open access on the impact of books, by examining both citations and altmetrics.

Several researchers have investigated book citations. Glänzel & Schoepflin (1999) discussed the differences in citation behaviour in the humanities and social sciences compared to the sciences. Their conclusion: book citations are strongly linked with the humanities and social sciences. Tang (2008) analyses citations of 750 randomly selected monographs in the humanities and the sciences. In general, the fields of science tend to have lower numbers of uncited books and more recent citations compared to books in the humanities. However, the citation culture within each scholarly field is quite different. Nederhof (2011) deems the results of the impact investigations more useful, when a “citation window” of at least six to eight years is used. According to Nederhof, this better reflects the worldwide reception of the publications. Another factor – not explicitly mentioned by Nederhof – is the fact that writing a book takes considerably more time than writing an article. This might have consequences for the citations in scholarly fields where monographs are the dominant publication form. Using a longer period to accumulate citations in the field of humanities is a solution also proposed by Linmans (2009). By doing so, Linmans is able to assess humanities publications. Furthermore, he expects Google Scholar to be a very useful source of book citations.

The use of Google Scholar as source of citation data is described by Harzing & van der Wal (2008). They conclude that Google Scholar is more comprehensive – especially in the area of books and non-US journals. Whether Google Scholar or Google Books fares better than Scopus citations is tested by Kousha et al. (2011).

Based on a set of 1000 books, these authors determine that the larger amount of citations by the Google products could be used for assessing the publications in book-oriented disciplines in the British humanities and social sciences. More recently, Prins et al. investigated the coverage of social sciences and humanities by Web of Science (WoS) and Google Scholar. They conclude that the coverage by Google Scholar is better for these scholarly fields, although the quality of the data is not as consistent as WoS (Prins, Costas, Leeuwen, & Wouters, 2014).

The availability of citation data for monographs is currently not on the same level as articles: the Thomson Reuters' Book Citation Index was first published in 2011, providing citation information relating to a selection of just 2,5000 titles (Jump, 2011). The paucity of citation data relating to books within the prominent citation databases has inspired several authors to explore alternative sources of citation information. For instance, Kousha and Thelwall use the Google Books index to identify citations from books. Their goal is to compare the number of citations in the Thomson Reuters/Institute for Scientific Information (ISI) databases to those in Google Books (Kousha & Thelwall, 2009). Recently, Thelwall and Sud have used the Thomson Reuters Book Citation Index (BKCI) to explore whether co-authorship of monographs leads to a higher citation impact. Contrary to the results found for articles, the authors conclude that cooperation does not generally lead to more citations (Thelwall & Sud, 2014). Again we see that citation behaviour for monographs differs from journal articles.

In the realm of monographs and other book-length publications, several researchers have been working on alternative ways to assess scholarly value. Perhaps not surprisingly, data from academic libraries is used. For instance, White et al. discuss “libcitations”, where the number of academic libraries holding a certain book is

the unit of measure. The collection of a library is based on qualitative decisions; a monograph that is acquired by a large number of libraries has a larger impact compared to a monograph that only resides in a few libraries. The authors do not compare those metrics to citation data (White et al., 2009; Zuccala & White, 2015). In contrast, Cabezas-Clavijo et al. (2013) use the number of library loans from two academic libraries as a proxy of scholarly impact. When the library-generated data is compared with the available citation data, again the same pattern emerges: at best a weak correlation between the “alternative” metrics and citations. Quite a different approach is used by Zuccala et al. (2014), who use machine-learning techniques to automatically classify the conclusions of book reviews in the field of history. However, the reported results derive from a pilot experiment, and no correlation to citations is described.

The question remains about which altmetrics outlet to use to assess monographs. Here we face an additional complication: most altmetrics tools use an online unique identifier attached to a publication. In the case of journal articles, this will most likely be the Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Books are usually identified by an ISBN, but the use of ISBNs as digital identifier is not as widely spread as DOIs. Another aspect to consider is the preferred outlet: are mentions of books evenly spread among all outlets? If that is not the case, which outlet or outlets are to be measured? Hammarfelt (2014) has compared the coverage in several online sources of 310 English language articles and 54 books – also written in English – in the field of humanities and social sciences. He concludes that for books, Twitter delivers the most results.

Most altmetrics tools use online identifiers – such as DOIs – to identify journal articles. Identifying publications turns out to be more problematic for monographs, which are more commonly associated with an ISBN. In contrast to DOIs, ISBNs are currently not widely used as an online identifier. In other words, a stable online identification was not available.

11.3 Combining downloads, citations and altmetrics: Springer Bookmetrix

We have discussed the role of the platform, downloads, citations and altmetrics. A combination of all these aspects can be found at Springer.com. In 2015, the publisher launched a service called Bookmetrix. The Springer platform displays a combination of downloads, citations and altmetrics for books and chapters.

Some of the data is delivered through Altmetric, listing references across mainstream media, policy sources, Wikipedia, blogs and social media. Most of the other data available for each book and chapter in Bookmetrix have come directly from Springer, including citations (which are gathered from CrossRef), usage data (downloads), and featured book reviews. (Liu, 2015)

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12. Recommendations for the transition to open access in Austria¹¹²

Below is a list of 16 coordinated measures that are recommended by the Working Group National Strategy of the Open Access Network Austria (OANA) and Universities Austria (uniko), to achieve the following goal:

“By 2025, a large part of all scholarly publication activity in Austria should be Open Access. In other words, the final versions of most scholarly publications (in particular all refereed journal articles and conference proceedings) resulting from the support of public resources must be freely accessible on the Internet without delay (Gold Open Access). This goal should be pursued by taking into account the different disciplinary practices and under consideration of the different disciplinary prioritisations of Open Access. The resources required to meet this obligation shall be provided to the authors, or the cost of the publication venues shall be borne directly by the research organisations. The necessary funding must be brought in line with the overall funding priorities for research.”

(1) Introduce open access policy

By 2017, all research and funding organisations financed by public sources should officially adopt and implement their own open access policy and sign the **Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities**. From 2020 onward, the open access policy should be obligatory for all members of the institutions.

(2) Create cost transparency

From 2016 to 2018, research and funding organisations should provide a comprehensive and transparent overview of the costs of the current publication system. On this basis, a permanent group of experts should be established. One of their tasks will be to coordinate the research and funding organisations by monitoring the costs of publication.

(3) Reorganise publishing contracts

- ▶ From 2016 onward, licence agreements with publishers should be concluded in a manner that the research publications of authors from Austria are automatically published open access
- ▶ All contracts from 2020 onward should include this clause
- ▶ Contracts and prices should be made public
- ▶ In their negotiations with publishers, the Austrian Academic Library Consortium (KEMÖ) should be supported by the executives of the research organisations

(4) Introduce publication funds

By 2018, all research and funding organisations should establish transparent publication funds to cover author fees for open access.

(5) Reorganise publication venues

When scholarly publication venues are funded by public resources, the funding conditions should be such that the publication venues can be transformed to open access at the latest from 2020 onward.

(6) Merging the publication infrastructure

Until 2020, research policy-makers should provide financial incentives which, by pooling resources, will permit the establishment of inter-institutional publication structures for publishing high-quality international open access platform in Austria.

(7) Support international cooperation

From 2017 onward, all research and funding organisations in Austria should participate jointly in international initiatives that promote high-quality non-commercial publication models and infrastructures. Access is the

(8) Provide start-up capital

Public funds – as start-up capital - should be available to commercial providers who want to switch to open access or plan new start-ups. This step will enable some providers from Austria to establish themselves on the international market.

(9) Registration of repositories

By 2018, all research organisations should have publicly accessible and internationally registered repositories.

(10) Support self-archiving

From 2016 onward, until complete conversion to open access publication (gold open access), secondary publishing of quality-tested articles should be actively pursued (green open access).

(11) Offer training programmes

From 2016 onward, all research organisations should prepare and provide training programmes for open access and open science.

(12) Acknowledging open access / open science

From 2018 onward, open access and open science activities should always be honoured in the curricula of scholars of all fields, and alternative evaluation systems should be taken into account.

(13) Expand the scope of the copyright reform of 2015

Austrian legislators should modify the copyright law by 2018 so that, independent of the form and place of publication, authors of scholarly publications will have the right to place their publication in a repository and render the original version of their publication freely accessible after a maximum embargo period of 12 months. Furthermore, large bodies of data should be made available for scholarly purposes with no restrictions in terms of search, networking and further use (content mining).

(14) Opening the inventories

All publicly funded archives, museums, libraries and statistical offices should digitise their inventories by 2025, and their collaboration with research organisations should be supported. Previously digitised inventories should be rendered accessible to the public for free and gratuitous use by 2020.

Footnotes

112 https://zenodo.org/record/34079/files/OANA_OA-Recommendations_30-11-2015.pdf

(15) Monitoring during implementation

A target of 80% (green and gold open access) of the total publication output should be achieved by 2020 and 100% gold open access should be achieved by 2025 for all academic publications in Austria. This should be accompanied by a monitoring process of the BMWFW (Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy).

(16) Set targets for open science

The strategy presented here should be developed into a full-fledged open science strategy from 2017 onward. Its aim should be to provide resources to those persons who wish to integrate the instruments of open science into their work processes.

13. List of interviewees

As described in Chapter 2 (Brief and methodology) we have performed in-depth interviews with people from 73 institutions in the eight countries that we have studied. Here right we list the institutions that have kindly let us interview a member of staff.

Country	Funders	Publishers	Libraries	Platform providers / Other
Austria	Austrian Science Fund	Holzhausen Böhlau Verlag Austrian Academy of Sciences Press	Vienna University Library	
Denmark	Innovation Fund Denmark Danish National Research Foundation Danish Council for Independent Research (Humanities)	Aalborg University Press Museum Tusulanum Press Gyldendal Aarhus University Press	Royal Library/ Copenhagen University Library University of Southern Denmark Library State and University Library (AU) Aalborg University Library	
Finland	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies Academy of Finland Ministry of Education and Culture	Tampere University Press Finnish Literature Society Gaudeamus - Helsinki University Press	University of Turku University of Helsinki	
France		Collège de France EDP SCIENCES Presses Sorbonne Nouvelle Institut de recherche pour le développement PUFR Université Grenoble Alpes Presse	Université Lorraine Université Dauphine Couperin	OpenEdition CAIRNS
Germany	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	Perspectiva De Gruyter Göttingen University Press KIT Scientific Publishing Heidelberg University Publishing Language Science Press	Max Planck Digital Library	Svenja Hagenhof Sven Fund
Netherlands	Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research	Brill Amsterdam University Press Leiden University Press	Amsterdam University Library Delft University Library Utrecht University Library	
Norway	Norwegian Research Council (Fritt Ord) UiT The Arctic University of Norway Library Bergen University Akerhus University College Oslo University Library	Scandinavian University Press Cappelen Damm Academic / NOASP	UiT The Arctic University of Norway Library Bergen University Library	
United Kingdom	HEFCE Jisc Wellcome AHRC	Liverpool UP UCL Press Routledge Manchester University Press Oxford University Press Springer Nature	University of Manchester University of Huddersfield University College London Library	

14. Acronyms

AAU	Aalborg University Press
AU	Aarhus University
AHRC	Arts and Humanities Research Council, UK
ANR	L'Agence Nationale de la Recherche
APC	Article processing charge
BFI	Bibliometric research indicator
BMC	BioMedCentral
BPC	Book processing charge
CNRS	National Centre for Scientific Research, France
CRISTin	Current Research Information Systems in Norway
CSC	Center for Scientific Computing (Finland)
CUP	Cambridge University Press
DDA	Demand-driven acquisition
DEFF	Denmark's Electronic Research Library
DFG	German Research Foundation
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books
DOI	Digital object identifiers
EKT	Greek National Documentation Centre
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, UK
ERC	European Research Council
ESRC	Economic and Social Research Council, UK
FWF	Austrian Science Fund
HEFCE	Higher Education Funding Council for England
HeiUP	Heidelberg University Press
HIRMEOS	High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure
HUP	Huddersfield University Press
HvA	Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
IRCSET	Irish Research Council for Science, Engineering & Technology
KU	Knowledge Unlatched
LIBER	Association of European Research Libraries
MPDL	Max Planck Digital Library
MRC	Medical Research Council, UK
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council, UK
NOW	The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research
NRC	National Research Council Canada
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OANA	Open Access Network Austria
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
OBP	Open Book Publishers
OEAW	Austrian Academy of Science

OKTA	Hungarian Scientific Research Fund
OMP	Open Monograph Press
OPERAS	Open Access in the European Research Area through Scholarly Communication
OUP	Oxford University Press
PDA	Patron-driven acquisition
PUFR	Presses Universitaire de Francois Rabbelais
RCUK	Research Councils UK
REF	Research Excellence Framework
ROARMAP	Registry of Open Access Repository Mandates and Policies
SCONUL	Society of College, National and University Libraries, UK
SE	Science Europe
SFI	Science Foundation Ireland
SNSF	Swiss National Science Foundation
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council, UK
STL	Short-term loans
SUP	Stockholm University Press
SURF	Collaborative organisation for ICT in Dutch education and research
UCL Press	University College London Press
UiT	The Arctic University of Norway (Tromsø)
UKB	Dutch University Libraries
UUK	Universities UK
VSNU	Association of Universities in the Netherlands

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16. Questionnaires

Publisher Questionnaire

Section 1: Identifier Questions

This questionnaire consists of five sections with a maximum total of 40 questions, depending on your company's activities.

1. Name of publishing house:

2. Name of respondent:

3. Professional title and business unit of the respondent (e.g. managing director/CEO, editorial director etc.):

4. Are you a Learned Society Publisher?

Yes

No

Publisher Questionnaire

Section 2: Company Profile

5. Which of the following terms describes your company status? (multiple options possible)

- For profit
- Non-profit
- University Press
- Library-based publishing
- Other, namely:

6. In what year was your company established?

7. Please indicate what your company's total sales were for 2015?

- €0 - €1 million
- €1 - €3 million
- €3 - €6 million
- €6 - €12 million
- €12 - €25 million
- Over €25 million

8. How many employees (FTE) did your company have in 2015?

Publisher Questionnaire

Section 3: Monographs and Open Access

In this survey 'monograph' is defined as follows: a long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, and extended to also include peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.

9. In absolute numbers, how many monographs did you publish in 2015?

10. In percentage terms, in which languages were your 2015 monographs published?

	National language	English	Other
2015 monographs	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

11. In absolute numbers, how many monographs did you publish Open Access in 2015?

12. If you have not yet published any Open Access monographs can you tell us why?(If you have published OA books please skip to Q14)

13. What would make you consider publishing OA Monographs?

14. What are your views on the future of Open Access for monographs?(If you have not published OA books skip to Section 4: Q17)

15. In percentage terms, in which languages were your 2015 Open Access monographs published in

	National language	English	Other
2015 OA monographs	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

16. How many Open Access monographs and/or Open Access edited collections has your company published to date?

OA monographs	<input type="text"/>
OA edited collections	<input type="text"/>

Publisher Questionnaire

Section 4: OA Monograph Publishing Models

We are trying to ascertain the total input costs of monographs and have broadly adopted the overall structure from the Andrew Mellon funded report *The Cost of Monograph Publishing*. We are not asking for as granular detail as their survey.

If, nevertheless, you do not have your monograph costs split up in this way, we kindly request that you provide an overall estimate further below that includes these costs (please skip to Q19).

17. Detail costs of monographs/edited collections:

Direct production costs (digital first copy costs including copyediting, typesetting, design, producing first digital file)	<input type="text"/>
Acquisitions (author acquisitions, project and manuscript development as staff time)	<input type="text"/>
Peer Review	<input type="text"/>
Staff Overheads (office costs including rent, travel, communications costs, equipment, professional development)	<input type="text"/>
Press-level Overheads (eg CEO, FCO, COO time)	<input type="text"/>
Marketing (derived as a proportion of annual company spend)	<input type="text"/>
Royalties or author fee (if payable)	<input type="text"/>

19. What are your approximate first copy costs (on average per book) for monographs?

- 0-€3 thousand
- €3-€5 thousand
- €5-€7 thousand
- €7-€10 thousand
- €10-€15 thousand
- €15-€20 thousand
- Above €20 thousand

20. In percentage terms, how many of your 2015 Open Access monographs were paid for by outside funding bodies? (If you do not publish Open Access monographs please skip to Section 5: Q32)

21. Please list the top three funding sources.

1.

2.

3.

22. In percentage terms, how many of your 2015 Open Access monographs were unfunded (i.e. published at the company's risk)?

23. Have you published your Open Access book policy on your website?

No

Yes (please provide the URL to your OA policy)

24. If applicable, does your company have a standard BPC charge?

Yes, namely:

No, the BPC varies along these determinants (e.g. length, complexity, license):

25. If applicable, do you indicate on your website what your standard BPC charge is?

- Yes
 No

26. Do you expect the number of monographs you publish Open Access to increase or decrease?

- Increase
 Decrease
 Remain constant

27. What kind of funder mandates have applied to your monographs?

Public funders (please specify)

Private funders (please specify)

28. If applicable, what were other, indirect funding sources for your 2015 Open Access monographs?

29. In absolute numbers, under which licenses did you publish your 2015 Open Access monographs?

CC-BY

CC-BY-SA

CC-BY-NC

CC-BY-ND

CC-BY-NC-SA

CC-BY-NC-ND

Other (specify)

30. Can you summarise why you select the licenses that you have?

31. Has there been a significant change in your Open Access monograph output in the first half of 2016, or have you begun a new OA for books programme?

- No
- Yes (please let us know why and to what extent it has grown in percentage terms)

Publisher Questionnaire

Section 5: Publication Formats

32. In which (technical) formats were your 2015 monographs published? (multiple options possible)

- Hardback
- Paperback
- PDF
- HTML
- MOBI
- EPUB
- Other, namely:

33. In which Open Access digital formats were your 2015 Open Access monographs published? (If you do not publish Open Access monographs, please submit the questionnaire at the end of Q40)

- PDF
- HTML
- MOBI
- EPUB
- Other, namely:

34. What pricing policies were adopted for the non-OA edition of OA print monographs?

- Same as for closed book
- Lower than for closed book
- Higher than for closed book

35. Where you make Open Access print books available please specify printing preference

- POD
- Short-run digital
- Conventional offset

36. What pricing policies were adopted for the non-OA ebook edition of OA monographs?

- Same as for closed book
- Lower than for closed book
- Higher than for closed book

37. If you sell your ebooks that are otherwise made available as OA monographs please indicate where they can be purchased. (If you do not publish Open Access monographs please skip to the end and press the Submit button)

- Amazon
- Google Play
- EBSCO
- Ebrary
- Your website
- Other (please specify):

38. How do you handle funder requirements?

Do you have instructions
or a procedure to deal with
funder
acknowledgements?

Do you add funder
information to the
metadata for the book?

Do you deposit OA
monographs on behalf of
authors?

Do you have a self-
archiving policy for
chapters/books?

39. We have asked mostly for a snapshot of 2015 in the questions above but it would be helpful if you could give us a rough idea of how many books you have published as open access in total over the years.

40. Please let us know what your working definition for Open Access is as applied to monographs and edited collections.

Funder Questionnaire

In this survey 'monograph' is defined as follows: a long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, and extended to also include peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.

1. Name of funding organisation:

2. Name of respondent:

3. Professional title and business unit:

4. What term best defines your funding organisation?

Public

Private

5. What is your total research funding budget?

6. To which research subject(s) does your funding extend?

7. Please let us know what your working definition for Open Access is as applied to monographs and edited collections.

8. Are you able to indicate what percentage of your research funding goes to OA publishing?

No

Yes, namely:

9. Do you mandate OA for monographs resulting from funded research?

Yes

No (proceed to question 20)

10. What is the nature of your OA mandate for monographs?

Gold

Green

Gold + green

11. Do you have deposit requirements for funded OA monographs?

No

Yes, namely:

12. In case it is known, of what does your OA support consist (in monetary value in euros):

Monographs

Monograph chapters

Journal articles

Other (please specify)

13. If applicable, how is your monograph support programme set up (e.g. part of a research grant, OA publication fund)?

14. Can you list the countries for which your OA budget is eligible?

15. Do you have licensing requirements for funded OA monographs?

No

Yes, namely:

16. Do you ask recipients to acknowledge your financial contribution within the book file and/or elsewhere?

No

Yes, namely:

17. Do you monitor compliancy with your OA mandate?

No

Yes, namely:

18. What incentives or penalties are utilized to encourage compliance?

19. If you do not fund OA monographs could you say why?

20. Where do you think OA for monographs is heading – in light of mandates, funding, institutional requirements and author expectations? Will it follow the growth of OA journals, or plateau out at a certain level?

21. In your view, who should be driving the change towards OA for monographs?

Library Questionnaire

Section 1: Identifier Questions

1. Name of library:

2. Name of respondent:

3. Professional title and business unit of respondent:

Library Questionnaire

Section 2: Your Library and Monographs

In this survey 'monograph' is defined as follows: a long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, and extended to also include peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.

Are you responsible for your library's decision making process regarding joining open access initiatives? If not, please redirect this questionnaire to the person who is.

4. Does your institution have a university press? If yes:

Name of University Press

Independent of the
Library (yes/no)

Reporting to the Library
(yes/no)

Do you know what
proportion of your
university press titles are
open access?

5. Please let us know what your working definition for Open Access is as applied to monographs and edited collections.

6. Does your institution mandate OA for monographs, or promote or support OA for monographs in any way?

Yes (go to question 7)

No (go to question 8)

7. Please describe the policies to support OA monographs (and then proceed to question 11)

OA mandate (including monographs)

Publication fund for BPCs

Participation in collaborative funding model (i.e. Knowledge Unlatched, OpenEdition freemium)

Participation in membership schemes from publishers

Aggregating publications in your institutional repository

Support for researchers, through Scholarly communication department, support for submitting publications in the institutional repository, advocacy, training etc

Specific measures to include OA publications in the institutions' research assessment

Other, namely:

8. Can you give the main reasons for not supporting OA for monographs?

9. Are you considering supporting OA for monographs in any way?

10. If you support OA monograph projects, please indicate your criteria:

11. We would like to know where funding for Open Access monographs in 2015 was coming from. Has your library set up a special Open Access support fund?

12. Has your OA fund been spent within the fiscal year of 2015?

- Yes, after 3 months
- Yes, after 6 months
- Yes, after 9 months
- No, this percentage was left:

13. Do these funds come from renewable budgets or are they decided individually each year?

- Renewable budgets
- Individual allocation

14. What discovery tools do you use in your library?

- Primo
- OCLC WorldCat,
- Proquest/SerialsSolutions
- EBSCO
- Other, namely:

15. Do you have any recommendations to improve the discovery of OA content?

16. Would your Library like to expand its support for open access? If so, in what way?

17. What are the main barriers for expanding support for open access?

18. What would need to change for the expansion to take place?

Publisher interview questions

Name:

Position:

Company:

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed. This will not take more than an hour, and perhaps less.

What we are looking for here is to understand your approach to publishing OA monographs, and your expectations and perceptions of where OA for monographs in HSS especially, and where possible STEM, is going and how you see your company fitting into this landscape.

This is our working definition of a monograph:

A long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, and extended to also include peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.

PRICING AND FUNDING

1. Can you start with a description of your pricing policy for OA monographs?
 - a) Do you charge BPCs?
 - b) Do you take part in collaborative funding models?
 - c) Do you have a membership model for libraries?
2. If you ask for BPCs, how do you determine the BPC level?
3. Can you give an estimate of:
 - a) Average first copy costs for OA monographs?
 - b) The typical range of first copy costs for OA monographs?
4. Assuming the costs of getting to first digital file are the same for OA and non-OA are there any cost savings that you can see in managing the publication over the years (e.g. – in sales, marketing, file management over time, distribution, publishing overheads etc.)?
5. How would you like to see funding for OA monographs administered? I.e. do you see a role for a centrally dispersed method for funding to reach publishers?
6. What are the three most successful schemes for OA funding for monographs, in your view?

7. Have different funding models, both BPC and non-BPC, been combined to enable a monograph to go OA? Do you ever cross-subsidise OA monographs?
8. How do you handle funder requirements?
 - a) Do you have instructions or a procedure to deal with funder acknowledgements?
 - b) Do you add funder information to the metadata for the book?
 - c) Do you deposit OA monographs on behalf of authors?
 - d) Do you have a self-archiving policy for chapters/books?
9. We're trying to establish in what ways OA monographs are published differently from non-OA monographs – and whether these will change. Can you speak a bit about:
 - a) Are any differences in pricing and mark-up strategies, and if so what?
 - b) Are the for sale formats likely to be the same in the near/distant future?
 - c) Do you expect to receive the same amount of revenue from BPCs plus sales from other formats as you would get from the traditional way of publishing books?
 - d) If sales drop do you expect there to be a corresponding increase in BPC charges?
 - e) Do you expect the distribution of the total publishing costs (acquisition, editing, production, marketing, distribution etc.) to change coming from non-OA to OA monographs?
 - f) Do you expect a speedier publishing process for the OA monograph?
 - g) Do you have a different peer review process for OA monographs, or did you change your process when introducing OA?

FORMATS and DISTRIBUTION

10. What is your strategy for making available OA monographs?
 - a) In what format is the OA edition made available? As PDF, HTML, ePub?
 - b) Where is the OA edition made available? On your website, through third parties (hosting platforms such as JSTOR, OAPEN, OpenEdition, Google Books, other)
11. What is your strategy for publishing OA monographs in other formats? Which of the following are available? And do you expect this to change?
 - a) HB
 - b) PB
 - c) retail ebook (ePub, Mobi, other)
 - d) institutional ebook (PDF, Epub, other)

12. Do you expect sales of print and other digital formats of OA monographs to grow or contract in the future?
13. Do you expect discovery of OA to get better or worse?
14. What, in your view, should be done to improve discovery of OA monographs and how long will it be before this might happen?

YOUR POLICY and THE FUTURE

15. Could you describe the process leading up to the formulation of your OA policy for monographs?
16. What reasons made you include monographs in your OA policies?
17. What kind of challenges did you encounter when introducing the OA policy for monographs?
18. What reactions have you received from the community since introducing your OA policy for monographs?
19. Do you think that certain types of monographs are better suited for OA publishing than others? If so, what kind of monograph content is best suited for OA publishing?
20. Do you have any views on mandates and embargo's for OA monographs and chapters in peer reviewed edited collections?
21. What role does the publishing language have for the development of the OA monograph?
22. Where do you think OA for books is heading – in light of mandates, funding, institutional requirements and author expectations? Will it grow, or plateau out at a certain level?
23. What are the main barriers for expanding OA into monographs further?
24. What incentives do you see as necessary for expanding OA into monographs further?

Funder interview questions

Name

Position

Organisation

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed. This won't take more than an hour of your time, and possibly less.

What we are looking for here are your expectations and perceptions of where Open Access (OA) for monographs is going and specifically how you see this development from a funding perspective.

This is our working definition of a monograph:

A long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, and extended to also include peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.

1. Has your organisation included monographs in any OA publication policy? (**if NO go to question number 17**)
2. How do you mandate OA for monographs?
3. Is this specifically for books or part of an overall mandate for all research output including journal articles?
4. Could you describe the process leading up to the formulation of the mandate?
5. Do you have funds for BPCs or how do you financially support OA for monographs?
6. If you pay BPCs, do you then have a price cap? How do you determine the BPC level?
7. What reasons made you include monographs in your OA policies?
8. What kind of challenges did you encounter when mandating OA for monographs?
9. What reactions have you received from the community since introducing your OA monograph mandate?
10. Do you monitor compliancy with your OA mandate, and if so how?
11. What incentives or penalties are utilised to encourage compliance?
12. Are there things you would like to change in your existing mandate?
13. Who would you like to see administering funding for OA monographs
 - a. Publishers
 - b. Authors
 - c. Libraries
 - d. Other intermediaries (e.g. the Copyright Clearance Center or the equivalent in your country)

14. What are the three most successful schemes for OA funding for monographs, in your view?
15. Do you have any views on mandates for chapters in edited specialist research book outputs?
16. What is your view on self-archiving of books and chapters (green OA)?
17. What are the main reasons for your organisation not to mandate OA to monographs?
18. Has your organisation considered including monographs in your OA policies? And, if so, in what way?
19. What would be helpful for you when/if developing an OA mandate for monographs?
20. In your country, how is the status, generally speaking, perceived of the scholarly monograph?
21. How do you seek and obtain knowledge about monograph publishing and OA as basis for decision making in this field?
22. What incentives or changes in the current book publishing landscape do you see as necessary for expanding OA into monographs further?
23. What incentives and/or penalties could you envisage to encourage compliance?
24. Where do you think OA for monographs is heading – in light of mandates, funding, institutional requirements and author expectations? Will it follow the growth of OA journals, or plateau out at a certain level?
25. In your view, who should be driving the change towards OA for monographs?

Library interview questions

Name

Position

University

Size of University in terms of number of degree-seeking students

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed. This shouldn't take more than forty five to sixty minutes.

What we are looking for here are your activities and motivations around open access policies, in particular for OA monographs, your expectations and perceptions of where OA for monographs is going, and specifically how you see this development from a library perspective.

We take as our starting point the following working definition of the monograph: *A long, academic and peer reviewed work on a single topic normally written by a single author, or peer reviewed edited collections by multiple authors.*

POLICY

1. Does your institution mandate OA for monographs, or promote or support OA for monographs in any way? (*if NO go to question number 16*)
2. Please describe the policies to support OA monographs
 - a. OA mandate (including monographs)
 - b. Publication fund for BPC's
 - c. Participation in collaborative funding model (i.e. Knowledge Unlatched, OpenEdition freemium)
 - d. Participation in membership schemes from publishers
 - e. University or Library support for in-house publishing department or University Press
 - f. Aggregating publications in your institutional repository
 - g. Support for researchers, through Scholarly communication department, support for submitting publications in the institutional repository, advocacy, training etc
 - h. Specific measures to include OA publications in the institutions' research assessment
 - i. Other?
3. Are these policies specifically for books or part of an overall policy for all research output (including journal articles)?
4. Could you describe the process leading up to the formulation of the OA policy for monographs?
 - a. What reasons made you include monographs in your OA policies?

- b. What kind of challenges did you encounter when introducing the OA policy for monographs?
5. What reactions have you received from the community since introducing your OA policy for monographs?
6. How do you evaluate your OA policies?
7. Do you monitor compliancy with your OA policy, and if so how?
 - a. Are there incentives or penalties to encourage compliance?
8. Are there things you would like to change in your existing policy?
9. What is your view on self-archiving of books and chapters (green OA)?
10. Do you actively promote the discovery of OA content, including books?
 - a. If so, how? Do you work with intermediaries or OA resources?

FUNDING

11. How do you fund your support for OA monographs?
 - a. Is this a specific budget for OA, part of the Acquisitions budget, a combination of sources, or something else?
 - b. Are these budgets renewable, or do they require annual decision making?
12. Did you decline to take part in collaborative or membership schemes?
 - a. Could you explain why you decided not to participate, what were the main reasons?
13. If you pay BPCs, do you then have a price cap? How do you determine the BPC level?
14. Who would you like to see administering funding for OA monographs
 - a. Publishers
 - b. Authors
 - c. Libraries
 - d. Other intermediaries (e.g. the Copyright Clearance Center or the equivalent in your country)
15. What are the three most successful schemes for OA funding for monographs, in your view? (**Jump to question number 20**)
16. What are the main reasons for your organisation not to support OA to monographs?
17. Has your organisation considered including monographs in your OA policies? And, if so, in what way?
18. What would be helpful for you when/if developing an OA mandate for monographs?

THE LANDSCAPE AND THE FUTURE

19. In your country, how is the status, generally speaking, of the scholarly monograph?

20. How do you seek and obtain knowledge about monograph publishing and OA as basis for decision making in this field?
21. In your view, what are the biggest obstacles for expanding OA into monographs further?
22. What incentives or changes in the current book publishing landscape do you see as necessary for expanding OA into monographs further?
23. Where do you think OA for monographs is heading – in light of mandates, funding, institutional requirements and author expectations? Will it follow the growth of OA journals, or plateau out at a certain level?
24. In your view, who should be driving the change towards OA for monographs?

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